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CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D10: CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design

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Executive Summary

D10 (*CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design*) corresponds to the final update of D9 (*CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem design*). D9 established the CODECO definitions, its initial architectural design of CODECO, and provided technological boundaries and alignment in terms of technologies used in the CODECO framework. D9, released in month 6 (M6) of CODECO has also provided the initial guidelines for the CODECO open-source ecosystem.

The differences between D9 and D10 can be summarized as follows. Firstly, D10 provides the full CODECO framework architecture taking into consideration concepts and software developed during M7-M18. Secondly, D10 updates to the CODECO framework architecture focusing on the future federated clusters operation, proposing directions to be researched and developed from M19 until M36 (WP4). Thirdly, it provides an update on technological guidelines and best practices concerning experimentation and validation in CODECO. Fourthly, it updates the CODECO open-source ecosystem guidelines.

Keywords: Edge-Cloud continuum; orchestration; Kubernetes; AI/ML; network; data; compute; context-awareness.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, Accounting
ACM	Automated Configuration Manager
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
APOC	Awesome Procedures on Cypher
AR	Augmented Reality
BTLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CA	Context-awareness
CD	Compute Domain
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CLI	Command Line Interface
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimental Framework
CP	Customer Premises
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
CSDG	CODECO Synthetic Data Generator
DEV	Developer
DL	Deep Learning
DoA	Description of the Action
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
EC	European Commission
EDA	Encoder Decoder Architectures
EN	Edge Node
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
FaaS	Function as a Service
FaaS	Function as a Service
FC	Federated Clusters
FIDO	Fast Identity Online
FL	Federated Learning
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GNNs	Graph Neural Networks
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRU	Gate Recurrent
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS	International Data Spaces
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force

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Acronym	Meaning
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IPR	Intellectual Property
IPSec	Internet Protocol Security
IPv6	Internet Protocol Version 6
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
KCP	Kubernetes like Control Plane
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L2	Layer 2
L3	Layer 3
LPM	L2S-M Performance Measurement module
LS2-M	Layer Two Virtual Private Network Service Model
LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
LTE	Long-term Evolution
MAC	Media Access Control
MAPE	<i>Mean Absolute Percentage Error</i>
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
MDM	Metadata Manager
MEC	Multi-access Edge computing
MGR	Infrastructure Manager
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Protocol
ND	Network Domain
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
NGIOT	Next Generation Internet of Things
NN	Neural Network
NSM	Network State Management
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
OAS	Open API Specification
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OLM	Operator Lifecycle Management
OS	Operating System
OSS	Open-source system
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
PLS	Programmable Layer 2 Switches
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
RFC	Request for Comments
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RTT	Round Trip Time
SDN	Software Defined Network
STGNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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Acronym	Meaning
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VoIP	Voice over IP
VR	Virtual Reality
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

List of Definitions

Term	Definition
Application	Computer software design to perform a single or several specific tasks, e.g., a calendar. In CODECO, an application is composed by at least one micro-service, i.e., applications are a collection of services that are loosely coupled, highly available, and independently deployable.
Application Programming Interface (API)	Well defined specification used in a software program to access services or resources provided by another software application. Establishes the interface between two different applications.
Cloud	IT environment that abstracts, pools, and shares IT resources across a network. A Cloud is a software-defined environment associated with hyperscale data centres, often far from the data sources or end-user.
Cloud computing	The act of running application workloads on a Cloud.
Cluster	A K8s cluster consists of the components that are a part of the control plane (master nodes) and worker nodes, where containerised applications run. A cluster corresponds to the logical environment where pods run in a way that has been orchestrated by a human operator.
Consumer	See service recipient
Container	Container follows the K8s definition, where it is a package with the overall settings (workload, state, data) to allow execution of an application in an independent way. A container runs logically in a pod.
Container manager	See orchestrator.
Container orchestrator	A tool that assists the setup and lifetime management of containerised applications. Examples of container orchestrators are K8s and Docker swarm.
CR	From K8s. CRs correspond to new objects (or instances of) defined by CRDs. A custom resource is the API extension mechanism in Kubernetes.
CRD	From K8s. A custom resource definition (CRD) defines a CR and lists out all the configuration available to users of a K8s operator. Written in YAML it has a limit of 1 MiB due to being stored in the K8s etcd, which has been designed to handle small key value pairs typical for metadata. CRDs supply definitions for CRs, thus assisting in creating new types of resources without having to add another API server in K8s.
Edge	An IT environment that abstracts, pools, and supplies IT resource sharing in a location close to data sources (e.g., IoT devices, end-user). Place computing resources closer to the user or the device, at the “edge” of the network, rather than in a hyperscale cloud data centre that might be many miles away in the “core” of the network. CODECO adopts the terms supported far Edge and near Edge as in NGIoT [1].
Edge-Cloud continuum	The overall IT environment interconnecting and end-user to services running across the far Edge until the Cloud.
End-user	See User.
far Edge	The notion of far Edge reflects the elements located on customer premises, covering not only the existing cyber-physical systems but also the interfaces to the real-world, as well as context-awareness (e.g., situational awareness) required to perform local/partial decisions (storage, processing, analysis decisions) upon data collected. Hence, the far Edge embodies a full intertwining to the real-world which can only be provided via some form of context-awareness, behaviour inference and learning, i.e., integration of intelligence. Physically, the near Edge integrates the last mile concept. Applications that run on the far Edge are often time-sensitive, require ultra-low latency, high scalability, and high throughput. Examples are AR/VR, Gaming. Other used terms for far Edge are deep Edge, micro-Edge.
Interconnection	The physical and logical linking of public communications networks used by the same or a different undertaking to allow the users of one undertaking to

Term	Definition
	communicate with users of the same or another undertaking, or to access services provided by another undertaking.
K8s control plane	The control plane is the system that can assist in defining, deploying, and managing the lifecycle of containers in a cluster. It continuously manages object states, responding to changes in the cluster and triggering changes to match a desired performance state. The K8s control plane is made up of three major components: the scheduler (kube-scheduler), the controller manager (kube-controller-manager) and the API server (kube-apiserver). The K8s control plane can run a single master node or can be replicated across multiple master nodes for high reliability.
Last mile	From telecommunications, the last mile corresponds to the final segment between the service provider and the user. Today, the last mile is often based on wireless and cellular communications.
Master node	The K8s node that holds the K8s control plane. The K8s master node holds configuration and state data and manages communication towards worker nodes (via the K8s API), to schedule containers efficiently.
Micro-service	An underlying component service of an application. Each micro-service in an application serves a specific service. An example is an application that integrates a PubSub broker; a database; an object detection application.
Migration	Process of transferring an ongoing application workload between two nodes.
Near Edge	near Edge is a definition tied to the Edge elements and services that are in the access/core regions of the network, i.e., between the far Edge and the Cloud data centres. The near Edge reflects the integration of ML to best support resource managements and to best orchestrate the applications to be served. An example of a near Edge architecture is the ETSI MEC 119. Near Edge hosts generic services. An example of a near Edge service is CDN.
Network service	Set of operational network functionality needed to sustain user services. Examples of network services in CODECO are resource management, network exposure. For instance, Internet connectivity is a network service
Network infrastructure	Collection of links and of networking nodes that together enable data transmission between (Internet) users. The links connect the nodes together and are themselves built upon an underlying transmission network which physically pushes the message across the link.
Offloading	Offloading implies moving an application and its micro-services across different environments. Therefore, with offloading, the "old" environment, the application workload and its state are deleted and not simply made inactive; a copy of workload and of state, followed by eventual adaptation of state is done in the "new" environment.
Operator	From K8s. A Kubernetes operator watches a CR type and takes application-specific actions to make the current state match the desired state in that resource. Hence, an operator is a software extension that allows to encapsulate K8s application resources (i.e., pods, Deployments, Daemon sets, Stateful sets, Jobs, Services, ConfigMaps, etc.) by creating a CR and a K8s controller. Operators track cluster events related to specific types of CRs. These CRs can track by default three types of events—add, update, and delete.
pod	pod follows also the K8s definition, being a logical wrapper entity for containers to be executed on a K8s cluster. This logical wrapper "holds" a group of one or more containers with shared storage and network resources, and a common namespace, providing a definition to run the containers. pod may hold more than one container. A pod is the unit of replication in a cluster.
Recipient of a service	"Recipient of the service" [2000/31/EC Art.2.d] any natural or legal person who, for professional ends or otherwise, uses an information society service, for the purposes of seeking information or making it accessible.
Replication	Replication implies that an application and its micro-services are copied across different locations, i.e., there are multiple replicas of the application in a system,

Term	Definition
	some active, and some inactive. Replication requires a way to synchronize state across an "old" and a "new" environment where the application is deployed and implies that even inactive applications consume resources (at least storage).
Resources	A physical or virtual element of a global system. For instance, bandwidth, energy, data, devices, are examples of resources in CODECO.
Scheduler	A software-based entity that performs assignment of resources to perform specific tasks. The scheduler performs assignments based on a specific performance target, e.g., load-balancing, bounded latency, low jitter.
Session	Permanent or transient information exchange between two or more devices and/or users.
Stateful applications	Stateful applications keep state on clusters, and require that state (data, status of the application) to be kept.
Stateless applications	Stateless applications require no data storage to work.
User	A legal entity or individual using or requesting a publicly available electronic communications service for private or business purposes, without necessarily having subscribed to such service. In CODECO, a user can be i) a legal entity or individual (application developer) relying on the CODECO framework to setup and deploy an application across the Edge-Cloud continuum; ii) a legal entity or individual (CODECO service operator) relying on the CODECO framework to manage cluster configuration (setup) and runtime.
User service	A system that fulfils a need from an Internet end-user. For instance, VoIP and CDN are examples of user services.
Worker node	CODECO adopts the K8s worker node terminology. The workers are entities (K8s nodes) that run containerised micro-service. Each cluster has at least one worker node. pods are assigned to worker nodes, where a local daemon (Kubelet) manages the worker nodes life cycle. Kubelet is also the entry point to the K8s control plane.
Workload	An active micro-service and its state. A workload in CODECO is the minimum viable "unit" for migration, as it comprises a micro-service (e.g., storage), its state, and dependencies (e.g., networking resources).
Underlay network infrastructure	The physical infrastructure that enables frames and packets to be forwarded from one point to another. Comprises the end-to-end physical path equipment, e.g., switches, routers. From an OSI model perspective, comprises the first three layers of the OSI model: physical, data link, and network.
Overlay network infrastructure	The software-driven transportation of network traffic, operating over the underlay network and abstracting low-level details of traffic forwarding, from a Kubernetes perspective. It is therefore a virtual network, i.e., provides an abstraction of the resources provided by the underlay network.

Acknowledgements

We thank all CODECO Partners for the commitment and involvement in the development of the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit, and their contributions to this deliverable. Special thanks to the internal reviewers from IBM and INTRA.

1 Introduction

The CODECO D10 deliverable provides an overview on the CODECO architecture, its technological boundaries; its positioning within the context of a flexible Edge-Cloud continuum.

D10 corresponds to an update of Deliverable D9 [2], report that describes the initial CODECO architectural design and provided guidelines to the CODECO experimentation and operation, as well as the initial guidelines to the CODECO open-source ecosystem during the first six months of the project.

D10 corresponds to a deliverable of *Work Package 2 (WP2)*, tasks 2.2 (*Technological Boundaries and Global Validation Design Aspects*), tasks 2.3 (*Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Design*), and task 2.4 (*CODECO architectural design*).

To be highlighted is the update to the CODECO reference architecture based on the work developed between M7 and M18 of the project in the CODECO components, and also in the CODECO use-cases, which led to changes in the design of the architecture. A second relevant aspect concerns the alignment of the CODECO reference architecture with the EUEdgeCloudIoT¹ architecture and taxonomy developments. A third relates with the initial directions being taken by CODECO in WP4 concerning a federated clusters' operation.

The key differences between D10 and the intermediate deliverable D9 can be summarized as follows:

- D10 provides the current CODECO reference architecture, aligned with the latest operational releases in CODECO, its use-cases, and also with reference architectural efforts in Europe.
- D10 provides an overview on relevant directions towards the CODECO federated cluster operation, to be developed in the second phase of CODECO, M19-M36.
- It updates the technological guidelines adopted by the CODECO consortium in the technical and experimentation WPs, concerning tools, benchmarking, analysis, and code development.
- It updates the CODECO OSS ecosystem guidelines and development.

1.1 Document Scope

As explained, D10 is an update of D9. The deliverable has been developed in the second phase of Task 2.4, from M14 (February 2024) to M18 (June 2024) of CODECO. This corresponds to a second phase of WP2 articulated under T2.4, to provide the final aspects of the architectural design of CODECO for a single cluster, and to provide starting points for the federated cluster operation, integrating changes and customizations derived from the other WPs.

This deliverable provides:

- The final CODECO architectural design for a single cluster operation, its components, and operational, including a list of assumptions and requirements to be passed to the other WPs in CODECO.
- Challenges and priorities to be addressed as starting point in CODECO on the second phase of the project.

¹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

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- Experimentation guidelines, including an overview on the existing tools (infrastructures, CODECO Experimentation Framework, CODECO synthetic Data generator, etc).

1.2 Dependencies

D10 has a dependency to Deliverable D9 [2], as it corresponds to the final update of D9. Furthermore, the reader is advised to check the companion deliverable D8 (Use-cases) [3] which provides additional input into the use-cases and application of the CODECO framework and its components in different environments and towards different vertical domains.

Finally, for the readers interested in experimenting the CODECO code, Deliverable D12 [4] should be considered (companion report to the existing OSS code)².

1.3 Document Structure

The Deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the CODECO architecture and the CODECO components.
- **Section 2** provides a functional overview on the CODECO architecture, including the alignment of the CODECO architecture with the latest development of the EUEdgeCloudIoT (EUCEI)³ Cloud-Edge-IoT reference architecture.
- **Section 3** provides the low-level design of the CODECO architecture, considering the first phase of the project (single cluster operation).
- **Section 4** debates on the expected CODECO operation in federated clusters, discussing challenges and priorities selected by the CODECO consortium for the second phase of the project (M19-M36).
- **Section 5** covers an update on the CODECO global validation aspects, covering the experimental tools in use, the CODECO experimental framework, and testbeds being used in CODECO.
- **Section 6** provides an update on the CODECO open-source ecosystem development and design.
- **Section 7** concludes the deliverable, presenting next steps.
- **Annex I** provides the current CODECO metrics (data, network, compute), highlighting implemented and planned metrics.
- **Annex II** provides an example for the CODECO Application Model.

² <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

³ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

2 Functional Overview of the CODECO Architecture

2.1 Kubernetes Background

The terminology used in this deliverable is provided the “*List of Definitions*”. Furthermore, for the sake of readability, this sub-section briefly explains the overall K8s operation and provides a sub-set of the terms related with dynamic container orchestration [5][6], to assist the reader in getting a faster grasp of the proposed architecture.

An **application** is considered to consist of multiple **micro-services** that can be run independently based on container technology, such as Docker. This is named containerized micro-service, or containerized application. **Application workload** refers therefore to the containerized micro-services, namely, binary system, data, state, i.e., a set of global variables defined in the micro-services and required at run-time. A containerized application therefore consists of one or several containerized micro-services which are interconnected via specific interfacing policies. The different micro-services may be deployed across different **nodes**, i.e., different cyber-physical systems (including virtual machines). To scale the application, allowing to meet specific requirements, e.g., bounded latency, it is feasible to consider **migration** strategies, e.g., transparent **replication** or **offloading**, also known as **relocation**. Applications supported in this process can be stateless or stateful. Stateless applications require no data storage to work. An example is a Web search. Stateful applications keep state on clusters, and require that state (data, status of the application) to be kept and eventually found.

Edge, Cloud definitions, including the notions of **far Edge/near Edge** follow the line of thought being driven in the European initiatives EUCEI⁴ and former *Next Generation IoT (NGIoT)*⁵ and, the vision for smart, decentralised Edge-Cloud environments for IoT applications [1].

The term **Container** follows the K8s definition, where it is a package with the overall settings (workload, state, data) to allow execution of an application in an independent way and logically run in a pod.

A **pod** follows also the K8s definition, being a logical wrapper entity for containers to be executed on a K8s cluster. This logical wrapper “holds” a group of one or more containers with shared storage and network resources, and a common namespace, providing a definition to run the containers. Hence, a pod is the unit of replication in a cluster. A (K8s) **cluster** corresponds to the logical environment where pods run in a way that has been orchestrated by a human operator (the **user**).

The high-level operation of K8s is illustrated in Figure 1. A K8s cluster consists of multiple **worker nodes**, where pods are scheduled to, and a K8s “**master node**”, which corresponds to the **K8s control plane** and which will be named as K8s control node, from now on in this document. K8s nodes run in Edge-Cloud **nodes**, i.e., cyber-physical systems.

4 <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

5 <https://www.ngiot.eu/>

Figure 1: K8s high-level operation, 1 cluster, roles in the master and worker nodes.

The master node (control plane) stores configuration and data and manages worker nodes and pods in a cluster. For this, the master node integrates **etcd**, a key-value internal database, which keeps the configuration of a cluster, is based on the Raft consensus protocol [7], and which stores/manages, among other K8s resources, the **K8s Custom Resource Definitions, CRDs**; the API server (**K8s API** or **kube-apiserver**); **scheduler**; **controller-manager**. The K8s API is the control plane front-end component.

The **controller** is the control-plane component (control loop) that runs processes which are continuously checking the state of the cluster and comparing them to the desired state in etcd, then being able to make or to request changes when required. The controller usually performs re-scheduling based on actions provided by the API server, but it can also execute the action itself. For example, a controller can scale nodes in a cluster. When the desired state is updated, the controllers will detect the mismatch and try to bring the cluster state to the desired one.

The desired state of a cluster is defined by a **user** via the API server. In CODECO, a user is i) an **application developer (user DEV)**, willing to deploy an application across Edge-Cloud; ii) a K8s infrastructure manager (**user MGR**), willing to automate the configuration, deployment, and management of clusters.

In K8s, the API server receives the cluster configuration and application requirements from the user, storing them in a K8s format (**CRDs**) based on YAML⁶, in etcd. CRDs provide a definition to **Custom Resources (CRs)**, listing out all the configuration available to users.

A K8s **operator** (a combination of CRs and a custom controller) is a software extension that provides support to package, deploy, and manage K8s resources. The operator configuration is provided in a CRD to the user; the operator is therefore associated with a CRD/CR. The operator watches the CR and takes resource-specific actions to make the current state match the desired state in that resource.

A scheduler (in the case of K8s, kube-scheduler; in the case of CODECO, SWM-scheduler) handles the pod to Node matching decisions, so that **Kubelet** on the worker nodes can then

⁶ <https://yaml.org/>

run the pods. Kubelet is the entry point from/to the K8s control plane. We also highlight that currently K8s provides replication support, and not offloading support, an aspect that we expect to further explore in CODECO, to best support new challenges, such as node mobility.

For the matching, K8s relies on a filtering and scoring approach. On a first phase (**filtering**), the scheduler checks which nodes can meet the scheduling requirements. These nodes are named **feasible nodes**. On a second phase (**scoring**), the scheduler ranks the feasible nodes for the "best" pod deployment, by calculating scheduling priorities, also defined in the desired state. As shall be seen in section 3.1.4 (SWM), CODECO follows a different approach to perform the pod-Node matching, allowing more flexibility and providing the basis to consider a matching that suits better the application requirements.

The applications across Edge-Cloud are therefore orchestrated via multiple clusters, where an Edge environment, or an Edge-Cloud environment may be inside a single cluster (e.g., if under the operation of a same service provider) or of multiple clusters (e.g., across multi-domain environments). We highlight here that an Edge node is different from a K8s node. A K8s node may (or not) reside on an Edge node. For a better understanding about the CODECO to CEI mapping, the reader can check section 2.3.

2.2 Global Architecture Perspective

CODECO is a containerised application orchestration framework (TRL 4-5), independent and yet pluggable to Kubernetes⁷ (K8s). CODECO aims at providing support for a flexible and cognitive *Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI)* infrastructure. The notion of infrastructure in CODECO considers different infrastructure perspectives: the **networking** perspective, where the network is perceived both as the *underlay* and *overlay* infrastructure required to support the deployment of containerised applications across CEI; the **data observability** perspective, bringing input on the data dependencies that micro-services may have, and that is important to consider during the application deployment and re-deployment; the **computational** perspective, bringing input on the suitable nodes to serve an application, taking into consideration. CODECO addresses the orchestration across these three different perspectives in an integrated approach, which is named as **data-compute-network** orchestration.

Figure 2: The CODECO data-compute-network approach for CEI.

⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/>

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The motivation to develop such an orchestration framework relates with the current evolutionary aspects of the CEI continuum [6]. In this context, applications (and their components) need to be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile, to run anywhere and everywhere. Secondly, there is a need to handle large amounts of data often with very different features both in terms of computation (processing) and exchange (networking), including those with low latency demands. Thirdly, it is important to guarantee a smooth data flow, to allow for a smooth and secure integration end-to-end, across Edge-Cloud environments. Fourthly, real-time decision-making on where to compute and to store data must be supported.

As a cognitive and decentralised orchestration framework, CODECO embraces a next generation vision where data and services are stored and computed across the Internet whole-chain, in a holistic cooperation between Cloud and far Edge [6]. Components of containerised applications, which in CODECO are addressed as *micro-services*, reside in isolated, self-sufficient containers, which can be deployed and executed in any underlying environment. A flexible and secure networking infrastructure provides adaptable interconnection that adapt to the needs and the surrounding environment of the services being run.

Relevant in CODECO is an adaptation based on application requirements and user requirements. A functional representation of CODECO and its open-source components is provided in Figure 3. Based on this functional level, CODECO offers the following aspects:

- **Automated configuration**, focusing on supporting application setup and application runtime across Edge-Cloud, by taking into consideration compute, network, and data aspects. The key aspects of this contribution are supported by the CODECO *Advanced Configuration and Management (ACM)* component.
- **Data as a resource**. CODECO addresses, via its *Metadata Manager (MDM)* component data as a resource in the sense that available snapshots from the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure, integrating different perspectives (application, user, system, data, network) at different instants of the CODECO operational workflow can be provided to different CODECO components, to assist in detecting relevant changes.
- **Dynamic scheduling and workload migration**. Supported by the CODECO component *Scheduling and Workload Migration (SWM)*, CODECO brings in novel QoS models that consider data-network-compute requirements to provide a best match between applications and available infrastructure (nodes, their computational and data properties, as well as network nodes and links), and to schedule and re-schedule application workloads across single cluster and federated cluster environments, considering application and user requirements.
- **Context-awareness and privacy preserving decentralised learning**. CODECO relies on context-awareness to be able to achieve a joint data-network-compute orchestration, and on privacy-preserving decentralised learning and inference to best support readjustment of aspects such as the processing capability, computational resources, networking resources and interconnections in real-time. Context-awareness and decentralised learning are part of the CODECO *Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning (PDLC)* component.
- **Infrastructure adaptation based on a cross-layer data-compute-network approach**. Via the CODECO *Network Management and Adaptation component (NetMA)*, CODECO assists in adapting not just computational (node resources) but also the networking infrastructure interconnecting such nodes, having as starting point for the exposure of metadata within 1 cluster and across federated clusters, from far Edge to Cloud.

Figure 3: Functional representation of the CODECO K8s framework and its components.

The only interface of CODECO to the user, as shown in Figure 3, is the ACM component, which focuses on supporting application setup and runtime from the far Edge to the Cloud, considering the input provided by the user.

The user in CODECO is perceived as an **application developer (DEV)** or as a **cluster manager (MGT)**.

To setup CODECO, a user relies on the CODECO framework. ACM installs the entire CODECO framework, handling the overall CODECO configuration. The user can specify, via the CODECO **Application Model (CAM)**, the requirements of the application and of its micro-services. These requirements are relevant to allow CODECO to deploy the application across CEI in an efficient way.

Via CAM, the user specifies also **target performance profiles** that is used in CODECO (PDLC) to meet a specific level of **greenness**, or **resilience** during its operation.

Once CODECO is installed, all CODECO components can be used. The CODECO components have been devised to allow each component to work independently, with other future open orchestration frameworks, requiring little adaptation.

The **CODECO MDM** component provides data and system observability to the other CODECO components, treating data as an integral part of the application workload, and integrating observability perspectives from different categories, e.g., application perspective, system perspective, network perspective, at different points in the CODECO operational workflow.

SWM handles the scheduling and rescheduling of the application workload, based on the *CODECO Application Model (CAM)*. CAM is supported by ACM and provided by the user during application setup, based on the novel data-compute-network approach proposed by CODECO.

The currently available approach in SWM for handling placement decisions relies on a graph-based optimization approach which in contrast to the K8s filtering and score approach is

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expected to provide an optimal match between application requirements and available resources (computational, network, data). SWM is also a control plane component, co-located with ACM and the K8s control plane, in master nodes.

PDLC is at the heart of the CODECO orchestration. Based on the infrastructure data collected by ACM (via Prometheus), NetMA, and MDM, PDLC has two functions. Firstly, it provides an aggregated cost view of a specific target performance profile for the available infrastructure which can be used by other components and is currently being considered in SWM to further define the optimal workload placement. Secondly, it provides an estimate on the overall system stability based on privacy-preserving decentralised learning approaches. PDLC is currently envisaged to operate on both K8s master and worker nodes.

NetMA provides the network awareness to CODECO and handles also secure connectivity across pods. Network awareness is provided via network probing based on the sub-component Network State Management (NSM). Then, exposure of network metrics (across multi-cluster environments) is based on the ALTO protocol [8]. NetMA provides in addition **secure connectivity** via **L2S-M**⁸. Hence, NetMA is a component responsible for interconnecting the *Software-defined Networking (SDN)* world with K8s.

To be able to achieve a flexible orchestration, CODECO counts with monitoring across the three different CEI infrastructure perspectives. NetMA monitors the networking infrastructure; MDM monitors the data infrastructure; ACM monitors the system (computational nodes) infrastructure based on the K8s metrics server Prometheus^{9,10}. This approach allows to explore the integration of new metrics as well as of providing the collected metrics of CODECO to future orchestration frameworks.

The CODECO framework is deployed as an application: each CODECO component is based on a modular approach, integrating different sub-components that are expected to be built as one or more independent (dockerized) micro-services.

2.3 CODECO to CEI Continuum Mapping

As an orchestration framework, CODECO can operate at the Edge, Edge to Edge, Edge to Cloud, including far Edge to Cloud. The operation of CODECO relates with the management of an Edge-Cloud infrastructure which is based on the abstraction principles of K8s.

CODECO as a framework pluggable to K8s is being developed to be able to provide a flexible K8s operation considering mobile heterogeneous environments, and a reach to the far Edge. CODECO is being developed in a way that allows it to operate in a single cluster or multiple clusters, across multi-tenant environments.

A cluster in this case is an abstraction from the K8s concept (rf. to section 2.1) which can be mapped solely to an Edge environment (including a far Edge environment), Edge-to-Edge, or Edge-to-Cloud. The principles of CODECO provide the capability to support Edge-to-Edge orchestration. The cluster abstraction concept always integrates a control plane (K8s master node, rf. to section 2.1) and a service plane (K8s worker nodes). From an Edge-Cloud continuum perspective, a cluster is expected to integrate at least one Edge node. A representation on this potential mapping for single cluster operation is illustrated in Figure 4.

⁸ <http://l2sm.io>

⁹ <https://prometheus.io/>

¹⁰ The current version of CODECO considers Prometheus as basis for the metrics gathering and analysis. However, for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments the consortium is also considering Thanos due to the higher availability, and extended storage capabilities.

Cluster 1 provides an initial example for a centralised mapping, where the control plane of CODECO (and of K8s) resides in the Cloud, while K8s worker nodes being monitored and managed in CODECO are located in the far and near Edge [1]. As illustrated, CODECO components such as ACM and SWM (control plane of CODECO) would then reside on the Cloud, co-located with the K8s control plane. Sub-components of MDM, PDLC, and NetMA, in particular the sub-components related with resource monitoring, would be located on the K8s worker nodes (far and near Edge in this example). While this representation places the CODECO control plane in the Cloud, it should be highlighted that it could also run in the near Edge or far Edge, as represented in **Cluster 2** for the near Edge. In this example, worker nodes are also running MDM, NetMA due to monitoring, and PDLC (learning at the Edge). **Cluster 3** provides a representation of the mapping of CODECO to the far Edge. CODECO can run on a single node or as represented, run on multiple nodes. The example here provided shows that in K8s worker nodes, NetMA is the only component active (network monitoring), while the other components are set to run co-located with the K8s control plane. MDM is not represented, to highlight that some components in CODECO are also optional. For instance, a user MGT may want to optimize the infrastructure just in terms of computational and networking resources, and hence, it is not required to run MDM.

Figure 4: CODECO and relation to the CEI continuum, single cluster representation.

Figure 5 provides a high-level representation of the CEI mapping of CODECO for multi-cluster environments. In this case, a cluster may be located at a single region (far Edge, near Edge) or span different areas (e.g. far Edge and Cloud; far Edge and near Edge; far Edge-near Edge-Cloud). Multi-cluster operation handled by CODECO takes into consideration different clusters as in K8s (independently of location) but brings to K8s CEI awareness in the sense that it **takes into the placement process data, network and computational awareness**. This allows CODECO to best adapt to, for instance, far Edge environments, where devices may be constrained in terms of computational resources and networking resources. It allows

CODECO also to react assuming that the suitable nodes running the application actually do have the expected resources, but an abnormal pattern was detected with the data workflow (e.g., stale database) and with the networking resources (e.g., temporarily congested link).

Figure 5: CODECO examples for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments across the CEI continuum.

2.4 Technological Enablers

This section summarizes the key technological enablers being addressed in CODECO, and the reasons for their application, as stated in Table 1.

Table 1: CODECO Technological enablers.

Name	Description	Where it is applied
Decentralised AI (RL, MARL)	CODECO shall analyse the role of distributed and split learning approaches; swarm learning; and adaptation of Machine Learning (ML) models to best serve next generation services needs and constraints	PDLC expects to validate and rely on decentralised/hybrid federated AI to support the operation of CODECO across federated, multi-tenant environments. Estimations are relevant to SWM (scheduler) and to NetMA (network adaptation).
Edge computing	CODECO overall orchestration approach is based on the architectural principles of Edge and Fog computing	The overall flexible orchestration of containerised applications reflects the computational abstraction principles of Edge computing.
Cross-layer orchestration	On the one hand, the networking infrastructure needs to become more flexible, intent and context-driven, i.e., the network should be seen and worked upon as being a single system. On the other hand, joint computational and networking paradigms, that integrate, by design, aspects such as security/trustworthiness, mobility	Several CODECO elements monitor the infrastructure (MDM – data; NetMA – network; ACM – compute). ACM provides a cross-layer view on collected metrics to the whole CODECO system. PDLC relies on such metrics to predict infrastructure behaviour. SWM relies on this estimation to weight the decisions of rescheduling applications across Edge-Cloud.

Name	Description	Where it is applied
	support, decentralised and flexible naming spaces are key to build a smart, decentralised Edge ecosystem.	
Security and privacy	Privacy and security automation are aspects also addressed in the automation layer of CODECO.	ACM provides privacy and security based on user requirements; PDLC relies on privacy by design in the proposed AI-based orchestration; NetMA provides secure channels between application micro-services via the L2S-M secure connectivity approach
Cross-layer context-awareness	Context-awareness and behaviour inference shall be considered to integrate into the management of containers aspects such as device usage, application requirements, prediction of mobility patterns, desired levels of privacy and security, to best assist the deployment of applications and services, and to provide a more dynamic network control management.	PDLC relies on context-awareness to provide a tuning of the overall Edge-Cloud environment based on target performance profiles provided by the user, e.g., optimize the overall CEI infrastructure for greenness.
Network Probing	CODECO extends the notions of CEI infrastructure to integrate network probing	NetMA provides network metrics which are used by PDLC and also SWM.
Network management	Dynamic connectivity established among workloads within a cluster or among clusters, providing isolation.	NetMA enables flexible and dynamic instantiation of connectivity between pods by means of overlay paths supported by the underlay network physically interconnecting the Edge-Cloud continuum.
FaaS	The locality aspects inherent to Edge computing require an adequate abstraction approach to support operations across Edge-Cloud in a smooth way. Such abstraction is being advocated by the Cloud model of <i>Function-as-a-service (FaaS)</i> .	Moreover, the notion of function and function chaining provides an abstraction approach that is strong enough to address joint orchestration of computational and networking resources, a key aspect in Cloud-Edge environments. However, the higher degree of decentralisation in Edge environments creates challenges to FaaS. For instance, function chaining brings additional overhead; balancing the performance and isolation provided by sandbox environments; integrating additional requirements, e.g., data locality, network requirements, application requirements are still aspects to be handled in NetMA, in particular considering the operation of CODECO in federated clusters.
Semantic service composition	CODECO internal and external interfaces consider notions of semantic service composition and aggregation. The cross-layer approach of CODECO relies on	In CODECO, existing semantic service composition principles of K8s are extended to allow for a notion of application (CODECO Application Model) without jeopardizing the application security and privacy. The user provides application requirements to the system

Name	Description	Where it is applied
	semantic service composition principles, present also in K8s.	based on a proposed semantic abstraction.
Configuration management	Automated configuration management concerns the installation, configuration and management of multiple distributed and heterogeneous clusters, as well as the mechanisms to deploy and manage applications on top of them.	ACM provides a single point of entry to the CODECO users and reduces the need for human intervention.

2.5 CODECO Context-awareness Aspects

In current container orchestration solutions, the need to replicate resources is usually based on system requirements (e.g., CPU usage of a node reaches a specific level, or energy level is perceived as high); application requirements (e.g., bounded latency); network policies. To further support dynamic Edge-Cloud environments, container orchestration needs to integrate context-awareness into the offloading process. *Context-awareness* refers to the capability of a system to consider knowledge about its environment, to perform specific actions. In this context, a system can be a computational system; a cyber-physical system; a set of cyber-physical systems [10][11]. Usually, context falls into a wide range of categories such as computing context (e.g., available processors, memory, nearby resources); user context (e.g., location, user profiles, nearby users); environmental context (e.g., lighting, temperature).

A first step towards achieving **context-aware orchestration** is the definition of a basic set of context-awareness parameter categories to consider in the offloading process, how to model context, and how such modelling can be integrated.

In CODECO, the initial proposal derives from prior analysis by partner FOR [5] is to consider the following categories of context-aware metrics as illustrated in Figure 6 and specific examples of attributes are provided in Annex I:

- **Computational metrics** refer to internal parameters of a system and are usually available already to K8s. Examples are CPU, memory, as in K8s. These are currently provided by ACM via Prometheus.
- **Network metrics** relate to both functional QoS requirements (e.g., RTT, latency, allocated bandwidth between worker nodes and the master node); and to non-functional QoS/QoE requirements (e.g., mobility, portability). These are in CODECO provided by NetMA.
- **Application metrics** relate with application QoS parameters. For instance, In the context of Industrial IoT critical applications often require minimum and bounded latency within one msec. Tight time synchronization among devices serving a specific application is often a challenge, due to time-aware queuing disciplines that support the exchange of critical traffic. Non-functional requirements, such as a sensitiveness level of an application, or even certification or compliance aspects, may prevent an application to run under specific conditions on a node. These are provided by ACM, via CAM.
- **Data observability metrics** relate with dataset characteristics, e.g., freshness of the data, compliance verification towards a specific location. These are provided by MDM.
- **User behaviour metrics** relate with the user behaviour as a carrier/controller of applications in the far Edge. A common indicator of user behaviour is user location, which is widely applied. Other forms of user behaviour, including user preferences, have been considered, e.g., social interaction, group formation, and social/physical proximity to improve overall system performance and to provide better support for task offloading

across the Edge [12][13]. These metrics are currently not provided in CODECO but expected to be relevant in the context of use cases. These metrics will be made available by Prometheus, via deployment in the CODECO use-cases.

Figure 6: Examples of context-awareness categories and metrics in CODECO.

As shall be explained in section 3, several CODECO components collect metrics:

- **Application and user behaviour/preferences - ACM.** This data is obtained during setup of an application deployment via the CODECO Application Model, which is being designed to capture functional and non-functional requirements from user DEV. The definition of this (or multiple) application-level model is a task of the CA in PDLC; initial metrics being considered are provided in Annex I. ACM would handle the transformation into a K8s declarative object configuration file.
- **Data/System observability – MDM.** MDM can tag events that relate with data and systems observability, e.g., if a dataset is not updated within a specified time, or if a dataset grows to exceed a specified size, a trigger to be generated to schedule application to handle the condition.
- **Network parameters – NetMA.** Via ALTO, NetMA is expected to collect relevant network parameters that assist in a better definition of the infrastructure, beyond the usual view of resources provided in K8s. The starting parameters are in Annex I. Additional categories of network data may rely among others, with security aspects, resilience aspects.

3 Low-level Architectural Specification

The overall CODECO architecture is illustrated in Figure 7 considering as starting point the CODECO operation within a single cluster deployment (M1-M18 of CODECO) and addressing design considerations to be taken into consideration during the second part of the project (WP4, M19-M36).

The low-level design of the CODECO architecture in this section starts with a list of assumptions and requirements (rf. to subsection 3.1) that are driving the design of CODECO. Then, the section continues with operational examples to guide the reader in the CODECO operational workflow for a single cluster (rf. to section 3.2).

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After this, details for each CODECO component are provided (rf. to section 3.3) based on the following structure:

- **Component Design Overview:** Detailed descriptions of each component or module of the system, including its purpose, functionality, interfaces, and dependencies.
- **Key technologies** being used as basis for the development of the component.
- **CODECO Metrics (if applicable)** being considered.
- **Low-level description of sub-components, and interfaces** (e.g., class diagram).
- **Interfaces.**
- **Single cluster operation description and sequence diagrams.**
- **FC operation starting points**, design to be considered and improved during the second phase of the development of CODECO (M19-M36).
- **List of To-Do features**, to be handled in the next phase of the project.

Figure 7: The CODECO reference architecture, single cluster operation.

3.1 Architectural Assumptions and Requirements

The design of CODECO has as basis specific the technical architectural significant requirements as listed in *Table 3*. These requirements are relevant to assist the modelling of CODECO as a flexible framework for the current use-cases, and for future ones. The list of requirements is expected to increase during the second phase of deployment of the project (M19-M36) due to the more complex multi-cluster, multi-tenant operation.

For the description of the requirements, this deliverable follows following the IETF principles: The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in IETF RFC 2119 [9].

Table 2: List of CODECO architectural assumptions.

Name	Description
A1	The user MUST have a running K8s cluster with at least one master node and two worker nodes.
A2	The master node in the cluster MUST at least have a connection to one worker node.
A3	Prometheus MUST be active in the selected cluster.
A4	The user MUST provide an initial description of the application, based on the CODECO Application Model
A5	Intermittent connectivity may be experienced in the K8s infrastructure e.g., due to mobility or constrained node energy.

Table 3: List of CODECO architectural requirements.

Name	Description
R1	CODECO interfaces SHOULD be based on CRDs.
R2	QoS networking models in CODECO are RECOMMENDED to follow an existing model, e.g., DiffServ
R3	In CODECO, concerning data, the strict rules, and regulations for data due to GDPR MUST be considered.
R4	To run applications, users MUST adapt the CAM to the specific selected application.
R5	It is RECOMMENDED to use the proposed scheduler, SWM.
R6	Connections between micro-services MUST be secure.
R7	CODECO components MUST be built in a modular way, based on containerized micro-services.
R8	The CODECO framework MUST be easily deployed in single and federated clusters.
R9	CODECO MUST be prepared to use heterogeneous networking technologies, e.g., Ethernet, Wi-Fi.
R10	CODECO MUST be user-friendly.
R11	CODECO MUST provide users with the adequate expectations and with feedback on the infrastructure being managed.
R12	CODECO MUST support efficient replication.
R13	CODECO SHOULD support efficient migration.
R14	CODECO MUST be resilient to malicious attacks
R15	CODECO MUST be energy-efficient by design.
R16	The CODECO framework SHOULD be flexible enough to allow for the use of other OSS schedulers

3.2 Operational Workflow Examples

To best guide the reader in the architectural design choices described next this sub-section provides a component-based description on the operation of CODECO for a single cluster.

3.2.1 Deploying an Application across the CEI

DEV is a user deploying an application consisting of multiple micro-services (multiple Docker images) across the far Edge to the Cloud. DEV downloads CODECO from the CODECO Eclipse GitLab¹¹ and follows the instructions to set up CODECO. For developers, it is recommended to check the CODECO deliverable D12, as this report is the companion document for the CODECO existing code.

As explained in section 2.2, the entry point for the CODECO user is the component ACM. ACM performs cluster sizing based on the *CODECO Application Model* (CAM) which is currently provided as a YAML file¹². provided to user DEV during application deployment setup. In this file, user DEV defines aspects such as desired *Quality of Service (QoS)*, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*, or other desired performance levels for CODECO, based on the syntax provided in CAM. The current attributes considered in the CODECO Application Model are provided in Annex I.

ACM also handles the complete K8s setup (e.g., namespace, databases, secrets) and makes the information available to other K8s components as needed. For example, metadata information, schema, can be passed to MDM (rf. to section 3.1.2). Computational application requirements such as CPU, or networking requirements such as bounded latency, are provided by user DEV via CAM and made available to SWM (rf. to Figure 2 I-ACM-SWM-1) and to PDLC (rf. to Figure 2 I-ACM-PDLC-1), for instance.

The exposure of requirements and application/user information also triggers the operation of each CODECO component. PDLC defines the processes for collecting available data (application requirements from CAM; network status from NetMA; computational status from Prometheus via ACM) and bringing cross-layer context-aware costs to the infrastructure; PDLC handles also learning to assist in a stable infrastructure. Specifically, based on existing CODECO metrics collected and aggregated, PDLC generates a set of recommendations to improve the application assignment and passes such recommendations to SWM as node costs to be considered for scheduling optimisation (I-PDLC-SWM-1). NetMA triggers the definition of the network overlay when it receives the initial deployment from SWM (I-SWM-NET-1).

In parallel, three components start monitoring different metrics. NetMA captures network metrics at link and path level and exposes this information via specific CRs that are accessible to all components and used by PDLC and ACM.

Similarly, MDM captures data aspects (e.g., data compliance), generates a knowledge graph which can be queried via specific connectors developed to allow MDM to be fully integrated with CODECO and with different information sources.

ACM captures user preferences and eventually behaviour, which may be useful for adapting the overall K8s infrastructure at a later stage.

¹¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

¹² The CAM is expected to be made available to the user as a Web-based dashboard in the second phase of the project.

3.2.2 Orchestration During Application Runtime

Once the setup is complete, CODECO enters the cluster management phase (application runtime support), targeting the user MGR. During this phase, the proposed application (CODECO application workload) has been set up and is running on several containers (1 cluster), 1 or more pods per worker node. PDLC periodically receives data from MDM (I-MDM-PDLC-1); from NetMA and ACM (I-ACM-PDLC-1) and feedback from SWM regarding the placement of the application workload (I-SWM-PDLC-1). Based on this, PDLC periodically evaluates the proposed system performance targets (e.g., greenness, service latency) provided by Bob during application setup, and provides a cost combination per infrastructure element via a CR (I-PDLC-ACM-2). If there is a need for cross-layer redistribution of the application workload, this step triggers a request from ACM to all CODECO components. In this case, PDLC passes a behaviour estimate to SWM (I-PDLC-SWM-2) via a specific CR; SWM starts the workload placement process. Once the process is complete, SWM passes feedback to PDLC (I-SWM-PDLC-1). This will not be an explicit interface; instead, feedback will be provided via specific SWM CRs (currently ApplicationGroup, Application, AssignmentPlan).

ACM handles the status to the user MGR, based on the Prometheus CODECO monitoring architecture.

3.3 Components

3.3.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management

3.3.1.1 Component Design Overview

ACM provides methodologies and tools that support the CODECO automatic configuration, regarding application setup and deployment across Edge-Cloud, for single and multi-cluster environments. ACM is based on the *Open Cluster Management (OCM)*¹³ community driven project which is the upstream project for Red Hat *Advanced Cluster Management*¹⁴.

The CODECO ACM component contemplates the CODECO integration into embedded and small footprint nodes; the development of K8s operators (and if required, additional semantic interfaces) that extend the ACM operation towards the other CODECO components; automated configuration and user interfacing, to support operations across multi-cluster (federated clusters) in a way that is transparent to the user; autoscaling. Furthermore, ACM addresses security focusing on attack mitigation and detection across multi-cluster (distributed environments).

For this purpose, CODECO ACM operation considers three main categories of aspects that address the integration of CODECO across the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure:

- **Integration points between users and applications.** Mechanisms for users (e.g., user DEV) to control and change configuration of the applications to be run across the CEI continuum.
- **CODECO configuration.** A specific user request during application deployment setup or application runtime implies activation and eventual configuration of CODECO components, e.g., NetMA, PDLC. This can be done, for instance, by enhancing the K8s API with CRDs and adding operators to monitor the changes in the CRs, reacting accordingly.

¹³ <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

¹⁴ <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/management/advanced-cluster-management>

- Cluster/federated cluster configuration.** The user in this case is a user MGT, handling the K8s infrastructure. A specific change to the CODECO configuration (for instance, increase or decrease in the application workload due to dataset changes) may imply the need to install, configure (for example, policy configuration, CODECO components deployments), or reconfigure a cluster.

Figure 8 shows the different interaction points between ACM and the other CODECO components. Since ACM is the integration point towards the user, it is also in charge of the system installation - the user can install the CODECO framework by installing the CODECO meta-operator (which is part of ACM), where this process triggers the installation of the entire CODECO system on the cluster to be managed and configured. In addition, there may be the explicit need to export more information from the CODECO system to the cluster control plane and towards the users. This task also falls under the ACM umbrella.

At the bottom (yellow colour) is the CODECO interface, and at the top (blue colour) the various K8s functionalities that are hidden from the CODECO user. These functionalities are, however, available for CODECO platform developers. Since the CODECO meta-operator is the only operator exposed towards the users, it is therefore in charge of the entire CODECO system installation, including the installation of all its components and their operators (MDM, PDLC, SWM and NetMA).

Figure 8: ACM interaction points to CODECO components and external systems and users.

3.3.1.2 Key Technologies

The following list contains the technologies that has been used for the first phase (single cluster deployment of CODECO) as part of WP3 (up to M18):

- **K8s API extensions** via CRD/CRs and respective operators.
- **Prometheus**¹⁵ and exporters such as the *Kubernetes-based Efficient Power Level Exporter*, *Kepler*¹⁶, as well as new Prometheus operators to support new monitoring plugins provided in the different CODECO components, supporting the integration of new metrics in K8s.

The second phase of CODECO (federated cluster deployment) provides additional challenges to the management plane of the platform (part of ACM) and the following list of technologies is expected to be used as part of WP4 (M19-M36):

- **Multi-cluster/federation management based on OCM** (to be developed during the second phase of CODECO, M19-M36).
- **Knative**¹⁷ to support serverless deployment of containerised applications across Edge-Cloud.
- **Lightweight K8s distribution solutions** such as K3s¹⁸, Microshift¹⁹, for far Edge integration.
- **Integration with non-K8s far Edge nodes** based on solutions such as Flotta²⁰.
- **Secure onboarding of devices**, considering *Fast Identity Online (FIDO)* and *Trusted Execution Environments (TEE)* approaches.
- **Fast provisioning of K8s clusters** on remote worker nodes via solutions such as Hypershift²¹.
- **Ansible**²², to support the automated deployment of CODECO.
- **Thanos**²³ to extend the monitoring framework and facilitate a highly available Prometheus setup with a global query view and the possibility for long term storage.

3.3.1.3 ACM CODECO Metrics

ACM is responsible for bringing computational metrics to CODECO. The minimum subset of CODECO computational metrics currently being considered are provided in Annex I, Table 16. These metrics are provided via CAM.

3.3.1.4 Low-Level Description of ACM Sub-components

ACM uses existing open-source technologies and will need to extend some of these technologies to support CODECO components and APIs. It is envisioned that ACM will rely on the initially proposed technologies as detailed in the previous subsection.

15 <https://prometheus.io/>

16 <https://sustainable-computing.io/>

17 <https://knative.dev>

18 <https://k3s.io/>

19 <https://github.com/openshift/microshift>

20 <https://project-flotta.io/>

21 <https://github.com/openshift/hypershift>

22 <https://www.ansible.com/>

23 <https://thanos.io/>

Figure 9: ACM, sub-components and interfaces.

The ACM initial sub-components, represented in Figure 9 are:

- **OCM:** This sub-component is the basis for ACM and is used to enable end-to-end visibility and control across K8s clusters. It will be used to provide the main ACM functionality and extended to provide special support and visibility of the CODECO components.
- **K8s API extensibility and CRD/CRs.** This is a mechanism that is provided by K8s to extend its functionality and provide native access to new components. It provides native K8s APIs to the CODECO framework thus making the interaction with the CODECO components seamless and making the CODECO framework K8s native.

Monitoring: new metrics integrated into Prometheus. Different CODECO components (ACM, NetMA, MDM) collect parameters that shall assist in a more flexible schedule, with compute, network, and data awareness. The CODECO components collecting input monitor specific parameters and provide these in CRD/CRs. Furthermore, PDLC (via its sub-component PDLC-CA) derives aggregated costs for nodes based on the collected CODECO cross-layer metrics. These aggregated node costs relate with target performance profiles that the user DEV selects during application deployment, e.g., resilience, or greenness. Additionally, use-cases may also have a need to consider additional application metrics (to be provided to Prometheus), which future versions of CODECO can use. In ACM, a Monitoring component articulates the overall monitoring provided by all components, currently proposing an integration into Prometheus and, for the second phase also with Thanos. The new CODECO CRDs can be extended to, among other functionalities, specify how groups of K8s services or pods should be monitored or to specify scrape configurations to be added to Prometheus. Built in K8s metrics can also be enhanced by gathering more information with the use of node exporters or eBPF hooks, like Kepler that relies on eBPF to probe energy-related system stats and exports them as Prometheus metrics. The proposed CODECO sub-component monitoring architecture is illustrated in Figure 10.
- **Automated configuration via Knative and Ansible.** Knative will be used when scalable stateless functions are required, so that ACM can easily scale-out and scale-in upon load change. This is usually a requirement for many stream processing and event-driven functions. Ansible shall be used to support the automation of cluster configuration and CODECO deployment tasks in ACM.
- **Control plane for independent/isolated clusters** – There are multiple open-source technologies that handle this problem (for example, KCP²⁴) and it is yet to be decided which technology to use for this problem. Here, the aim is to consider mobile environments where intermittent connectivity may prevent the registration of a cluster to

²⁴<https://github.com/kcp-dev/kcp#-kcp>

the OCM Hub. An example relates with the use of clusters involving mobile devices, such as cars (rf. to deliverable D8 use-cases. P2), or *Automated Guided Vehicles* (rf. To D8 use-cases, P5).

- **Far Edge integration**, via lightweight K8s distributions. CODECO addresses the support of clusters involving embedded devices at the far Edge, potentially mobile. Hence, ACM considers the integration and interoperability to handle lightweight support via solutions such as K3s, Microshift.
- **Integration towards non-K8s systems**. ACM supports connectivity towards non-k8s nodes via Flotta, to provide the connection of containerised workload to other K8s clusters.
- **Secure deployment**. The secure onboarding of new cyber-physical systems at the Edge is handled via ACM, based on tools such as FIDO and TEE.
- **Hierarchical control plane**. Via Hypershift, ACM supports a separation of the control plane into a centralised cluster (Cloud or Edge) and considering that remote worker nodes are being deployed at the Edge.

Figure 10: Monitoring architecture in CODECO [37].

3.3.1.4.1 CODECO Automated and Secure Deployment

ACM provides the full installation of the CODECO framework via a single operator (ACM). Such deployment is currently based on CLI but shall be deployed on *Operator Lifecycle Management (OLM)* technology.

3.3.1.4.2 CODECO User API and CAM

The user API corresponds to the entry point of CODECO. The API relies on CAM, for which a representation is provided in Figure 11 and for which an example is provided in Annex II. The figure represents different specifications for applications, services, and channels, while it also outlines the metrics for assessing the status and performance of these entities. The structure supports the aggregation of metrics at multiple levels, ensuring detailed insight into the operational aspects of the system.

The API does not require extra privileges for managing the cluster and is used for deploying a single application composed of multiple micro-services as a single entity. CAM is an extension to the K8s pod-based model designed to manage and monitor distributed, multi-pod

applications as a whole, emphasizing both specification and status aspects. Each application can consist of multiple services (micro-services in CODECO), defined by the *ServiceSpec* class, detailing resource usage at a computational (CPU, memory), network (latency, bandwidth, energy spent during transmission), and data (freshness, age of information) level.

Each micro-service is implemented as a pod. Communication between micro-services is facilitated by the Channel and *AdvancedChannelSettings* classes, which outline the communication pathways and additional channel configurations. The *podSpec* class links services to K8s pod specifications, ensuring deployment consistency. On the status side, the *AppStatus* class aggregates runtime metrics, captured in the *AppStatusMetrics* class, e.g., pod count, memory and CPU usage, network load, and associated costs. The model also includes *NodeStatusMetrics* to monitor node-specific performance and reliability, and *ServiceStatusMetrics* to track service-level metrics on nodes. This structure allows for detailed, hierarchical monitoring and management of applications, ensuring efficient resource utilisation, performance tracking, and compliance adherence across distributed systems.

Figure 11: Logical representation of the CODECO Application Model.

An example for CAM (which is exposed as a CRD) is provided in Figure 53, for a minimal application. CAM is parsed by the ACM operator, and its information (application requirements; infrastructure status) is propagated to the other CODECO components and to K8s as required.

3.3.1.4.3 Monitoring Framework

The monitoring in CODECO is based on Prometheus as the de facto K8s metrics server. Most of the monitoring work is done by direct integration of the CODECO components with Prometheus. In addition to this, ACM provides some additional functionality for Monitoring tasks:

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- **Slow-paced metrics**, such as an averaged metric over a time window of one or five minutes, relevant to the user, are populated in the ***status*** part of the CRD (rf. to Figure 12). As a result, the ACM operator runs on a timely manner (once a minute) and not only when an application resource is changed (as is the default behaviour for K8s operators).
- **A mechanism for no code addition of Prometheus rules was added** (a central place for managing and deploying Prometheus Rules) so that the components can export their rules and make them visible to the other components in a managed and centralised process. This mechanism can export non-trivial metrics (one that requires a query) by the metric owner to the metric users.

```
status:
  appMetrics:
    avgAppCpu: "2"
    avgAppMemory: 8Gi
    numPods: 2
    serviceMetrics:
      avgServiceCpu: "100"
      avgServiceMemory: 2Gi
      podName: acm-swm-app-front-end
      clusterName:
      nodeName: c1
      serviceName: front-end
      avgServiceCpu: "100"
      avgServiceMemory: 2Gi
      nodeName: c1
      podName: acm-swm-app-backend
      clusterName:
      serviceName: backend
  errorMsg: No errors
  nodeMetrics:
    avgNodeCpu: "2"
    avgNodeEnergy: "2"
    avgNodeFailure: "0"
    avgNodeMemory: 10Gi
    nodeName: c1
    avgNodeCpu: "2"
    avgNodeEnergy: "2"
    avgNodeFailure: "0"
    avgNodeMemory: 10Gi
    nodeName: c2
status: OK
```

Figure 12: CAM, status part example.

3.3.1.5 Interfaces

ACM is the single-entry point in CODECO to the users, thus interacting directly with K8s and non-K8s systems. The current interfaces of ACM to other components are summarized in Table 4. The full set of interfaces between ACM and the other CODECO components are based on the extensibility of K8s APIs and will be defined when the exact integration points are finalized.

Table 4: ACM interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-PROM	Integration of the CODECO metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-MDM-1	Data collection from CRDs of other components, to be used in the MDM integration of the CODECO MDM operator.	CRD	Bi-directional
I-ACM-PDLC-1	Integration of CA derived metrics into Prometheus	CRD	Input
I-ACM-PDLC-2	Use of CRDs from other components by PDLC	CRD	Output
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA CRD/CR(s) and respective operator(s)	CRD	Input
I-ACM-SWM-1	Integration of the SWM controller-manager (CRD/CR(s) via K8s API)	CR via K8s API (REST)	Bi-directional

3.3.1.6 Single Cluster Operation

As has been explained, ACM relies on OCM (the upstream version of the RHT project ACM), which provides benefits for federated clusters. In a single cluster, the ACM operation is simplified. A user DEV starts by, in an active cluster, to install the ACM operator (which handles the setup and installation of all the CODECO framework).

The user then needs to specific the application to deploy based on the CAM specification. This currently requires manual adaptation. However, during the second phase of CODECO, the user shall be provided with a dashboard and enter in a friendly-user way the different application requirements. The user may enter requirements at a computational, network, and data level for the overall application and its micro-services.

3.3.1.7 Federated Clusters' Operation

The adaptation of ACM to a federated clusters should be straightforward from a logic perspective, given that ACM is based on OCM. Key challenges to be addressed are as follows:

- CAM adaptation to multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments.
- The automated bootstrapping of authentication for worker nodes; the encryption of control messages exchanged to set the overlay aspects.
- Monitoring architecture adapted to multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments.

Concerning **CAM**, the current model will have to be tested and validated, potentially being modified to a multi-cluster environment. Specifically, the CAM model needs to consider some cluster-level awareness. **An approach** is to integrate into the CAM an additional level for clusters:

- At level 1 a graph is considered, where a definition of a cluster service level is provided.
- Level 2 would be the current application definition.
- Level 3 would be the application micro-services.

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This approach assumes that the user DEV has in fact an idea of the cluster deployment to be handled. It is therefore a static approach which may create blockers to the flexibility in CODECO.

A second approach may be to consider a flag which allows, per micro-service, the definition on whether or not the application micro-services need to run on the same cluster (or same node) or not.

Another aspect relevant to be addressed is the CODECO **monitoring architecture** which may best serve multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments. Figure 13 illustrates how it is initially expected that the monitoring architecture is distributed over a federated clusters' environment handled with CODECO, assuming ACM would consider a centralised control plane deployment.

Thanos²⁵ would be deployed in the OCM Hub cluster and an instance of Prometheus running in Agent mode²⁶ would be deployed in each of the remaining clusters (Spoke clusters). The Prometheus Agent mode offers a light-weighted version of Prometheus that has querying, local storage and alerting disabled. When enabled, only discovery and scraping of metrics are available and they are sent to a central remote endpoint (Thanos) using the remote-write protocol²⁷.

Additionally, Thanos offers the possibility to store the metrics in a S3 storage system, which is accessible seamlessly by using the Thanos Querier²⁸, which implements the Prometheus HTTP v1 API to query the data via PromQL²⁹. Despite having all metrics centralised in Thanos, it would still be possible to group them by cluster with the use of Prometheus labels.

Figure 13: Monitoring Framework, initial operation aspects in federated clusters.

25 <https://thanos.io/>

26 <https://prometheus.io/blog/2021/11/16/agent/>

27 https://prometheus.io/docs/specs/remote_write_spec/

28 <https://thanos.io/v0.17/components/query.md/>

29 <https://prometheus.io/docs/prometheus/latest/querying/basics/>

3.3.1.8 ACM To-Do features

ACM To-Do features for the next version are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: ACM To-Do features.

Id	Description
ACM-TD-1	The CAM is currently provided based on a CLI approach The CAM will be provided via a Web-based dashboard.
ACM-TD-2	Integration of the monitoring framework with Thanos.
ACM-TD-3	Adaptation of CAM to a multi-cluster environment based on the initial aspects discussed in section 3.3.1.7
ACM-TD-4	Analysis of interoperability to constrained, far Edge nodes.
ACM-TD-5	Allow the user to define multiple target performance profiles, which shall be provided to PDLC (e.g., greenness, resilience).

3.3.2 MDM: Metadata Manager

3.3.2.1 Component Design Overview

The CODECO MDM component aims at supporting real-time Edge applications and in achieving a higher degree of efficiency in Cloud-Edge operations. The MDM is a new system that integrates three novel aspects: i) a semantic data catalogue including a rich set of metadata providing a complete cross-domain view of data, systems and software; ii) metadata discovery, aiming at enriching the collected metadata, including input provided by other CODECO components (via CRDs) and learnings derived from the multi-cluster operation; iii) data orchestration support, to assist CODECO in making orchestration decisions that are cognizant of data constraints (e.g., performance issues if there are frequent accesses to remote data or compliance issues that may preclude copying data).

The MDM graph information can encompass attributes and properties such as data source, semantic description, classification, identification; data structure (e.g., data type, schema); application-specific information (e.g., data analysis, curation aspects); network specific information (e.g., access latency, bandwidth). The catalogue is populated continuously, based on a pull or push model whenever new information is available. It is therefore populated via the Kubernetes API, directly via data-sources, or via the ACM (user input) through Prometheus metrics, for example. MDM keeps track of the meta-data and provides a common platform where all metadata (multi-cluster) can be shared across multiple domains.

Example entities in a K8s and CODECO setting include “pods”, “namespaces”, “worker nodes”, as well as “datastore”, “file”, etc. Relationships are also typed and connect exactly two entities. Relationships have a direction. For example, the relationship “contains” may be used to express that a namespace contains a set of pods.

MDM and its sub-components are illustrated in Figure 12. MDM collects metadata from any “native system” that has information on the data, software and systems, including data stores, Kubernetes, or any other relevant system. For this purpose, MDM relies on **connector interfaces** for each specific data type (I-MDM-E-1).

Figure 14: MDM interfaces to other components.

An MDM connector interfaces to a native data system or CRD and pushes metadata into a knowledge graph through the native (internal) MDM API. By adding new connectors or expanding the graph model, the system can be extended to collect any required metadata. MDM is event-based, relying on Apache Kafka³⁰. MDM relies on the Kafka event queue, a log of metadata events that occur for an Edge-Cloud setting managed with CODECO. Events describe changes that have happened and correspond to insert/update/delete of metadata entities and relationships.

MDM materializes (subsets of) the event queue in the knowledge graph to meet the needs of other CODECO components.

MDM is implemented by three components:

- **MDM API:** Implements the REST APIs that allow metadata to be pushed into the graph database and the graph to be queried.
- **Graph Database:** Stores the metadata graph.
- **Connectors:** They gather metadata and push it into the Graph Database using the MDM Controller APIs.

3.3.2.2 Key Technologies

The MDM metadata collection has materialized in data systems that make it convenient to manage and exploit the metadata. The key technologies used in the current MDM implementation include:

- **Apache Kafka:** Distributed event store and stream processing.
- **Apache ZooKeeper**³¹, for the overall Kafka management and coordination (e.g., configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization).
- **Python 3.9** or higher for the implementation of the APIs and the interaction with Kafka and the Graph database.
- **OpenAPI 3.0** as the standard for the REST API for both input and output

³⁰ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

³¹ <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

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- **IBM Pathfinder SDK³²**: Provides YAML-based configuration and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API
- **Kubernetes watcher API**: This allows the Kubernetes connector to receive as events all the entities created in the Kubernetes cluster, including but not limited to pods, CRDs, deployments.
- **Kubescape**: Kubescape is an open-source technology that performs a number of tests (controls) following compliance rules from well-known security and compliance frameworks. By default, the MITRE and NSA frameworks are enabled³³, which perform controls on configuration of worker nodes, K8s API, etc, and provide a level of coverage as a percentage.
- **Neo4j 4.4 or higher**.
- **Neo4j APOC**: *APOC (Awesome Procedures on Cypher)* is an add-on library for Neo4j that provides hundreds of procedures and functions adding a lot of useful functionality.
- **Cypher Graph Query language**: Cypher is a declarative graph query language that allows for expressive and efficient data querying in a property graph. It is the query language for Neo4j and the language openCypher is based on.
- **JSON Schema**: It is used to define the entities, their properties and relationships among them in a language-independent manner. The schemas are available online.

3.3.2.3 MDM CODECO Metrics

MDM is responsible for bringing data workflow level metrics to CODECO. The minimum subset of CODECO data metrics currently being considered are provided in Annex I, Table 17.

3.3.2.4 Low-level Description of Sub-components and Interfaces

The MDM sub-components, described next, are available as Helm charts running on K8s.

3.3.2.4.1 Graph Database

The Graph Database is the backend storage of the MDM component. The metadata events from all MDM connectors are consolidated here, making it possible for other components to extract insights from the distributed system from a single pane of glass. It is of course possible to request information by directly querying the database using cypher, but other than during development or exploration of the metadata the MDM component is designed to offer this functionality through the MDM API.

3.3.2.4.2 Connectors

Connectors send metadata to MDM in the form of events. Events are structured JSON documents. Users of the CODECO framework can install any connectors they develop or use the MDM APIs to provide metadata into the system to compute metrics or other information for their own purposes. Out of the box, CODECO provides three connectors that provide the metadata for certain metrics that are used by the scheduling mechanism in PDLC to decide on the placement of the CODECO application.

3.3.2.4.2.1 Kubernetes connector

Information about the Kubernetes environment managed by CODECO is essential to provide meaningful decisions as to how to schedule CODECO applications. Using as input the events obtained by watching the Kubernetes API, the Kubernetes connector provides metadata about all Kubernetes entities in the MDM graph, together with the relationships among them. The Kubernetes connector collects among other data the number of restarts of a pod, which is used as a proxy for the portability metric of that pod running in that cluster and namespace.

³² <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

³³ <https://kubescape.io/docs/frameworks-and-controls/frameworks/>

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3.3.2.4.2.2 Prometheus connector

CODECO components and use-cases may use Prometheus as a means to make certain metrics available. The MDM Prometheus connector obtains configured metrics from Prometheus to enrich entities in the metadata graph with those values. In particular, the “freshness” metric is captured such that if a CODECO application is to be scheduled according to that particular metric, making it available in CODECO’s Prometheus will make it possible for PDLC to schedule the application to optimize the “freshness” of the data being processed. The Prometheus service needs to be integrated with Kubernetes so the association between the metric and the pod producing it can be obtained and reflected in the Knowledge Graph.

3.3.2.4.2.3 Compliance connector

The level of compliance of a Kubernetes environment managed by CODECO is another metric required to schedule CODECO applications. The Compliance connector uses Kubespace to obtain a metric of compliance of the cluster and adds that information to the MDM metadata graph.

3.3.2.5 MDM API

The MDM API is based on OpenAPI REST (OAS REST API) and integrates five endpoint groups, illustrated in Figure 15:

- **Publish** which is the endpoint for connectors writing to the MDM.
- **Events** which is the endpoint to get events from MDM.
- **Graph** gets information by querying the data projection. Initially this would allow for Cypher queries to be performed on the knowledge graph. If because of the experience gained with partners the set of queries required for the CODECO operation can be defined in a closed set, they can be incorporated to this API at a later stage.
- **PDLC** is the end-point where the PDLC component can query the graph for specific metrics related to the pods in the CODECO application.
- **MDM** is the system information endpoint for getting status and resets or other system relevance functions.

All endpoints are protected and authorized usage enabled. The MDM API implements both the interface used to communicate with PDLC (I-MDM-PDLC-1) and the interface used by connectors to bring metadata into the graph database (I-MDM-E-1).

Figure 15: MDM API and its endpoints.

Figure 16 shows how the different MDM subcomponents interact with ACM, PDLC, Kubernetes and Prometheus. ACM deploys MDM by provisioning the subcomponents (Kafka, Zookeeper and Neo4j for the Graph database), as well as the controller, MDM API and the MDM connectors. ACM provides MDM with the relevant configuration using interface I-ACM-MDM-1 described in the next section.

The MDM connectors interact with the Kubernetes API and the Prometheus API to obtain relevant metadata, using the interface I-MDM-E-1 (described in the next section) provided by the MDM API to send events that populate the Graph database.

PDLC then obtains the metrics required for the CODECO application scheduling using the interface I-MDM-PDLC-1.

Figure 16: Interaction of the MDM sub-components with ACM, PDLC and external metadata sources.

3.3.2.6 MDM Interfaces

MDM provides access to different metadata categories, creating K8s infrastructure knowledge graphs that can integrate data-network-compute awareness. At the current stage of architectural development, MDM interacts with two additional CODECO components, ACM and PDLC. For MDM, the possibility to further understand relevant metadata also derives from the CODECO use-cases. Hence, the interfaces will also be designed taking into consideration data requirements from the use-cases (WP5).

Table 6: MDM interfaces.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-MDM-E-1	This interface is used by all MDM connectors to provide metadata into the Graph database. Rf. to Annex V		Input
I-MDM-PDLC-1	This interface is used by PDLC to obtain the metrics computed by MDM from the metadata gathered by the connectors.	OAS REST	Output
I-MDM-ACM-1	This interface defines the information provided by ACM to MDM	CRD (Helm)	Input

3.3.2.6.1 I-MDM-E-1

This interface is used by all MDM connectors to provide metadata into the Graph database.

POST /publish/event

Accepts in the body a JSON structured event. The event payload object could be an entity or relationship structure. An event contains the following elements:

1. The event type, either “insert” or “delete”.
2. An identifier that uniquely identifies the connector that issued the event.
3. A timestamp.
4. The payload, i.e., the metadata.

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Metadata is sent as entities and relationships. MDM imposes a basic structure on both entities and relationships to ensure that metadata can be stored as a graph. Entities must have a globally unique identifier and a type. It is the task of the connector to assign these. In addition, entities contain arbitrary numbers of attributes. The mandatory elements of a relationship are source and target entity identifier as well as a type. Relationships do not carry attributes. MDM does not define or enforce a static data model. Instead, the graph data model is defined by the structure of the entities and relationships that are inserted into MDM. MDM expects a set of rules to be followed by entities and relationships:

- Connectors assign a universally unique identifier to each entity that they insert. The UUID is deterministically computed from properties of the entity. For example, the UUID of an entity representing a Kubernetes pod is computed using the cluster ID, the namespace, and the pod name.
- Connectors “own” the entities that they insert. A connector that inserts an entity has the rights to update and remove it again.
- Connectors cannot change or delete entities that have been inserted by other connectors.
- Connectors use a consistent method for computing the entity IDs. This enables connectors to integrate the entities that they produce into the graph by creating relationships to existing entities.
- A relationship defines how an entity is related to another entity. The connector computes the relationships’ endpoint IDs using the same deterministic method that is used for computing the entity IDs.
- Connectors own the relationships that they insert. A connector has the right to remove its own relationships again. Since relationships do not have properties, they cannot be changed.
- Connectors cannot overwrite relationships that have been inserted by other connectors.

3.3.2.6.2 I-MDM-PDLC-1

This interface is used by PDLC to obtain the metrics computed by MDM from the metadata gathered by the connectors.

GET /pdlc

This endpoint gets the metrics associated with the pods required by PDLC following a CRD format. The parameters are as follows:

- *cluster*: The name of the cluster where the pod is running.
- *namespace*: The namespace where the pod is running.
- *pod*: The name of the pod.
- *rnd*: (optional) If this is set to “true”, the API provides random values for all metrics.

The result is provided in JSON as a K8s CR. The output properties are, as described in Table 17, Annex I:

- *pod_name*: The name of the pod, as provided as input
- *freshness*: How fresh the data processed by pod is (see Prometheus connector below)
- *compliance*: Level of compliance of the pod given where it’s running (see Compliance connector below)
- *portability*: A metric of how robust the execution of the pod is where it’s running (see Kubernetes connector below).

3.3.2.6.3 I-MDM-ACM-1

This interface defines the information provided by ACM to MDM. Explicitly, ACM provides MDM with the following parameters at deployment time:

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- **storageclassName:** provides the storageclass to be used for volumes in Kubernetes, such as those used to store the Graph database or the Kafka log.
- **crawler.k8s.api_url:** The URL of the Kubernetes API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.k8s.sa_token:** If the connector is not running under a sufficiently privileged service account, the token with sufficient permissions to obtain configuration information through the Kubernetes API must be provided in this parameter.
- **crawler.prometheus.server.url:** The hostname of the Prometheus query API.
- **crawler.prometheus.server.port:** The port of the Prometheus query API.
- **crawler.prometheus.metric:** The name of the metric to capture (default is *CODECO_freshness*).
- **crawler.prometheus.entity:** The name of the entity in the metadata graph to attach the metric to.
- **pathfinder.url:** The URL of the MDM API.

These parameters may be provided by cluster in a multi-cluster environment, which each set of values provided to the corresponding connector.

Implicitly, it provides the MDM Kubernetes connector with a service account with sufficient privilege to access the Kubernetes API, where the Kubernetes connector is able to gather all relevant information about pods, workers nodes, and any CRDs available.

3.3.2.7 Single Cluster Operation

MDM interfaces to ACM to collect K8s infrastructure data (I-ACM-MDM-1) required for deployment and configuration of the MDM API, Graph database and connectors. Connectors interact with other data sources (Prometheus, Kubernetes API) and send the metadata to MDM (I-MDM-E-1). The collected metadata is then stored and processed into the Graph database, to provide complete data observability in the cluster.

The MDM knowledge graph links all the collected information to create additional value since attributes like data lineage are shown explicitly and attributes like data classification can be derived. For example, assuming the appropriate connectors are running, Personal Information coming from a video feed that is processed in the cloud and stored in an S3 bucket would make in turn the contents of the S3 bucket Personal Information.

As illustrated in Figure 17 in each cluster MDM connectors interface to local components, including Kubernetes (through the K8s API) and other CODECO components such as Prometheus, and collect relevant information. If the data source has an event interface it will trigger the information update and otherwise the collector will poll the source and generate an event to MDM. The new or updated information is added to MDM's knowledge graph, and if events have been subscribed to, an event will be generated to the relevant component. Specific metrics computed from the generated knowledge graph with all associated metadata are made available through CRDs to other CODECO components (mainly PDLC) as described above. Exploration of the Knowledge Graph is always possible through the exposed Graph Query endpoint in the MDM API.

Figure 17: MDM single cluster operation.

The data requirements of the application workload can be exposed as part of its definition (CODECO Application model, cf. to section 3.3.1.3.4.2). The CODECO PDLC component integrates the information provided by MDM with the other information it collects regarding the state of applications and systems to create and evaluate models to predict their future performance. PDLC leverages the MDM knowledge graph through the MDM API to obtain the metrics described above. The scheduling in SWM can also leverage this information (derived from PDLC).

3.3.2.8 Federated Clusters' Operation

Figure 18 depicts how it is initially expected that MDM is distributed over a federated clusters' environment handled with CODECO, assuming ACM would consider a centralised control plane deployment. MDM and its API would be co-located to the ACM control plane (ACM Manager cluster), although other locations are also feasible, assuming the ACM manager cluster is a well-known entry point that can be discovered easily.

Figure 18: MDM, initial operation aspects in federated clusters.

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MDM runs connectors on dedicated namespaces on those managed clusters (preferred solution), or on the original cluster if credentials can be provided and the clusters are reachable from the outside. The connectors are deployed as for the single cluster operation by ACM using Helm charts.

If ACM deploys connectors in a single cluster, it needs to provide the URLs of the Kubernetes API and the associated Prometheus API to the connectors through the I-ACM-MDM-1 interface. If ACM deploys the connectors for each cluster on dedicated namespaces on those clusters, then it must provide the URL of the MDM API in the management cluster so that the connectors can report the relevant metadata. This is provided through the configuration of the Helm charts at deployment time, as ACM has knowledge of all the clusters in the CODECO multi-cluster and their associated Prometheus instance or instances.

The metrics provided on a single cluster deployment are provided for all clusters in the multi-cluster deployment through I-MDM-PDLC-1.

3.3.2.9 MDM To-Do Features

A summary of to-do features for MDM is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: MDM To-Do features.

Id	Description
MDM-TD-1	Analyse the interoperability of MDM for relevant CODECO use-cases - Note that it may be possible to meet the needs of multiple CODECO use-cases with a single projection, but the system is extensible, allowing multiple projections, e.g., for performance or storage efficiency reasons.
MDM-TD-2	Contribute to the definition of a global semantic model composition that can best suit multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments.

3.3.3 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness

3.3.3.1 Component Design Overview

PDLC integrates, as the name points out, 3 sub-modules: privacy preservation; decentralised learning; context-awareness, illustrated in Figure 19. The PDLC-CA is a sub-component that, based on metrics collected via other CODECO components, and/or available via K8s plugins, correlates different categories of metrics such as application requirements (ACM); user behaviour and feedback (ACM); data aspects (MDM); node (ACM) and network functional and non-functional requirements (NetMA). Its output, which concerns a set of computed weights related with the desired performance optimization (e.g., greenness level of the multi-cluster environment; QoS needs; privacy needs and privacy-preserving adaptations, sovereignty needs; soft network characteristics, e.g., network lifetime stability), is fed to the PDLC-DL sub-module and expected to be directly provided to other modules, currently to SWM and to ACM. CODECO shall explore novel, decentralised learning approaches (e.g., Swarm learning), to assist a cross-layer adaptation of data-computation-network.

Hence, PDLC corresponds to the component that handles context acquisition and modelling, and a ML-based orchestration engine, which can assist SWM in making an informed scheduling/re-scheduling decision, based on behaviour prediction. This is achieved via three main subcomponents of PDLC, as represented in Figure 19:

- **Data Preprocessing (PDLC-DP):** the subcomponent that acts as an input interface of PDLC with all other CODECO components. Responsible for obtaining all necessary data

and performing the needed pre-processing operations (cleaning, normalization, etc.) for the data to be ready for use by the other subcomponents.

- **Context-Awareness (PDLC-CA):** the subcomponent responsible for data gathering, integration and pre-processing (PDLC-DP) to generate exploitable context information and performance profiling (PDLC-PP).
- **Decentralised Learning (PDLC-DL):** the subcomponent responsible for exploiting the context information provided by PDLC-CA through decentralised learning models to add an additional intelligence layer to the operations of CODECO. It currently contains two models, a *Graph Neural Network (GNN)* and a *Reinforcement Learning (RL)* agent. Furthermore, this sub-component will include *Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)* pipelines to orchestrate the (re)training process of the mentioned models.

Figure 19: PDLC, sub-components, and interfaces.

The role of each CODECO component towards PDLC is as follows:

- **ACM:** PDLC relies, similarly to other CODECO components, on the CRs managed by ACM. These CRs will provide all the necessary information about the CODECO applications through the CODECO application model, providing both specs and status updates. ACM will also potentially receive output from PDLC-CA in the form of recommendations about initial cluster configurations, once enough historical data has been gathered and learning models have been trained.
- **MDM:** provides additional data information to PDLC related to data-related issues that may impact orchestration decisions. For instance, if an application requires access to large data sets, depending on network bandwidth and latency constraints, it may be necessary to constrain where the data is processed to achieve performance requirements. MDM provides a complete set of metadata describing the data (e.g., location, size, classification, policy evaluation) to assist CODECO in making orchestration decisions that are cognizant of data constraints.
- **NetMA:** provides network-layer metrics that are used by PDLC-CA and PDLC-DL in conjunction with the metrics combined from ACM and MDM to generate performance profile heuristics and pod placement recommendations. This will include both underlay and overlay network metrics and will be provided through the NetMA CR files.
- **SWM:** the main component to receive output from PDLC, both in the form of performance profiling as well as behaviour estimation and optimization. Crucially, SWM might need to provide feedback to PDLC about the decisions it makes based on the provided output, which would allow PDLC-PP and PDLC-DL to compare their suggestions with the taken actions and use that feedback to improve.

3.3.3.2 Key Technologies

- **TensorFlow**³⁴ and **Pytorch**³⁵ for the training and development of the PDLC-DL models, both the GNN model and RL agent.
- **Kubeflow**³⁶ for the implementation of the MLOps pipeline.
- **Prometheus**, Kepler, and new Prometheus CODECO operators, to observe and provide metrics to PDLC.
- **Python** and its main libraries such as numpy³⁷, pandas³⁸ for the processing and manipulation of the data throughout the PDLC sub-components.

3.3.3.3 Low-level Description of Sub-components

3.3.3.3.1 PDLC-DP: Data Pre-processing

PDLC-DP's objective is to deliver high-quality, interpretable data, continuously collected from ACM (I-PDLC-ACM-1), MDM (I-MDM-PDLC-1), and NetMA (I-NET-PDLC-2) CRs. This data is then provided to other PDLC sub-components, namely PDLC-CA and PDLC-DL, for further processing. The PDLC-DP architecture includes two main modules:

- **The Gatherer:** an entity that is responsible for collecting real-time data (cross-layer metrics) from all the aforementioned CODECO components through their predefined CRDs.
- **The Pre-processing Module (PP module):** in which data derived from the Gatherer are delivered and a collection of pre-processing operations is utilized to provide clean and correct-formatted data before being delivered to the other internal CODECO-PDLC sub-components.

The PDLC-DP architecture and its internal functionality is represented in Figure 20. As can be observed, the preprocessing module gathers stream-oriented data, (currently, recorded every minute by default) and then executes various processing operations tailored to each sub-component. However, these operations are performed concurrently to minimize execution time.

Figure 20: PDLC-DP internal functionality and steps.

34 <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

35 <https://pytorch.org/>

36 <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

37 <https://numpy.org/>

38 <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

The **gatherer module** is responsible for gathering all the metrics provided by the other CODECO components with their corresponding metadata (**from CAM, status section**), saving them in memory for PDLC-DP to use and then destroying them when they are not needed anymore. Another responsibility of the Gatherer is the continuous validation and recreation of the cluster topology from the topological information provided by NetMA.

The cluster topology, provided by NetMA, is described by the Gatherer in an adjacency matrix for the rest of the PDLC subcomponents to use. This procedure is happening in a configurable amount of time in order to easily fit with PDLC needs.

The **pre-processing module** is responsible for cleaning, curating, and preparing the data provided by the Gatherer. This module encompasses various operations, including data validation, transformation, normalization, integrity checks, and quality assurance processes. When the processing operations are completed, the processed data are stored in different CSV files - each one to serve the subcomponents functionalities and declares again its availability to the gatherer in order to start receiving new data.

3.3.3.3.2 PDLC-CA: Context-awareness

The metrics pre-processed by PDLC-DP are aggregated by PDLC-CA based on specific target performance profiles provided by the user via CAM.

PDLC-CA therefore relies on CODECO metrics (e.g., computational parameters such as CPU, memory; network parameters such as bandwidth, latency, link energy; data metrics such as data compliance, data size), and is also prepared to consider metrics from Prometheus.

The existing parameters are combined to provide nodes with a **data-network-compute** cost (aggregated cost) that provides a measure on how “well” the node is behaving for a specific performance profile selected by the user.

For instance, assuming the user would select as performance profile “*resilience*”, then PDLC-CA would create a node cost that **embodies node resilience and network (link) resilience**. Assuming the user DEV has opted to optimize the available infrastructure to reduce energy consumption, PDLC-CA considers energy consumption at a node level, and energy consumption during packet transmission (all links of a node) to provide an **aggregate resilience score** for the node.

The aggregated approach provided by PDLC provides a way to feed a finer-grained level of context to CODECO, while still reducing the information to be passed, and eventually reducing the number of operations to be required in the scheduling and re-scheduling process. The PDLC-CA communication sequence is provided in Figure 21. As represented, periodically, components NetMA, ACM, MDM monitor specific metrics as detailed in Annex I. These metrics are made available to PDLC-DP, which cleans, processes them, and normalizes them based on the specific needs of each PDLC sub-component.

For PDLC-CA (represented as CA controller), the metrics are periodically fetched from the treated data provided by PDLC-DP. Then, aggregated costs based on specific target profiles are computed to all available nodes in a cluster. The resulting scores are then written as a CR, which is available for PDLC-DL.

Figure 21: PDLC-CA Communication sequence diagram.

Assuming for instance, that a user would select resilience as a target for optimizing the overall system performance, the scheduler would have to handle resilience at a node level and resilience at a networking level. This would imply having to integrate multiple parameters, and at the same time, increase the number of operations required to ensure the computational resilience and then the networking perspective resilience.

By using a data aggregation approach to **score nodes based on specific performance target profiles**, CODECO expects to achieve the following:

- A significant reduction in the number of parameters having to be passed to a K8s scheduler.
- A better abstraction for schedulers (where aggregated costs are attributes of nodes), thus allowing for an easier introduction of new metrics.

The current approach followed in CODECO for data aggregation is statistical and considered an initial approach to a robust data aggregation. This approach will not suffice, in our opinion, for the multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments, where aggregated performance profile node scores shall be modelled based on a multi-objective suitable weight aggregation strategy.

Nonetheless, the current approach is relevant to provide CODECO with an initial approach to score suitable nodes based on performance target profiles that can take into consideration, at once, data, computational, and networking resources.

For a single cluster operation, the output of PDLC-CA is internally provided to the PDLC-DL component, core of the ML-based orchestration in CODECO, to ACM (I-PDLC-ACM-2) and to SWM (I-PDLC-SWM-1)³⁹. This aggregated cost (e.g., resilience or greenness) is then considered a node attribute by PDLC (and, in future versions, by SWM).

The model for the aggregated node score provided by PDLC-CA is as follows. A score (w) for a target performance profile (t) of a node i , represented as $w_i(i)$ is based on a set of cross-

³⁹ This interface, considered in the architectural design, has not yet been implemented – cf. To PDLC To-Do features, section 3.3.3.7.

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layer parameters \mathbf{P} : p_1, \dots, p_n related with: i) data being kept on the node for a specific application; ii) network link performance for the links; iii) computational resources (e.g., CPU, memory).

A generic score would be computed as in Equation (1), where the specific cross-layer parameters p_j are combined and weighted based on w_j . The weight w_j for each parameter can be set based on the level of importance that a specific infrastructure perspective has, and the sum of all w_j is 1. For instance, parameters related with networking may be more relevant than parameters related with data observability for a specific application. Currently, the specific weight to be set has not been analysed and hence, all parameters are equally weighted.

$$w_t(i) = \sum_j^n p_j w_j \quad (1)$$

The node score $w_t(i)$ is computed for each iteration with PDLC-DL. In the future, for the scheduler, the aim is to provide $w_t(i)$ as a target performance score, that SWM (or any other scheduler) can use as a node attribute, to rank the nodes.

It is currently possible to test (in CODECO, or standalone) two specific target profiles, which are provided as potential examples on how aggregated node costs based on a performance profile can be implemented. The efficiency and performance improvement of the heuristics have not yet been validated, being this a next step in the research being developed.

3.3.3.3.2.1 Performance Target Profile Greenness Examples

A first performance target profile implemented in CODECO concerns “**greenness (g)**”. By greenness it is meant that the aim is to ensure that the overall application deployment can reach a lower (ideally, lowest possible) energy consumption.

For greenness, different instantiations of $w_t(i)$ can be built, $w_g(i)$. An example currently available in CODECO is provided via Equation (2), based on the following purpose and rationale:

- **Purpose:** to provide nodes with a higher score that can contribute to achieve an infrastructure (for an application group) that has the least energy expenditure possible.
- **Rationale:** the lower the node energy expenditure; the higher the available bandwidth; the higher is the node greenness.

$$w_g(i) = \frac{1-n_e(i)}{n_e(i)} b(i) \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2), $n_e(i)$ corresponds to the energy expenditure in the node (between 0 and 1), and $b(i)$ corresponds to the available bandwidth of the node, computed as the sum of available bandwidth on all egress nodes of node i .

$n_e(i)$ is provided via ACM/Prometheus, based on the Kepler plugin⁴⁰. The node available bandwidth is based on the aggregated available bandwidth provided by the CODECO component NetMA.

⁴⁰ <https://sustainable-computing.io/design/metrics/>

Another potential formulation of a greenness node score is provided in Equation (3):

- **Purpose:** to provide nodes with a higher score that can contribute to achieve an infrastructure (for an application group) that has the least energy expenditure possible.
- **Rationale:** the lower the node energy expenditure; the lower the energy expenditure across the node egress links; the higher is the node greenness.

$$w_t(i) = \left(\frac{1-n_e(i)}{n_e(i)} \right) \left(\frac{1-l_e(i)}{l_e(i)} \right) \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), $n_e(i)$ corresponds to the energy expenditure in the node (between 0 and 1), and $l_e(i)$ corresponds to the energy expenditure across all egress links of the node, computed as the averaged sum of energy expenditure across all egress links on the node, based on an energy expenditure model per packet. $n_e(i)$ is provided via ACM/Prometheus, based on the Kepler plugin⁴¹. The link energy expenditure is provided via the CODECO component NetMA (netma-nsm-mon monitoring approach).

3.3.3.3.2 Performance Target Profile Resilience Examples

Another potential target profile being analysed and implemented in CODECO concerns resilience of the overall system. Currently, a resilience score $w_r(i)$ is focused on the selection of nodes that will maximise the resilience of the infrastructure, being provided in Equation (4):

- **Purpose:** Nodes are weighted for their contribution to resilience of the selected infrastructure.
- **Rationale:** the higher the number of link failures associated with the node; the smaller the node_degree; the lower is the resilience of the node

$$w_r(i) = n_f(i) \left(\frac{1}{d(i)l_f(i)} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where $n_f(i)$ corresponds to the number of failures of the node (provided by ACM/Prometheus), $d(i)$ corresponds to the node degree (provided by NetMA, nsm-net-mon, section 3.3.4.4.1.2) and $l_f(i)$ corresponds to the sum of link failures computed by NetMA (rf. to nsm-net-mon).

3.3.3.3.3 PDLC-DL: Decentralised Learning

PDLC-DL is responsible for all learning aspects in the CODECO framework. It receives input from PDLC-DP and from PDLC-CA and can provide output to all other components that need it. Thus, DL is not expected to have direct communications with other components of CODECO to retrieve any input data. On the other hand, the output that DL generates is made available via a CR to SWM, in the form of recommendations of nodes to which a specific application workload should be assigned. In the future, it may also be feasible to consider output to other components if required. For instance, for NetMA, PDLC may generate recommendations or provide information that can assist NetMA in handling abnormal networking patterns. **This interface is not currently implemented and is contemplated as optional in the design for future implementation** (rf. to To-Do features, subsection 3.3.4.7).

Another component that may benefit from the output of PDLC-DL is ACM (towards Prometheus): the output would relate in this case with feedback on the infrastructure

⁴¹ <https://sustainable-computing.io/design/metrics/>

improvements, due to the PDLC-DL recommendations provided to SWM. **This interface is not currently implemented but is contemplated in the design for future implementations.**

PDLC applies AI in different aspects, to improve the overall performance and adaptability of CODECO:

- **Reinforcement Learning Model:** provides node recommendations to allocate applications with the objective of balancing resource usage (data, compute, network) amongst all available cluster nodes.
- **Graph Neural Network Models:** provide predictions for the values of the monitored node and cluster metrics.
- **MLOPs.**

3.3.3.3.1 PDLC-DL-RL: Reinforcement Learning

RL is based on the notion that an agent must learn to adjust its behaviour within the dynamic environment that it interacts with by exploring and exploiting the search space and therefore to provide the best action/recommendation based on the specific environment's situation. PDLC-RL generates pod placement recommendations based on the input data it integrates from PDLC-DP, PDLC-CA and PDLC-GNNs. These node recommendations are written in a CR so that SWM can make more intelligent placement decisions.

State definition

The problem has been formulated as a *Markov Decision Process*, the components are defined as follows. The state (S_t) observed by the agent corresponds to a given timestamp t where a pod p needs to be allocated in the system as described via Equation (5). It contains the node resources CPU (C_p) and memory (M_p) requested by p , and the current state of the system, with all of the available C_p, M_p, g_n (greenness), r_n (resilience) for all nodes n .

$$S_t = C_p, M_p + \{C_n, M_n, G_n, R_n \forall n \in N\} \quad (5)$$

Action space

As per the action space the algorithm can choose to allocate a pod to all nodes in the system, but for this algorithm an adaptation is done where the result is obtained right after the Softmax⁴² layer of the Actor Network, by doing this the probability distribution of the network is obtained, then all values are normalized using min-max scaling between the obtained probabilities, thus obtaining a list containing the likelihood of allocating p to nodes in the cluster.

Reward

The reward function is defined by creating three separate components that are later combined with a series of weights that allow for the creation of custom models for specific performance profiles (e.g., Greenness). These reward components are the following:

- e_p : Energy consumed by pod p in the time where the reward is computed.
- $l_x(c)$: Distribution of resource x across a cluster i, c for CPU and m for memory.
- a : Value that rewards the algorithm for correct allocations.

Thus, the reward (R) is computed as is Equation (6), where the different weighted components, namely, energy consumed by pod p ; the demanded resources, load distribution

⁴² A softmax function or normalized exponential function converts a vector of K real numbers into a probability distribution of K possible outcomes.

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(on this example for node resources CPU and memory) are used to provide a result that can assist in understanding how well the overall resources are being used across a cluster, and finally, encourage is a flat value that rewards the algorithm for allocating the pod.

$$R = \begin{cases} e_p * w_e + l_c * w_c + l_m * w_m + a & \text{if action is correct} \\ -1 & \text{if action is waiting} \\ -10 & \text{if action is illegal} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Within the work of WP4, PDLC-RL will be updated to a decentralised approach adopting *Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL)* [19] which is suitable for the federated vision of PDLC-DL and the CODECO framework. In MARL, multiple agents across CODECO edge nodes can be trained with their own contextual data to provide the respective actions that maximize their cumulative reward.

3.3.3.3.2 PDLC-DL-GNN: Graph Neural Networks

This class of Neural Networks (NN) is beneficial in processing and learning from data that can be represented as graphs. GNNs are used *in lieu* of conventional ML/DL models, which are specialized in simpler and more uniform data types. In the case of CODECO, GNNs are used to generate resource consumption forecasting for the CODECO cluster nodes. These forecasting values are then integrated into the PDLC-RL model to generate pod placement recommendations based on the future outlook of the cluster status instead of only the current resource consumption status.

The *Graph Neural Network (GNN)* models within the PDLC-DL subcomponent are based on a *Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network (STGNN)* [22] [23]

The GNN models can provide predictions for the monitored metrics of a cluster's nodes. The models take as input historical timeseries data of each node (e.g., CPU or memory usage), as well as information about the cluster's topology, so that they can consider the spatial, as well as the temporal dependencies of the nodes and provide predictions about the aforementioned parameters in future timesteps. These predictions can be fed as input features to the RL models of PDLC-DL to enhance their performance and help them provide an improved pod allocation plan to SWM.

The *Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network* can predict future values of nodes' metrics based on historical observations, by modelling both spatial and temporal dependencies among nodes. The nodes' topology is mapped into a Graph structure and the model consists of a Graph Convolution Layer and a Recurrent Neural Network layer.

The Graph Convolution Layer applies graph convolution to the input to get the nodes' representations over time, so that for each time step, a node's representation is informed by its neighbours' representations. The Graph Convolution is calculated according to Equation (7):

$$h_i^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(b^{(l)} + \sum_{j \in N(i)} \frac{1}{c_{ij}} h_j^{(l)} W^{(l)} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $N(i)$ is the set of neighbors of node i , c_i is the product of the square root of node degrees (i.e., $c_{ij} = \sqrt{|N(i)|\sqrt{|N(j)|}}$), and σ is an activation function.

The nodes' representations are computed by multiplying the input features by the node's own weight and then each node's updated value is calculated by aggregating the neighbours' representations and then multiplying the results by the node's weight. The output of the layer is computed by combining the nodes representations. Based on the input, the graph convolution layer produces new tensor that captures the representations of nodes over time. To process the nodes' representations over time, a Recurrent Neural Network layer is utilized, in this case a *Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)* layer [20].

The workflow that is associated with the GNN models in PDLC is handled, as illustrated in Figure 22, by a controller, which includes the GNN orchestrator and the Inference service. The GNN orchestrator is responsible for continuously reading data provided by the PDLC-DP subcomponent.

Periodically, the aim is that the GNN orchestrator can therefore read information about the nodes in the cluster. Currently, it considers only CPU and mem (rf. To D12 for information on the current implemented models); however, the aim is to allow the orchestrator to consider any CODECO metric that PDLC may be relying upon. It then creates the appropriate request body and sends an API request to the Inference service every minute. The Inference service continuously reads the given cluster topology and when an inference request is received, it selects the appropriate pre-trained model based on the number of nodes, the requested CODECO metrics, and the requested forecast horizon (e.g., minutes, hours, days). Results are kept in a transient repository (currently, csv format) to be available to PDLC-DL-RL.

Figure 22: Representation of the PDLC-DL-GNN sub-component.

3.3.3.3.3 MLOps: Automation, maintenance, and deployment

To deploy ML models that will efficiently receive data from other components and output a multi-objective estimation, MLOps techniques will be employed within CODECO framework. Currently, the MLOps sub-module is used to evaluate and retrain the GNNs and will be extended to the RL models during the rest of the project. This MLOps pipeline consists of a module to evaluate the performance of the GNNs using the *Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)*. If the MAPE dips below a specified threshold, a retraining of the GNN is triggered. The pipeline then performs hyperparameter tuning and trains a new model with the optimal combination of parameters. Finally, the deployed GNN model is updated with the newly trained model. A representation is provided in Figure 23, and details on the implementation can be further checked in D12.

In this example, MLOps is responsible for the retraining of the PDLC-DL GNN models. Within the GNN controller, a retraining module is responsible for continuously MAPE in order to evaluate the models' performance and potentially trigger a retraining procedure depending on whether the MAPE is higher than a given threshold. If retraining is necessary, the retraining module of the controller uses the KFP SDK to create a Pipeline Run in Kubeflow. This pipeline

performs hyperparameter tuning and trains a new model with the optimal hyperparameters that were identified. After training, the new model is written in the shared volume, overwriting the previous one and in that way the inference service automatically uses the newly trained model.

Figure 23: MLOps pipeline depicting the retraining integration with PDLC-GNN.

3.3.3.4 Interfaces

The current interfaces of PDLC to other components, identified in Figure 19, are summarized in Table 8. The interfaces highlighted as *Planned* are not currently fully implemented but will be further developed within WP4.

Table 8: PDLC interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction	Status
I-PDLC-ACM-1	Obtaining data collected by other CODECO components and made available via CRs of those components.	CRs	Input	Available
I-MDM-PDLC-1	Data collected by CODECO MDM	CR	Input	Available
I-PDLC-SWM-1	Adding new attributes to SWM application CRs related to performance profiles generated by PDLC-CA	CR	Output	Planned
I-PDLC-SWM-2	Adding new attributes to SWM CRs related to node recommendations for application workload placement generated by PDLC-RL	CR	Output	Available
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC will be able to know about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Input	Available
I-NET-PDLC-2	PDLC receives underlay and overlay network metrics from NetMA	CR	Input	Available

3.3.3.5 Single-cluster Operation

The current operation of PDLC for a single cluster is represented in Figure 24. For a single cluster operation, PDLC has been devised to work in a centralised way (control plane of CODECO thus being placed in the CODECO control-plane).

PDLC sub-components are available in a modular way (docker container) and currently consider a common shared volume to store, access and modify the common data files generated by PDLC-DP.

Figure 24: Deployment diagram of PDLC within a single CODECO cluster.

These data files are periodically generated by polling the CRD and API endpoints of components that provide CODECO metrics via ACM. Once new data is detected, PDLC-DP processes it and generates the output to be used by the PDLC sub-components for their respective objectives.

PDLC-RL provides node estimations and updates the respective CR of SWM with node recommendations once the entire processing pipeline is done.

Figure 25 shows a sequence diagram of the interactions between the different PDLC sub-components in a single-cluster operation.

Figure 25: Sequence diagram of PDLC and its sub-components within a single CODECO cluster.

3.3.3.6 Federated Clusters' Operation

In the FC operations' phase, the PDLC component (PDLC-FC) will be enhanced to tackle two main challenges that are arising in Federated environments. The primary priorities of the CODECO PDLC FC component are two-fold:

- Firstly, it aims to address the challenges related to the acquisition, processing, management, and analysis of heterogeneous data generated and collected from diverse sources across different clusters, and to proceed with their respective aggregation.
- Secondly, it seeks to implement a collaborative learning approach among the federated clusters using federated learning techniques facilitating the privacy preservation and ensuring data sovereignty and confidentiality.

To address the first challenge, the consortium is planning to employ a suite of sophisticated methodologies designed to ensure the effective collection, processing, homogenization, and aggregation of data sourced from a variety of platforms with disparate software and hardware configurations and diverse data samples. The core strategy involves leveraging both supervised and unsupervised learning techniques, complemented by advanced data analytics methods, to achieve seamless data integration and analysis.

Regarding the second challenge, a decentralised learning approach will be adopted to avoid storing the data in a central location while concurrently facilitating the security and privacy preservation. This objective be achieved by selecting among novel fully decentralised approaches such as Swarm Learning [24][25], SplitNNs [26], Gossip Learning [27] to achieve a knowledge exchange among federated clusters.

Moreover, *Differential privacy* [28] can also be adapted to protect the privacy of individual datasets generated and collected within the clusters, while simultaneously ensuring versatile, agile scalability and enhanced robustness. The implementation plans for the PDLC-FC component involve extending the functionalities designed and implemented for single cluster operations to a decentralised framework. This includes enhancing capabilities such as RL and transitioning to MARL approach, as well as the study, design, and implementation of decentralised GNNs to support operations in federated environments [29].

Key considerations in the second phase include determining the optimal placement of the PDLC-FC component, whether it should operate within a hybrid architecture—where certain subcomponents are hosted within a central cluster while decentralised learning occurs across multiple clusters—or within a fully decentralised architecture. Both architectural approaches require thorough examination to assess potential risks and complexities and to ensure effective communication with other CODECO components. Furthermore, careful attention must be paid to defining the interfaces among CODECO components in federated environments. This includes the critical monitoring of diverse data collection in heterogeneous settings and addressing both inter- and intra-cluster communications.

Figure 26 provides a representation of the PDLC-FC component initial design, which will be further be tailored to assist the federated cluster operation phase.

Figure 26: Example of a potential design for PDLC-FC.

3.3.3.7 PDLC To-Do Features

A summary of to-do features for PDLC is presented in Table 9.

Table 9: PDLC To-Do Features.

ID	Description
PDLC-TD-1	Create MLOps pipeline for the PDLC-RL model, involving cross-layer CODECO metrics
PDLC-TD-2	Integrate the model training process to be done in alignment with CODECO (single cluster, multi-cluster, in-band with the Edge-Cloud and not necessarily offline).
PDLC-TD-4	In terms of context-awareness (PDLC-CA), perform the validation of the proposed heuristics; propose other formulations, and consider advanced methods (ML-based) for generating aggregated metrics.
PDLC-TD-5	In regard to the PDLC output, analyse the impact of PDLC-CA metrics on the scheduling process.

3.3.4 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation

3.3.4.1 Component Design Overview

NetMA is a network management and adaptation solution that automates the setup of interconnections for flexible Edge-Cloud operations, while addressing the integration of internetworking control and supporting the needs of diverse network environments (fixed, wireless, cellular) that are expected to be managed by CODECO. This CODECO component handles aspects such as network softwarization, secure data exchange, network performance monitoring and integrated network capability exposure through standard-based mechanisms and K8s APIs.

The areas of network softwarization that NetMA works on include providing connectivity to enable *Function-as-a-Service (FaaS)* to the Edge and automating network resource management to accommodate specialized service requirements. To promote the integration

of various networking domains it also realizes a continuous monitoring of the network performance and status with standardized technologies and integrates different network views into a joint status overview.

NetMA and its sub-components is represented in Figure 27. It currently considers the following sub-components:

- **Network state monitoring (NSM).** This sub-component allows the use of different network probing mechanisms (currently, active probing) [30] to bring network status to CODECO. Network status is captured at an underlay and overlay perspective, also from an individual link and path perspective.
- **Network exposure system (Nemesys).** Nemesys brings the networking metrics (underlay and overlay) captured by NSM into Prometheus and exposes them in the CODECO system (via ACM) and will also be responsible for the inter-cluster exposure aspects.
- **Secure Connectivity (L2S-M).** Based on the Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms (L2S-M) solution⁴³, secure connectivity in CODECO concerns the secure support of connectivity between pods within a cluster, and for federated clusters. L2S-M is a K8s networking solution that complements the CNI plugin approach of K8s to create and manage virtual networks in K8s clusters. In this context, the workloads are configured with an additional network interface (complementary to the one supplied by the CNI of the K8s cluster), and the traffic operated by such interface is handled by SDN. Thus, ensuring that all data traffic is isolated, and enhancing the security in the communication process between micro-services of an application.

Figure 27: NetMA, sub-components, interfaces.

3.3.4.2 Key Technologies

- The **ALTO⁴⁴ protocol and framework**, as the basis for building a network capability exposure mechanism. This protocol has a TRL of 3-5 being the protocol tested in relevant scenarios but the current implementation to be used is still under development.

43 <https://github.com/Networks-it-uc3m/L2S-M>

44 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/alto/about/>

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- **L2S-M**⁴⁵ as mechanism for providing link-layer secure connectivity for microservice platforms, for creating and managing virtual networks in K8s clusters. This component has a TRL of 5-6 as has been tested before in simulated scenarios both in European projects and academical tests.
- **ExaBGP**⁴⁶ as Border Gateway Protocol (BGP) speaker. This will be used to extract network routing and topological information. This component has a TRL of 7-8 as it has been used before in real telecommunications scenarios to obtain the BGP messages and topology updates.
- **Netperf**⁴⁷ as IP monitoring key enabler. This technology is the basis for the netma-nsm-mon, one of the NetMA sub-components related with underlay probing. One of the advantages is its flexibility in integrating new metrics to be monitored in K8s worker nodes. It currently has a TRL of 4-5.
- **ONOS**⁴⁸ as the SDN controller for transport network management in the creation and use of the network overlay. This component has a TRL of 7-8 as it has already been used in real scenarios in other projects.

3.3.4.3 NetMA Metrics

Current NetMA metrics are provided in Annex I, Table 18.

3.3.4.4 Low-level Description of Sub-components

3.3.4.4.1 NSM: Network State Management

NSM is being designed to support multiple networking probing approaches (for potential probing tools and their implementation, please refer to the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit, D12).

CODECO networking metrics are provided at an overlay and underlay level, at a node and application perspective. Examples of networking metrics being considered (rf. to Annex I, Table 12) are: throughput, latency, packet loss, link failure, and link energy, which are important for evaluating network performance.

NSM is currently based on two different approaches, described next. **Netma-nsm-npm** relies on ICMP and sockets to bring information at a networking level. **Netma-nsm-mon** considers a node-oriented approach to collect networking metrics and is based on an existing network probing aggregation approach, K8s netperf. These two approaches are explained next, with the caveat that the aim in CODECO is to provide flexibility to allow different network probing solutions to be integrated, based on a common abstraction.

3.3.4.4.1.1 netma-nsm-npp

netma-nsm-npp is based on ICMP Echo Requests and is aiming at allowing a high degree of flexibility in design. Netma-nsm-npp is an example of a network probing plugin which considers availability of metrics to meet expected QoS requirements. Currently, it provides throughput, latency, and packet loss.

The design of netma-nsm-npp emphasizes flexibility, allowing it to adapt to various network environments and requirements. Users can configure the tool to measure different metrics by setting appropriate flags during execution.

⁴⁵ <http://l2sm.io>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/Exa-Networks/exabgp>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/HewlettPackard/netperf>

⁴⁸ <https://opennetworking.org/onos/>

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- **Throughput:** The tool measures the data transfer rate between the source and destination. This is done using the measure throughput function, which sends a large amount of data over a TCP connection and calculates the rate of data transmission.
- **Latency:** The time taken for a packet to travel from the source to the destination and back is measured using the ICMP Echo mechanism. The *measure_latency* function captures this delay, providing data into the responsiveness of the network.
- **Packet Loss:** The *measure_packet_loss* function sends multiple packets and calculates the percentage of lost packets, indicating the reliability of the network connection.

The tool supports integration with various data communication platforms, and data are exposed via Prometheus on real-time. This allows for seamless data transmission and real-time monitoring. The Nemesys subcomponent listen to specific designed port to gather the measurement results.

The netma-nsm-npp probe is deployed as a DaemonSet in K8s, ensuring that each node within the cluster runs a replica of the probe. This deployment strategy guarantees that every node continuously measures the network performance to all other nodes in the cluster. When new nodes are added to the cluster, new replicas of the probe are automatically created to maintain coverage. The probes operate asynchronously, performing measurements every 120 seconds by default, with each measurement cycle taking approximately 4 seconds. This setup ensures real-time, distributed monitoring of network metrics across the entire Kubernetes cluster, facilitating efficient and scalable network performance management.

3.3.4.4.1.2 netma-nsm-mon

netma-nsm-mon is a sub-component of the HE-CODECO NetMA that focuses on probing the CODECO selected **underlay network** metrics. Netma-nsm-mom has been based on the existing open-source code of the K8s netperf licensed under Apache 2.0⁴⁹. The current design of netma-nsm-mon has been flexibilized to allow for the integration of any new metric. For the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit, the following metrics are monitored: **bandwidth, latency, packet loss, jitter, node degree, link failures** and **link energy consumption**. These parameters are relevant in CODECO, to the concept of node scores based on target performance profiles (rf. to PDLC-CA). netma-nsm-mon usage scenarios comprise:

- Real-time Network Monitoring: Continuously monitoring network metrics.
- On-Demand Network Measurement: Initiating network performance measurements based on external triggers or user requests.

The approach embodied in netma-nsm-mon⁵⁰ achieves a comprehensive view of network health and performance by integrating various monitoring tools and techniques⁵¹, for instance:

- **iPerf3**⁵². The traffic generator iPerf3 provides a way to create IP flows between nodes, and measuring aspects such as bandwidth, latency, jitter, packet loss. iPerf3 supports various parameters, such as setting the test duration, adjusting the TCP window. In the current netma-nsm-mon version it is used for bandwidth and packet loss testing based on the UDP protocol.

49 K8s Netperf is a benchmarking tool designed to measure various aspects of networking performance, focusing on bulk data transfer and request/response performance using TCP or UDP with the Berkeley Sockets interface. It supports tests over IPv4 and IPv6, and can be used on multiple platforms, including Unix, Linux, and Windows. It provides a simple way to test network performance between pods using various metrics

50 Publication under submission (R. C. Sofia, Bringing networking context into Kubernetes, 2024)

51 <https://www.redhat.com/en/blog/performing-large-scale-network-testing-red-hat-openshift>

52 <https://iperf.fr/>

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- **ICMP Ping.** Ping relies on ICMP Echo Requests to check connectivity and provide latency in the form of RTT for messages sent from the originating host to a destination computer. It is currently used for connectivity testing to monitor node degree and link failure states.
- **TCPdump.** TCPdump supports filtering criteria to capture specific types of traffic, making it a versatile tool for network administrators and security professionals. It can analyze protocols such as TCP, UDP, and ICMP, providing detailed insights into network activity. Used for packet capture and analysis to calculate link energy.

Bandwidth, latency, jitter and packet loss are provided based on the existing netperf approach and iPerf. The netperf command focuses on latency, providing detailed percentile metrics, while the iPerf command measures bandwidth and packet loss over the same duration.

Node degree is defined as the total number of active links available in the node. Currently, the implementation considers ping to assess available links. However, ping may not suffice in specific environments where nodes may be blocked with, for instance, local firewalls. Other kernel based neighbour discovery approaches are being considered, e.g., Nmap.

Link failures are currently measured by recording the number of ping failures to a specific target node over a period. Hence, currently the notion of link failure is associated with a soft link failure (connectivity). The overall value considers the total count of logged failures will give the number of link failures to the target node within a specific time-window. Other approaches that can be helpful in detecting other failures are “ip link”, Wireshark, etc.

Link energy refers to energy consumption over link which is computed based on the modelling proposed by Feeney et al., which establishes a linear relationship between power and packet size derived from experiments conducted in Wi-Fi networks, involving embedded devices [31]. Feeney et al. provides a practical approach to estimate link energy consumption based on packet transmission without having to recur to specialized hardware. Energy consumption is calculated as the product of power and time. The power P is determined by Equation (8) [31] where P_0 corresponds to a static parameter and a is a coefficient parameter that has been derived based on the measurement provided in Feeney et al. [31]; S corresponds to the size of the received or sent packet in bytes.

$$P = P_0 + aS \quad (8)$$

In the current formulation, packets transmitted were measured based on tcpdump. Assuming the time used for transmitting a packet is t , then the corresponding power consumption (e_p) for a packet p is calculated as in Equation (9), in microwatt-seconds.

$$e_p = Pt \quad (9)$$

The overall link energy consumption for a link i during a transmission period T is based on the computed consumed power per packet (e_p) per the time required to transmit packet p (t_p) as provided in Equation (10).

$$e_T(i) = \sum_{p=0}^n e_p t_p \quad (10)$$

To exemplify a usage scenario for netma-nsm-mon, Figure 28 shows a cluster with three worker nodes and one master node, interconnected via Wi-Fi. To monitor network parameters, each node hosts two daemon pods.

A first pod corresponds to a K8s-netperf pod deployed in a passive state, solely used for storing the netma-nsm-mon modified K8s-netperf, and the network monitoring iPerf tool. The other pod is actively engaged in real-time network monitoring and data updates by invoking the network tools deployed in the K8s-netperf pod or other interface information. Additionally, periodic updates of the ConfigMap (netma-nsm-mon output) are performed: the current code considers by default an update every five minutes. This can be configured by user DEV.

Figure 28: Example, netma-nsm-mon in a cluster with 3 worker nodes.

The specific monitoring timeline is shown in Figure 29. The time points below the timeline indicate the start of collecting a particular network parameter, while the time points above indicate the end of the collection and the storage of measurement results in the respective file. Specifically, at time t0, monitoring of link energy and link failure is initiated with durations of two minutes and one minute, respectively, based on the Python’s asyncio⁵³ package for asynchronous operations allows for simultaneous monitoring of both network parameters. At the end of the first minute, denoted as t1, the link failure monitoring concludes, and the results are recorded in the specified file. At the end of the second minute, denoted as t2, the link energy monitoring concludes, and the results are similarly recorded. Subsequent network parameters, being subject to real-time measurement, do not require continuous monitoring over a specific time period and thus do not need asynchronous operations.

From time t3 onwards, sequential monitoring of bandwidth, latency, packet loss, and node degree is conducted, with results being recorded in turn. This method allows for the concurrent monitoring of multiple network parameters within the same time frame and orderly recording of the monitoring results in the designated files.

Figure 29: netma-nsm-mon timeline example.

53 <https://docs.python.org/3/library/asyncio.html>

3.3.4.4.2 Nemesys: Network Exposure

Nemesys is the component that works as a *North-bound interface (NBI)* for NetMA. It currently provides output to the overall CODECO system (via ACM/Prometheus) by exposing underlay and overlay networking metrics captured by NSM.

Nemesys has as input the networking metrics captured by NSM (at an underlay and overlay level) and corresponds to a **topology view integrator**. It provides as output (NetMA CR/CRD) a topological network perspective as represented in Figure 30. Network performance information will be provided to ACM/Prometheus.

Figure 30: Nemesys matching between overlay and underlay network views.

From an architectural design perspective, once Nemesys becomes active in a cluster, it establishes a connection to the CODECO Prometheus instance running in the cluster⁵⁴. Prometheus is being periodically fed with information from NSM, which Nemesys uses to derive a fine-grained view on the topology (underlay and overlay).

Once the connection with the NetMA Prometheus is established, Nemesys starts reading the CODECO network metrics (which have been captured by NSM and integrated into the local Prometheus), mapping the entries' names obtained from Prometheus with the metrics to expose. The Nemesys workflow is represented in Figure 31.

⁵⁴ Please notice that in D12 the implementation of the OSS Basic Toolkit relies on a local Prometheus pod; the new release is expected by September 2024.

Figure 31: Nemesys interaction with NetMA components and CODECO components.

The output is currently provided in a CRD format and pushed to Prometheus (ACM). The updates are performed periodically (default is 300 seconds).

3.3.4.4.3 L2S-M: Secure Connectivity

The design of the NetMA Secure Connectivity component is based on the *Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms (L2S-M)* solution⁵⁵, identified as the basic connectivity mechanism for CODECO. L2S-M provides a K8s networking solution that complements the CNI plugin approach, enabling the creation and management of virtual networks in K8s clusters. These virtual networks allow workloads (pods) to have isolated link-layer (or layer-2) connectivity with other pods within a K8s cluster (*i.e.*, intra-cluster communications), regardless of the K8s node where they are deployed. L2S-M enables the creation/deletion of virtual networks on-demand, as well as attaching/detaching pods to those networks, providing a high degree of flexibility to dynamically incorporate new application and/or network configurations into K8s clusters. The main K8s interface of pods remains intact (provided by a CNI plugin), retaining the compatibility with all the standard K8s elements (*e.g.*, services, connectivity through the main interface).

To offer this, L2S-M operates a link-layer overlay network among the different nodes composing the cluster and turns that overlay into a programmable substrate for the creation of link-layer virtual networks by leveraging *SDN*. This OSI Layer 2 overlay approach provides some advantages in an environment such as CODECO, for instance in terms of transparency regarding the underlying transport technology or independence of the IP addressing for the establishment of services across the cluster nodes deployed in different network locations.

⁵⁵ L2S-M: <https://l2sm.io>

Figure 32. NetMA Secure Connectivity Design.

As part of the design outlined for the first phase of the project, L2S-M was added with the capability of measuring the performance supported by the overlay network, and also to provide a CR/CRD interface to interact with the rest of the CODECO components. Consequently, L2S-M can handle via this interface the notification of the performance supported by the overlay (so that the creation of virtual networks with a set of quality requirements can be based on that information) to other CODECO component, as well as providing an entry point to receive the request for the creation of virtual networks to communicate pods allocated in any node in the cluster.

Figure 32 illustrates this design, showing an overview of how the overlay network is composed, i.e., by the Programmable L2 switches (PLS) and the links established among them. In addition, the depicted L2S-M control plane accommodates the SDN controller, which manages the creation of virtual networks by controlling the different PLS. Co-located in the control plane there is also the *L2S-M Performance Measurement module (LPM)*, which collects the performance measurements of each of the links in the overlay network. Finally, the design includes the aforementioned CR/CRD type interface to enable interaction with the rest of the CODECO components.

The L2S-M operator conforms the communication channel between the SDN Controller, the K8s API and the L2S-M database, and redefines how virtual networks are created to allow pods use them. To this later, the operator offers a new a new type of networks, the Vlinks, which supports the path selection to steer the packets across the overlay in the bidirectional communications of two workloads.

Moreover, the operator comprises a CRD Controller (a Kubernetes Controller Manager) that actively utilizes an internal K8s API to continuously communicate with the SDN Controller, and

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to maintain an accurate representation of the Virtual Network's 's status, while enabling the other components the usage of the L2S-M component through K8s CRDs.

3.3.4.5 Interfaces

The current interfaces of NetMA to other CODECO components, represented in Figure 27, are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10: NetMA interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-ACM-NET-1	Integration of the NetMA metrics by Prometheus.	Prometheus	Output
I-SWM-NET-1	Used to request NetMA to perform QoS reservations. SWM may perform requests for reservations to NetMA, based on the scheduling/placement decisions. Furthermore, NetMA may also handle network related CRs (<i>Endpoint</i> , <i>NetworkLink</i> , <i>NetworkNode</i> , <i>NetworkPath</i>) to reflect network conditions.	CR	Bi-directional
I-NET-PDLC-1	Exposition of Network State Metrics both for Underlay and Overlay Networks.	CR	Output

3.3.4.6 Single Cluster Operation

During the setup of an application deployment NetMA is activated by ACM and triggers the definition of the network overlay through the policies and requirements received (ACM, SWM), passing the overlay information to SWM (IP, DNS/namespace configuration). This information and the underlay one, will be sent also to PDLC to perform its initial multi-objective estimations, which it will be passed to the SWM to perform the initial configuration process readjustments.

Once this phase is complete, the system enters in the cluster runtime phase. In this phase, SWM readjusts the configuration according to the input it receives, activating NetMA to perform a readjustment of the connectivity between nodes. This will be an iterative process that will be performed periodically as needed by the system, adjusting the behaviour according to the readjustments to be considered at each moment of operation. To enable this readjustment, NetMA will monitor periodically the state of both overlay (L2S-M) and underlay (Network State Monitoring) and exposing the information obtained to SWM (overlay information) and PDLC (overlay and underlay). Once with this information and the forecasted metrics provided by PDLC, SWM will calculate such readjustments.

In the initial configuration phase (single cluster), the Secure Connectivity sub-component (i.e., L2S-M) will provide secure connectivity among pods deployed across worker nodes within the cluster, regardless the specific compute nodes involved in the workload deployment. To this purpose, Secure Connectivity supports the flexible creation of virtual networks in the cluster, and the attachment of workload to those virtual networks. Likewise, Secure Connectivity will support the connectivity of workloads towards external networks, i.e., the Internet.

This workflow is represented in Figure 33, where both initial configuration and runtime activity is represented, showing also the main interactions between the three main sub-components of NetMA (considering SDN Orchestrator and Secure Connectivity an integrated module).

Figure 33: NetMA single cluster operations workflow.

Also, within a single cluster it is expected that NetMA has components on the control-plane of CODECO (secure connectivity, Nemesys), and others residing in the service plane at worker nodes (the LPM pods, a sub-component inside Secure Connectivity module and the different instances of NSM), as represented in Figure 34.

Figure 34. NetMA single-cluster deployment view.

3.3.4.7 Federated Clusters' Operation

Within a federated cluster, multi-tenant environment, for NetMA it is relevant to map the notion of clusters to a single administrative domain, which in the case of CODECO follows the internet *Autonomous System (AS)* principles, defined for routing: a federation can take place among clusters belonging to the same AS or to multiple AS. To complicate this even further, when multiple AS are considered, NetMA needs to consider also the **tenant** involvement, i.e., if the different AS are operated by the same tenant, or not. Hence, the basis for the design of the NetMA federated operation is a **multi-cluster, multi-tenant environment**.

Two main questions are expected to be addressed for the NetMA-FC operation:

- How to ensure secure data exchange across multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments, addressing challenges derived from potential frequent mobility and application migration.
- Which information needs to be exchanged across clusters, to allow for an efficient orchestration and migration of applications across Edge-Cloud, while ensuring low latency, and low energy consumption.

To assist the design of NetMA for federated clusters, the consortium will start by considering a multi-cluster environment within a single AS. For NetMA, in this case a centralised network control can be considered, which is common also at an AS routing perspective. This design will therefore have also to be mapped to the K8s design (which does not necessarily consider a centralised design, even if a single AS is involved).

For the case of multiple administrative domains in the networking part, an analysis should be performed about suitability and feasibility of considering centralised versus decentralised scenarios, in terms of coordination, data monitoring transfer, topology visibility, etc, which could require multiple NetMA instances in parallel coordinated and synchronized.

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For the NetMA-FC operation, three main functionalities shall continue being addressed: i) provision of connectivity; ii) provision of network visibility; periodical, iii) aggregated and secure network state monitoring.

In the case of having a centralised or unique control plane (multi-cluster, single AS), this could be translated to the need of potentially having a complete topological view associated to the CODECO control. Starting from a single administrative domain, this implies the constitution of a central decision-making and authorization entity, handling the overall topology view.

Under this perspective, a feasible alternative could be to continue the model presented up to this stage of the project and extend it to the multi-cluster scenario. Figure 35 illustrates this potential approach, where a new overlay network could be operated but this time formed through inter-cluster links and managed in parallel to each of the existing single-cluster overlay. This overlay is based on the external links established between the elements defined as *Network Edge Devices (NEDs)*, which are devices implemented as virtual functions that can be deployed within each cluster and establish secure IP tunnels with the other NEDs allocated on different clusters. Thus, this additional overlay extends the data plane of each cluster and, as in the single-cluster model, could rely on SDN to provide programmability and support the creation of virtual links that enable link-level communications among workloads running remotely.

Additionally, NetMA could include a module to collect the available performance in term of network metrics (such as end-to-end delay, available bandwidth or jitter) across the links composing this inter-cluster overlay network. This module is depicted in Figure 35 as inter-cluster LPM (or i-LPM), since it would be based on the performance metrics collection solution developed in the single-cluster phase (i.e., LPM). Then, this performance information would be available to other components (through the module delineated as Inter-cluster Performance Metrics), assisting in the integration with other components of the CODECO framework. For instance, the SWM component could use such information in its scheduling operations, or the PLDC for forecasting activities.

Similarly, the monitoring information from Nemesys needs to be extended to the federated cluster scenario. The implications will depend on the involvement, or not, of multiple AS in the federation, since aspects such as inter-AS monitoring (i.e. monitoring of the boundaries between AS's), the exposure of intra-AS monitoring information, the composition of metrics for deriving end-to-end values, etc. All these concepts are expected to be part of such analysis. An additional aspect to consider in the multi-cluster scenario is the need of passing information from different cluster to some other components, for instance monitoring. This is an issue being addressed in articulation in CODECO, namely, the design of a common semantic abstraction perspective for clusters and their data.

Without a complete topological view (which, from a design perspective, is the main aim of CODECO in regard to a decentralization of the control plane of orchestrators), then network exposure mechanisms increase in relevancy. In NetMA, the current approach is to consider a derivative of ALTO as the basis for network service exposure to CODECO.

Figure 35. NetMA-FC initial multi-cluster approach, with focus on L2S-M aspects.

3.3.4.8 NetMA To-Do Features

Table 11: NetMA To-Do features.

ID	Description
NetMA-TD-1	Align NSM, ensuring a design with different probing mechanisms that complement itself and that allow for the easy integration of i) new network metrics; ii) new probing mechanisms.
NetMA-TD-2	Integrate the overall architectural design with the CODECO monitoring architecture based on Prometheus and in the future Thanos

3.3.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration

3.3.5.1 Component Design Overview

The CODECO SWM component handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This implies assisting the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) placement of applications and their containers across Edge-Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics). The SWM handles, for instance, the “best” placement (based on context-awareness indicators) for the containerised components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, dealing with dynamic properties of available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Further, this placement shall be dynamically adaptable, which implies achieving the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerised micro-services of an application, including their state, across Edge and Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (device and node availability; container centrality, network aspects).

SWM provides the following main functionality:

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- **Initial placement of workloads based on the application/user QoS requirements.** SWM performs a decision for each application deployment on which workload (pod, Container) should run on which node in a cluster, while fulfilling the QoS requirements of the application. The requirements are expressed by the user DEV via ACM, using the CODECO Application Model, and available to all CODECO components.
- **Dynamic placement of application workloads (re-scheduling).** SWM makes a new decision on placement of workloads whenever conditions change (e.g., new applications/components added, applications/components removed or changed, infrastructure conditions changed, change of QoS requirements by the user).
- **Application workload deployment and re-deployment.** SWM takes care that the workloads are executed on the selected nodes and takes remedial actions in case of failure, using native K8s mechanisms.
- **Application workload migration.** SWM manages moving a workload already running on a compute node to another compute node. This may be implemented in different qualities and steps:
 - Migration of stateless workloads.
 - Migration of stateful workloads.

SWM , its sub-components and interfaces are represented in Figure 36.

Figure 36: SWM sub-components and interfaces.

A very basic concept that is integrated in SWM is the so-called SWM QoS model. It is a formal model to describe application requirements provided by the user (a translation is performed from the CAM by ACM into the SWM Application model) and the infrastructure (*Infrastructure Model*).

SWM resides on the control plane of K8s. It extends the K8s resource model by some CRs, making use of the K8s controller pattern to implement controllers for those resources. SWM implements the following CRs, as represented in Figure 37 and described next:

- **ApplicationGroup:** Bundles a set of *Applications* that shall be placed/scheduled together. Using this construct, users can explicitly control the granularity and sequence of placement decisions.

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- **Application:** Bundles a set of *Workloads* and *Channels* that belong to a (modular and distributed) application.
- **Workload:** Represents a component of an *Application*, is defined by a *Workload* spec that is an extension of the K8s pod spec. Typical characteristics of a *Workload* are compute, memory, and storage requirements. In CODECO, the *Workload* spec is expected to be extended with new attributes, for which examples are provided in Annex I. A *Workload* maps to one or several pods, that are deployed at a later stage.
- **Channel (object):** Represents an explicit, unidirectional communication relation of a *Workload* to other *Workloads*. Current attributes of a *Channel* are bandwidth and latency (in the sense of requirements of the application). These attributes are used by the *Workload Placement Solver* to match with the available network infrastructure capabilities and conditions when deciding on the placement of the *Workloads*. In CODECO, the *Channel CR* is expected to integrate additional attributes to further strengthen the network awareness, and to integrate a broader notion of context-awareness, as being defined in CODECO.
- **Channel (CR):** Each *Channel* object will be mapped to a *Channel CR* that represents an explicit communication service in the network infrastructure. Depending on the underlying network technology and service class, it may be possible or required to setup communication services to reserve network resources and to guarantee certain QoS requirements for *Channels* between *Workloads* that are placed on different nodes. The *Channel* resource keeps track and manages the lifecycle and states of such a communication service, handling the required interactions with the respective service endpoints of the network infrastructure. As the QoS guarantees in CODECO are provided via NetMA with a new level of sophistication, this CR may or may has a strong relation to network resources handled by NetMA.
- **NetworkTopology:** Represents a compact description of the overall network that is available for the *Channels*, i.e. for explicit communication between *Workloads*. It is used by NetMA to communicate and update the available network resources to SWM. The *NetworkTopology* consists of nodes (compute nodes, network nodes), network links, and network paths (optional). For better internal handling, SWM translates the *NetworkTopology* into own internal CRs: *NetworkEndpoint*, *NetworkLink*, *NetworkPath*. There is a separate *NetworkTopology* per so-called network implementation. In CODECO, currently two network implementations are used: k8s-network and L2S-M -network. While the k8s-network uses the standard k8s overlay network for best effort communication, the L2S-M -network uses the NetMA Secure Connectivity (L2S-M) for network services with dedicated QoS.
- **NetworkEndpoint:** Represents worker nodes in the cluster. It covers aspects of the nodes that are not covered by the K8s standard resource *Node*. Currently, it is used to keep information about network interfaces and related addresses (IP and MAC) on the nodes. Additional aspects and information related to the worker nodes may be added to the *NetworkEndpoint CR*, e.g., information on its specific energy consumption, availability (current and projected). It is envisioned that the *NetworkEndpoint CR* may be controlled by another CODECO component (e.g., ACM).
- **NetworkLink:** Represents the links of the underlying communication network that interconnects the compute nodes of the cluster. Current attributes of a *NetworkLink* are bandwidth, available bandwidth, and latency. Network awareness shall be further extended in CODECO, being currently envisioned that the *NetworkLink CR* will be controlled by another CODECO component, NetMA. A first sub-set of attributes is provided in Annex I. A *NetworkLink* connects a *NetworkEndpoint* or *NetworkNode* with another *NetworkEndpoint* or *NetworkNode*.
- **NetworkPath:** Besides the physical network topology, the paths (or routes) that can be used to transmit data between any pair of endpoints are relevant to decide on usage and/or allocation of network resources. In the current implementation, *NetworkPaths* are

calculated by SWM from the existing network topology. As part of the scheduling decision, each Channel is assigned a NetworkPath. For the L2S-M -network, SWM requests a reservation for a NetworkPath for each Channel from the NetMA component.

- **AssignmentPlan:** CR that contains the result of the placement decision, as returned by the Workload Placement Solver. This includes for an *ApplicationGroup*: for all *Workloads* the *Nodes* they shall be placed on, and for all *Channels* the *NetworkPath* that shall be used.

Figure 37: SWM CRs and objects.

3.3.5.1.1 State diagrams for the CRDs

The following state diagrams are implemented as state machines as part of the reconciler loops of the respective CRDs. There is a state transition function for every state transition, that handles the respective actions.

3.3.5.1.1.1 ApplicationGroup

Figure 38 shows the state diagram of the SWM CRD *ApplicationGroup*. Once created, the *ApplicationGroup* remains in the state “Waiting” until the minimum number of applications are present. Triggered by that condition, the state progresses to “Optimizing”, and the Workload Placement Solver is called to calculate the placement for the Workloads and Channels for all applications in the *ApplicationGroup*.

Depending on the outcome, the *ApplicationGroup* either enters the state “Failed” or “Scheduling”. In the state “Scheduling”, the Channels for all Applications are established and the pods corresponding with the Workloads of all Applications are scheduled. Once all Applications are running, the *ApplicationGroup* returns to the “Waiting” state.

Figure 38: SWM CRD ApplicationGroup state diagram.

3.3.5.1.1.2 Application

Figure 39 shows the state diagram for an Application CR. Once created, the Application is in the state "Waiting", where it waits for the trigger from the ApplicationGroup to start scheduling pods for its Workloads.

Figure 39: SWM CRD Application state diagram.

As soon as some pods are in the state Pending, the Application also moves to this state, until all pods are running (the Application transitions into “Running”) or at least one pod or Channel fails (the Application transitions into “Failing”).

3.3.5.1.1.3 Channel

Figure 40 shows the state diagram for a Channel CRD. This state diagram provides a generic model to implement even complex network interactions. The states represent the different steps for reserving resources locally as well as in the network, getting acknowledgement from the network, as well as observing QoS during operation, and freeing resources when cancelling or deleting a Channel.

Figure 40: Channel state diagram.

In summary, the following steps correspond to the Channel states:

- *Requested*: The Channel was created by the ApplicationGroup controller (as a consequence of being part in an SWM Application Model that was requested by ACM). This triggers a review of logical resources to establish the Channel, like e.g. required IP addresses.
- *Reviewed*: The logical resources are available. In this state, physical resources are checked (still from a local perspective). This can be e.g. checking the available resources on the required network links as reported by the NetworkTopology CR.
- *Implementing*: Physical resources are deemed sufficient, and the Channel is requested from a corresponding external Network Manager, like e.g. NetMA for Channels using the L2S-M network.
- *Implemented*: Once the requested Channel is acknowledged by the external Network Manager, CNI metadata (network annotations) are attached to the pods at both ends of the Channel (sending and receiving end).
- *Acknowledged*: Once the pods are successfully annotated, the ApplicationGroup controller creates the K8s services and endpoints, that allow the application to make use of the Channel using DNS name resolution.
- *Running*: The Channel is ready to be used to transfer data.

3.3.5.2 Key Technologies

The initial design and components of SWM is based on the SIE existing background implementation of “Seamless Computing” [32]. The “Seamless Computing Orchestrator” is built as an extension to the K8s control plane, making use of new CRDs/CRs and respective controllers and operators. Main technologies in SWM are:

- K8s, the K8s control plane and the K8s extended API (all TRL 9); the controller and scheduling frameworks (TRL 9).
- Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC, TRL 9) and Protocol Buffers (Protobuf, TRL 9).
- Go programming language (Golang, TRL 9).

The QoS Scheduler is currently available for CPU architectures AMD64 and ARM64.

3.3.5.3 Low-level Description of Sub-components

As illustrated in Figure 13, SWM is composed of the following components:

- **Extended K8s API/ CODECO CRs.** The main API of SWM is the (extended) K8s API. It serves as an API to users of SWM (e.g., to deploy applications, or to request status information about them), but also as a system interface towards the compute infrastructure via the Kubelets running on the worker nodes (e.g., to update resource information about the compute nodes, or to instruct the deployment of pods on a worker node). It is also via this API that SWM interacts with other CODECO components. The interfaces to other CODECO components are implemented as CRs, either as an extension of the existing SWM CRs, or as new ones.
- **QoS model.** The QoS Model is used by SWM to decide on the placement of workloads of an application. It is not a component, but a data model that is used in different places, as explained in subsection 3.3.5.3.1. (SWM QoS Model).
- **SWM controller-manager.** The SWM controller-manager bundles a couple of SWM custom controllers that manage SWM CRs, which have been described in Section 3.3.5.1 (SWM component design overview).

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- **QoS Scheduler.** The QoS Scheduler is a custom scheduler that is built using the K8s scheduling framework⁵⁶, it runs as a pod in the K8s cluster, and it registers as scheduler to the K8s control plane. It implements the so-called scheduling plugins for certain phases of the K8s scheduling lifecycle. While the K8s standard scheduler schedules each pod individually, one of the specific mechanisms of the QoS Scheduler is that it decides on the placement of all pods of an *ApplicationGroup* at once. This is required to consider dependencies between the pods (e.g., communication relations and QoS), and to treat the pod placement as a graph problem, rather than a sequential, linear problem. The deployment of the pods within an *ApplicationGroup* is held back, until the placement decision is taken, and all communication resources have been confirmed (if applicable).
- **Workload Placement Solver.** The Workload Placement Solver is called by the SWM controller-manager to determine the placement of the workloads of all Applications in an *ApplicationGroup*. There can be different implementations of Workload Placement Solvers. The API uses gRPC, where the QoS Model (call of Workload Placement Solver) and the placement decision (returned result) are described as Protobuf. The Workload Placement Solver is deployed as a pod in K8s. In CODECO, an implementation of the QoS Solver is provided as source code and could also be used as blueprint to implement further solvers, optimizers, or heuristics (e.g., learning-based implementations). A more sophisticated optimizer is available as container image for use by the CODECO partners within the CODECO project.

3.3.5.3.1 QoS Model

The SWM QoS model consists of two parts: the *Application Model* and the *Infrastructure Model*.

The *Application Model* describes distributed, modular applications, that consist of workloads that communicate via interfaces. The attributes of an application are expressing the QoS requirements of the application. The *Infrastructure Model* describes the hardware entities that form the execution environment for the applications. It consists of compute and network infrastructure, particularly compute nodes, network nodes, and network links. The attributes of the Infrastructure Model express the resources and capabilities of the infrastructure.

Further data may be required to define the decision objective, i.e., the criteria that are optimized or at least used as guidance to prioritize and finally select a placement of the workloads of an application. A generic extension mechanism has been implemented, that allows to define weights (called node recommendations) for each workload as part of the *Application Model*. These node recommendations can be used to express any combination of criteria to influence the scheduling. The node recommendations are considered by the *Workload Placement Solver* to place workloads on the suggested nodes, as far as the constraints given by the *Application Model* (e.g. compute capacity, network requirements) can be fulfilled.

Regarding network QoS, SWM implements two service classes, ASSURED and BESTEFFORT. The BESTEFFORT service class uses the ordinary K8s overlay network to communicate over the dedicated *Channels* requested in the *Application Model*. *Channels* with the service class ASSURED are implemented using the overlay network provided by NetMA. For this, dedicated L2S-M Vlinks are requested from NetMA for each Channel.

⁵⁶ <https://github.com/kubernetes/enhancements/tree/master/keps/sig-scheduling/624-scheduling-framework>

3.3.5.3.2 QoS Scheduler Extension Mechanisms

As described above, a generic extension mechanism has been implemented to influence the behaviour of the SWM QoS scheduler without having to change the implementation. For each Workload, so-called node recommendations can be defined in the Application Model. They define weights where to place this Workload, which serve as the primary optimization criterion for the placement decision, after fulfilling all QoS constraints.

3.3.5.3.3 Workload Placement Solver

The SWM solver works with a set of applications each having a set of workloads. There are channels connecting two workloads. This logical description of an application is mapped to a set of (compute) nodes connected by network paths, i.e., the physical infrastructure of a Kubernetes cluster. A workload and a channel specify criteria that a node or network path must support.

The SWM solver considers for each workload the set of nodes it may be assigned to (e.g., with respect to node resources such as CPU and RAM) and for each channel the set of network paths it may use (with respect to network resources such as bandwidth and latency). For each workload and channel there is a decision variable defining the set of options available.

There is a single list with all decision variables. Variables for workloads are ordered so that workloads with few options are checked first. The variable for a channel is inserted right after the variables for its two workloads. Consider two workloads A and B checked in this order. The variable for a channel connecting these workloads follows directly the variable for workload B. When the workloads were placed, the Solver can select a suitable path between the nodes.

The Solver then traverses the list of decision variables to find a solution. If the currently selected set of nodes and paths is not suitable, the Solver tries another set until a solution is found. The Solver may not be able to place all applications in a cluster. In this case it drops the last application and tries again.

3.3.5.3.3.1 Sequence Diagram

The target environment for the SWM Solver is currently a K8s cluster where Solver returns a solution for an assignment problem to the SWM QoS Scheduler. Figure 41 shows the interaction between Solver and Scheduler. In this setup only the Solver's component "solved" is involved. Component "solve" is not used. To keep the figure simple, the user talks directly with Scheduler to request a deployment. In a real cluster the user talks to Kubernetes' API that reaches out to Scheduler as appropriate.

Figure 41: Interaction between the SWM QoS Scheduler and Solver.

In a development setting Solver’s components “solve” and “solved” are used as shown in Figure 42. The user uses component “solve” to send requests to component “solved” running as a background process. In this setup the server can be located on the same machine or on another machine. The user installs the command-line applications of “solve” and “solved” as appropriate.

The first part in the figure below shows how an assignment problem given in “native” form (e.g., as a JSON file) is handled. The user passes the file to solve that sends it to solved via the gRPC interface. solved computes a solution for the assignment and returns the solution via the gRPC interface to solve that displays it to the user.

The second part shows how solve handles an assignment problem given in Solver’s special text format for assignment problems. An assignment problem is easier to specify in this format.

If the Solver talks to a server in this way the server can be running as a background process or in a Kubernetes cluster. The user passes the process’ address on the command-line when invoking solve.

Figure 42: Interaction between the SWM Solver’s components.

For testing purposes, it is sometimes convenient to “just” determine a solution for an assignment problem, as represented in Figure 43. If solve is not given an address of a server to talk to, it solves the given assignment problem itself using exactly the same algorithm as solved.

Figure 43: SWM Solver computing a solution itself.

3.3.5.3.3.2 Solver’s Backtracking Algorithm

When a user deploys an application group in a cluster, Solver is the component that decides which workload is assigned to which worker node. The task of placing workloads in a cluster corresponds to an *assignment problem*. This section is about the algorithm Solver uses to find a solution to an assignment problem.

The SWM Solver follows the principles below when assigning pods to nodes. In contrast to the K8s standard scheduler, the SWM Solver considers applications and not only workloads and knows about the network within a cluster. It is not necessary to specify network requirements for an application:

- The SWM Solver tries to assign all workloads of all applications in an application group to a cluster’s worker nodes considering both computing and network resources.
- The Solver places as many pods as possible in the cluster. An application is handled in its entirety.
- The Solver distributes workloads using the same rules as Kubernetes (i.e., it computes the same node priority). The set of rules is simplified with respect to Kubernetes as Solver does not consider for instance node or pod affinity.
- The Solver does not try to find the “best” solution for a set of applications but finds a suitable solution (the first is encountered).

3.3.5.3.3.3 Network Communication

A path describes how two nodes can communicate and defines bandwidth and latency between the two nodes on this path. If the protocol requires to acknowledge messages there is also a path in the reverse direction needed. The reverse path must have sufficient resources for the acknowledgement information. It is not necessary that the path in the reverse direction is the reversed path.

Currently, the Solver assumes that the traffic forwarding can be configured with respect to the channels. If there are two channels between two nodes, it is assumed that the traffic moves on the appropriate channel. If the network does not support channel-based forwarding, the assignment might not work properly as network requirements might be violated due to “unexpected” forwarding.

Especially any communication in the “reverse” direction might be problematic. For some network types it may not be possible to specify a particular path for the reverse direction (e.g.,

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for automatic acknowledgements) as they always “reverse” the path of the incoming traffic. In this case, it will be necessary to extend Solver’s model so that different network types are supported.

This applies not only to traffic forwarding but also to how a network type makes use of its bandwidth. Collision detection might eat some bandwidth due to the delays it introduces. For properly routing traffic it might be important to know a channel’s chunk size. Using small chunks for a given bandwidth may decrease the available bandwidth by more than the required bandwidth due to the delay introduced by the chunks. Solver does not take this into account.

3.3.5.3.3.4 Workload Representation

A workload is currently represented by a tuple with the workload requirements: resources, e.g., CPU, RAM, and required and forbidden labels. This is sufficient to solve the assignment problem but has a problem as the SWM Solver is not able to take advantage when there are identical workloads. If two workloads have the same set of requirements, they still may be different workloads as they may use different images. Adding an image identifier to workloads tuple allows Solver to avoid visiting of identical combinations.

3.3.5.3.3.5 Workload Placement Solver Algorithm

The current algorithm is based on Knuth’s Algorithm B [33], which has been adapted to assign the workloads of a set of applications to nodes while respecting the application networking requirements. The example here provided considers latency and bandwidth as examples of such requirements.

A network is defined by links between two nodes having a given latency and bandwidth. There may be network nodes (i.e., nodes that do not run workloads) to build a certain topology. A network path consists of one or more links and connects two compute nodes. A path’s bandwidth is the minimum bandwidth of its links and its latency the sum of the latency of all links. There may be more than one path between two nodes. A set of nodes may be connected by more than one network. Network paths do not span networks, i.e., all links in a path are of the same network “type”.

The domains D_k for algorithm B are subsets of the compute nodes for workloads and subsets of the network paths for channels. These subsets are not static as they change (i.e., get smaller) as workloads are assigned to nodes and channels to paths. A property P_l is fulfilled if for all nodes the workloads assigned to the node do not exceed its capacity and for all paths the channels using it do not exceed its bandwidth.

Visiting an assignment means that a solution was found that fulfils all workload and channel requirements. No further checks are necessary to accept this solution.

The algorithm does *not* traverse all assignments. It stops at the first suitable solution found. There is no optimization with respect to the number of total workloads assigned to the cluster. If it is not possible to assign the workloads of all applications, the algorithm reduces the set of applications considered.

Algorithm B (Basic backtrack). Given the domains D_l (set of nodes suitable for a workload and path suitable for channels between workloads) and properties P_l (all workloads or channels W_i placed so far do not exceed nodes or paths’ capacities), visit all sequences $x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$.

1. [Initialize] Set $l \leftarrow 1$. Initialize auxiliary data structures:
 - For all channels determine the set of possible paths. Go to step 6 if there is a channel without any path.
 - Determine the network requirements for all workloads.

- For all workloads determine the set of nodes. A node is available for a workload if the workload's compute and network requirements are satisfied. For each node keep the list of nodes that the workload talks to when assigned to this node. Go to step 6 if there is a workload without nodes.
 - Sort the list of workloads with respect to the number of available nodes. This assigns workloads with few possible nodes early and leads to a fast failure.
 - Insert the variables for channels into the list of variables for workload so that a channel is inserted when its two workloads were placed.
2. [Enter level l .] (Now $P_{l-1}(x_1, \dots, x_{l-1})$ holds.) If $l > n$, visit $x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$ and stop if the solution is suitable or go to step 5. Otherwise (i.e., $l \leq n$) set D_l to the set of nodes or network paths that can currently host W_l . If the set of nodes or channels is empty, go to step 5. Sort nodes in D_l with respect to Kubernetes' node priority or sort channels with respect to latency. Set $j_l \leftarrow 1$ and $x_l \leftarrow D_l[j_l]$, the node with the highest priority in D_l or the path with the lowest latency.
 3. [Try x_l .] If $P_l(x_1, \dots, x_l)$ holds, assign W_l to node x_l or to path x_l , set $l \leftarrow l + 1$, and go to step 2.
 4. [Try again.] Unassign W_l to node or path x_l . If $j_l < |D_l|$, set $j_l \leftarrow j_l + 1$, $x_l \leftarrow D_l[j_l]$, and go to step 3.
 5. [Backtrack.] Set $l \leftarrow l - 1$. If $l > 0$, go to step 4.
 6. [Reduce problem size.] If there is more than one application, remove the last application, and go to step 1. (Otherwise stop without a solution).

3.3.5.4 Interfaces

The current interfaces of SWM to other components are summarized in Table 12. The interfaces between SWM and other components are realized via K8s CRs. One advantage of this is, that the K8s API already provides extensive means of access rights and control.

Table 12: SWM interfaces to other CODECO components.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-SWM-ACM-1	Access/integration with CRs/operators handled by SWM and other CODECO components, e.g., NetMA	CR	Bi-directional
I-SWM-ACM-2	Registration, configuration, and operation of QoS Scheduler	K8s scheduling framework	Bi-directional
I-PDLC-SWM-1,2	PDLC will set attributes of custom resources of the infrastructure model, that are used by SWM to influence the placement decision for workloads. This can relate to combined costs (I-PDLC-SWM-1) or to behaviour estimation (I-PDLC-SWM-2). , this is done by setting node recommendations for the workloads in the SWM Application Model.	CR	Input
I-SWM-PDLC-1	PDLC knows about scheduling/placement decisions of SWM by accessing the <i>AssignmentPlan</i> CR	CR	Output
I-SWM-NET-1	Used to request NetMA to perform QoS reservations. SWM performs requests for reservations to NetMA, based on the scheduling/placement decisions. Furthermore, NetMA uses the <i>NetworkTopology</i> CR to regularly update SWM about the topology and status of the network infrastructure.	CR	Bi-directional

As has also been explained, SWM may perform QoS reservation requests to NetMA. Assuming interface I-SWM-NET-1 would be based on the CR *Channel*, then NetMA would have to implement a controller⁵⁷ that handles the reservations.

As next steps, we expect that NetMA handles QoS reservations per type of network QoS model adopted (e.g., DiffServ, L2VPN), thus requiring a CR/controller per network QoS model. Such controllers would also be responsible to observe and manage the respective CR and react by implementing all steps to establish an end-to-end connection with the required QoS settings and to indicate success or failure via appropriate states.

3.3.5.5 Single Cluster Operation

The operation of SWM starts when ACM, via the CODECO operator, sets up all components. The steps are the following, being the sequence diagram presented in Figure 44:

- Via ACM/CAM, user DEV describes the application requirements.
- SWM relies on this file to create the description of the desired deployment, considering the CRs ApplicationGroup and Application (including Workloads, Channels, and all relevant attributes).
- Once the minimum number of Applications that are part of the ApplicationGroup is created, the ApplicationGroup custom controller collects all information required for the placement (QoS Model).
- Both the SWM Application and Infrastructure Models are compiled based on the CODECO Application Model, obtained via ACM.
 - The Application Model considers the CRs: Applications, Workloads, Interfaces.
 - The Infrastructure Model is compiled by retrieving information from the related infrastructure custom resources: Node, Endpoint, NetworkLink, NetworkNode, NetworkPath. Basic node capabilities are retrieved using the K8s information. Information about the network (L2S-M overlay) is regularly updated by NetMA (using the NetworkTopology CR).
- The ApplicationGroup custom controller calls the Workload Placement Solver, handing over the QoS Model.
- The Workload Placement Solver determines a placement for the workloads of the applications, considering all constraints and (if it is an optimizing solver) optimized according to the defined objective. Basic node capabilities are retrieved using the K8s information. Information about the network (L2S-M overlay) is regularly updated by NetMA (using the NetworkTopology CR). The result is returned and placed in the CR AssignmentPlan.
- For each Workload that could be placed, a pod is created, the preferred node for the pod is set according to the placement decision. However, deployment of the pods is still held back.
- For each Channel between Workloads that could be placed, a CR Channel is created. Channels between Workloads that are placed on the same node are tagged as “*loopback channels*” (they do not require connections over the network).
- For all other Channels, the respective network controller (watching the creation of the Channel) will react accordingly. Depending on the network technology and implementation of the network controller, a reaction could be keeping track of occupied bandwidth for the Channel, and/or reserving/establishing an end-to-end channel through

⁵⁷ A simple network controller for best effort networks is being implemented as blueprint as part of the current redesign of Seamless Computing.

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the network. In any case, success, or failure of the establishment of an end-to-end channel needs to be reported via the state of the CR Channel.

- Once all Channels of an Application are in state “ACKNOWLEDGED”, the deployment of the pods of the Application will be kicked off.
- K8s will deploy the pods, resulting in downloading and starting the appropriate containers in the selected nodes, and the Applications will become operational.

A so-called QoS deployment works as outlined in Figure 44 To keep the event sequence diagram readable, it shows components (e.g., ACM and SWM) and does not show all controllers involved.

Figure 44: Event sequence diagram for single cluster operation.

The operation outlined so far starts with a user deploying an application. SWM can also reconsider a deployed application when “the environment” changes. When PDLC (rf. to section 3.3.4) determines a changed node recommendation for an application already deployed to and running in a cluster, PDLC considers the current deployment and computes node recommendations for the application workload(s) due to certain criteria (e.g., energy efficiency of node or network usage), and sends them to SWM, i.e., it updates SWM’s CRs as appropriate. SWM uses the changed application description to determine a new assignment plan and implements it. In this case the set of workloads running in a cluster does not change but workloads are relocated from one node to another. The event sequence diagram derived from node recommendations triggered changes is provided in Figure 45.

Figure 45: Event sequence when node recommendations are changed.

Triggers for re-scheduling relate with PDLC and may also be derived from other aspects. For instance, if a node goes down, or if a network link or path does not longer meet the expected QoS level, then SWM is expected to, in the future, consider information provided to reschedule the application workload(s).

3.3.5.6 Federated Clusters' Operation

The design of SWM for federated clusters requires addressing at least the following challenges:

- **Adapt the SWM Application Model for multi-cluster**, multi-tenant environment. Such adaptations, which will have to be aligned with CAM, are expected to be minimal, as the intention in CODECO is to ensure that multi-cluster operations are transparent to the user.
- **Evaluate and decide on scheduling alternatives in accordance with the latest developments of multi-cluster management.**
 - Meta-scheduler approach (centralised).
 - Hierarchical approach
 - Decentralised approach

The crucial aspect to handle in terms of complexity, is to work on a scheduling approach that remains as simple as the one provided for a single cluster operation and yet can cope with the higher degree of complexity.

As has been discussed in ACM (CAM) for federated cluster environments, an important aspect is to allow the user to label micro-services in case they have a specific dependency and should not be moved across clusters. Assuming, however, that there are no limitations, then the application workload scheduling and re-scheduling should be able to be deployed across multi-cluster environments.

For scheduling in a federated environment two approaches are considered at the time of writing: a centralised and a hierarchical approach. The centralised approach uses a so-called meta scheduler, and the distributed approach uses an enhanced version of SWM's scheduler for a single cluster. Both mechanisms use the information about the inter-cluster network.

- *Meta Scheduler*—A meta scheduler is a central component (i.e., there is one instance) that distributes an application's workloads to different clusters. It relies on aggregated information from the clusters to decide on where to place workloads. The clusters report aggregated information in a timely manner to the meta scheduler. Placing a workload within a cluster is done using the cluster's scheduler. The meta scheduler computes the latency available for a channel' sub-paths in a cluster and passes it as a requirement to the cluster's scheduler. The latency for an inter-cluster path is computed from the information about the inter-cluster overlay network.
If a distribution of workloads does not yield a valid deployment for some reason, the meta scheduler tries again with another distribution. It is beneficial to enhance the cluster schedulers to report some statistics and diagnostics to the meta scheduler so that a solution is determined faster. If a certain workload for instance cannot be hosted in a cluster at all, this should be indicated to the meta scheduler, so it can reassign the workload.
- *Hierarchical Scheduling*—With distributed scheduling the deployment of an application starts in a particular cluster. The starting cluster may be specified by the user or determined by the system. The cluster considers the deployment and schedules all workloads it supports. The deployment is updated accordingly and forwarded to another cluster. These steps are repeated until all clusters were visited or all workloads were placed in a cluster.
If the first round does not yield a solution, the process can be repeated by sending the remaining workloads to a different cluster (i.e., enumerating all clusters). If this does not yield a solution, the system can retry with another starting cluster. It might be helpful to annotate workloads with the set of clusters that support them to speed up the search for a solution.

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Both the aforementioned approaches consider a model where a multi-cluster, multi-tenant environment is devised as a multi-layered graph: clusters are seen as nodes (where a node is a networked environment); between clusters there is a network. A specific gateway on each cluster would handle ingress and egress traffic to other clusters following the usual networking translation approach. This would assume that each cluster would be synonymous to the Autonomous System (AS) structure of the internet, and that NetMA would be able to capture the configuration.

An inter-cluster network path between nodes N and M in clusters A and B would consist of three sub-paths: a path in cluster A from node N to the gateway, a path from cluster A's gateway to cluster B's gateway, and a path in cluster B from the gateway to node M. SWM can place two workloads connected by a channel in different clusters, if there is an inter-network path between the two nodes.

It is anticipated that SWM treats clusters as “units”, i.e., a cluster's infrastructure details like its network topology should not be considered or needed outside of the cluster to arrive at a scheduling decision for a federated environment. Without this restriction, decisions about placing connected workloads in two clusters depend on each other and this complicates the scheduling substantially. This approach would therefore be similar to the one provided by Hydra[16]

An additional direction to be addressed concerns a **decentralised control plane design**, for which starting points are, for instance, DOCMA [10], or the debate of Larsson et al. advocating for a decentralised control plane to increase the level of resilience and scalability of Kubernetes [15]. Megha [17] and Pigeon [18] are, in this context, interesting approaches to be further checked. Megha relies on flexible logical partitioning of clusters to distribute its scheduling load, ensuring that the requirements of the workload are satisfied with very low scheduling overheads. It uses a distributed global scheduler that does not rely on a centralised data store but, instead, works with eventual consistency, unlike other schedulers that use a tiered architecture or rely on a centralised database. Pigeon provides decentralised scheduling by dividing worker nodes into fixed resource encapsulations, which may not be suitable to the CODECO compute-network-data approach.

3.3.5.7 SWM To-Do Features

A summary of to-do features for SWM is presented in Table 13.

Table 13: SWM To-Do features.

ID	Description
SWM-TD-1	Introduce additional aspects, like energy consumption. This could for instance be achieved by tagging the infrastructure components (nodes, network links) with specific energy consumption, and potentially providing specific energy demand in SWM's application model (e.g., for workloads or channels).
SWM-TD-2	The current implementation of SWM supports QoS based on 2 levels (Assured and Best Effort). As NetMA brings a new level of network awareness, the specific QoS guarantees to be provided will be discussed with NetMA. In case of changes, SWM will have to be adapted. It should be noticed that for usage in CODECO, the Seamless Computing implementation has been redesigned in a way that each communication service level maps to an appropriate network infrastructure technology, and each network infrastructure technology will require a network operator. Hence, assuming CODECO adopts (as an example) another QoS model, such as DiffServ, then, the respective CRs and operators will have to be handled in NetMA.
SWM-TD-3	Re-scheduling and workload migration
SWM-TD-4	Analysis of up to which point decentralisation should be handled for scheduling in federated cluster operation.

4 Challenges and Priorities towards Federated Cluster Operations

4.1 Federated Cluster Orchestration Challenges

Federated cluster (FC) orchestration is a complex and challenging task in the realm of the Edge-Cloud continuum, in particular due to the fact that the original design (for Cloud services) needs to be adapted to selecting, deploying, monitoring, and dynamically control applications composed of several micro-services across mobile, heterogeneous Edge-Cloud environments [47]. This section brings the perspective of related literature and related projects, to further explain the selected priorities described in section 4.2. The work here described corresponds to the starting point for the work to be developed in CODECO, WP4.

4.1.1 Edge-Cloud FC Orchestration Challenges

Related literature has been addressing some of the challenges that are more urgent to be tackled. For instance, Prigent et al. debate on challenges for FC operation and propose future directions, making a distinction between a resource-intensive Cloud environment, and an Edge low-latency environment [48]. The authors' view focuses on the computational resources and debate on the need to further address **decentralization**, in particular for AI-based orchestration. Their focus is on the debate and systematic presentation of existing federated learning approaches to support the decentralised, robust, and diverse behaviour of FC orchestration operation across Edge-Cloud. Relevant in this context is also the debate on how to train personalized models in a way that can best adapt to the modelled Edge-Cloud. CODECO follows this work, aiming at addressing the higher degree of complexity of considering computational, network, and data resources. Similarly, Ullah et al. provide a survey towards CEI, considering heterogeneity of computational resources, different architectures, and a need to achieve **standardised interfaces and API** for inter cluster coordination. **Mobility** and **scale** are also additional challenges debate in this survey. While the survey stills focuses on the management of computational resources across Edge-Cloud, connectivity is also mentioned in the form of automatic or manual registration. While in CODECO, the aim is to consider a higher degree of heterogeneity and a flexible approach to the management of different resources, at different layers (currently, computational, network, data).

Overall, based on related work, the key challenges to address in the context of FC orchestration are:

- **Standardised support for application description.** Similarly to CODECO, several approaches consider YAML as basis for this description. Others consider TOSCA to describe applications. However, TOSCA still falls short in regard to Edge applications [50].
- **SLA management.** Most available solutions target SLA enforcement, but the overall management (violation reporting, inter-cluster monitoring, standardized description of SLAs) is still lacking. ETSI in this context
- **Context-aware resource discovery/registration.** The focus is on the possibility to provide user DEV with enough flexibility to bring new resources into the orchestration process, and to dynamically share resource availability among different administrative domains.

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- **Pro-active reconfiguration/re-scheduling.** The volatile and higher heterogeneous architecture of the Edge-Cloud continuum requires a more sophisticated approach to the re-configuration processes required during application runtime. Currently, scaling and offloading are two common processes that start to be assisted via AI/ML. This is the approach followed in CODECO as well, following a context-aware ML based approach that aims at analysing also how to stabilize the system in terms of a need for reconfiguration, as a reactive approach results in more variability in the system.
- **Decentralisation.** Current approaches are focusing on centralised architectures as these significantly reduce the implementation complexity and provide a robust approach to the decision-making process of orchestration. However, centralised approaches may not suffice for an Edge-Cloud continuum that is mobile, highly heterogeneous, and multi-tenant [51]. Scalability, single points of failure, and bottlenecks are examples of immediate drawbacks which, for a proposal such as CODECO that addresses orchestration via an integrated approach at different layers, becomes problematic. The aim is therefore to analyse up to which point a decentralised control plane is required to ensure scalability, robustness and energy efficiency.
- **Security handling and privacy-preservation.** Security continues to be a major issue in related literature, being partially addressed. For the constrained Edge, security also becomes an issue, as nodes may be limited in terms of resources (network, computational) [52]. CODECO is addressing security management and privacy preservation by design, based on the components ACM and PDLC.

4.1.2 Edge-Cloud FC Operational Challenges

From an operational perspective, K8s addresses the need to provide FC orchestration based on the following requirements:

- **Low latency:** serving the user closer to their location via multi-cluster architecture reduces latency.
- **Fault isolation:** By deploying applications across smaller clusters instead of in a single large cluster, improves fault isolation support in case of failures.
- **Scalability:** User demand drives the scalability needs of a system.
- **Hybrid cloud:** Prevent provider lock-in by having environments based on multi-cluster, multi-tenant operations.
- **Administration Isolation:** Keeping separate clusters tied to different administrative domains simplifies SLA handling, improves service decoupling, and provides better performance when compared to the multi-tenant architecture that relies solely on the presence of namespaces.

The K8s Multicluster Special Interest Group (K8s SIG-MC)⁵⁸ focuses on challenges concerning management of multi-cluster environments, including cluster federation environments. For K8s, FC management consists of a centralised control plane (host cluster that manages deployments and propagates changes to participating clusters) that supports the loose coupling of several independent K8s clusters. Such coupling is managed via a standard API to manage cluster-wide operations, while DNS aspects are managed by federated configurations. Resources and services of multiple clusters can be aggregated into a single, logical entity while handling the management of individual clusters in isolation. A key difference between the federation notion and multi-cluster operation is that the former

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/kubernetes/community/blob/master/sig-multicluster/charter.md>

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embodies the notion that multiple K8s clusters are linked together, allowing them to share resources and manage workloads among them.

CODECO will follow the evolution and discussion on K8s SIG-MC; however, given that the current debate misses fundamental answers to some of the identified challenges, CODECO will also follow its path in terms of FC operation proposal, in a way that is compatible with K8s.

Additional relevant projects to mention are the OSS Ligo⁵⁹, KubeAdmiral⁶⁰, Karmada⁶¹, to name a few. Each of those solutions takes a different approach to multi-cluster management. Ligo key aspects concern the use of peer-to-peer (P2P) approach to simplify inter-cluster networking; the definition of application seamless offloading based on a virtualized abstraction of multi-cluster sets; transparent network exposure.

KubeAdmiral derives from the K8s Kubefed v2.0 tool providing compatibility with the Kubernetes native API. Some new features concern the scheduling framework, status aggregation of member cluster resources and improved user experience. Karmada has also been developed based on Kubefed v2.0. In Karmada, member clusters register with the host cluster which acts as the sole admin overriding policies and propagating configuration changes and workload scheduling decisions to the registered clusters.

Out of these three approaches, Ligo is an approach that will be further debated in CODECO concerning the proposed P2P approach and seamless offloading mechanisms. This shall be addressed by considering the Ligo approach against the support that the NetMA L2S-M solution provides, in particular its capability to bring to K8s an SDN-based programmable data plane which allows networking paths to be influenced by a variety of algorithms (e.g. reactive, metric-based, geographic-based), as well as allowing services to react in advance to changes and select the most appropriate paths without tampering with their network layer configuration. Thus, it provides high flexibility to incorporate new applications into K8s clusters in a dynamic way.

Hence, despite the recent advancements in federated cluster management systems, most approaches cope just partially, or not sufficiently with the challenges posed by the Edge-Cloud continuum paradigm, such as providing seamless end-to-end interconnection, handling device or communication protocol heterogeneity, while still, tackling scalability and elasticity issues that hinder their application in Edge-to-Cloud setups.

4.1.3 Summary, Main Challenges

Based on the analysed literature and projects, CODECO defines as the most relevant challenges to handle in FC orchestration the challenges presented next. For the description of the requirements, this section again follows following the IETF principles: The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in IETF RFC 2119 [9].

- **Decentralization and Self-organizing cluster federation model.** The CODECO FC operation **MUST** be able to handle the Edge-Cloud continuum based on a model of self-organizing clusters. For this, the potential decentralization of the control plane **SHOULD** be studied and considered in terms of advantages and disadvantages for the overall design, where resilience, reduced energy consumption and improved QoS/QoE performance (e.g., lower latency) are the main target performance goals.

59 <https://github.com/liqotech/liqo>, <https://docs.liqo.io/en/v0.10.3/>

60 <https://github.com/kubewharf/kubeadmiral>

61 <https://karmada.io/>

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- **Visibility.** A key aspect to handle is the capability to handle resource sharing across multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments. Exposure of information (network exposure, but also computational exposure) SHOULD integrate an expressive, eventually intent-based semantic abstraction and MUST consider a flexible approach to context-awareness exposure across clusters.
- **Mobility and Adaptive Networking.** At an inter and intra-cluster level, networking aspects need to be handled from a K8s perspective and also taking into consideration the internet administrative domain fabric (AS). It is RECOMMENDED to consider SLA management and approaches to allow for a flexible adaptation of the established overlay networking, taking into consideration underlay variability.
- **Application-oriented semantic composition and data aggregation.** The overall application scheduling and re-scheduling process MUST rely on an application-oriented semantic composition, for which the FC starting point is the CAM. This model will be further extended to integrate the devised approach for decentralization and cluster self-organization in CODECO.
- **Pro-active rescheduling, with focus on migration (instead of replication).** Current K8s based approaches focus on resource scaling, load-balancing. However, in mobile Edge-Cloud environments there are scenarios where migration is required. CODECO shall continue the debate on the advantages and disadvantages of considering migration instead of replication in the context of container orchestration.

4.2 CODECO FC Proposals and Priorities

This section summarizes the initial CODECO proposals to tackle FC orchestration, derived from the debate presented on section 3 for each of the components' expected operation in multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments. The debate is presented by order of priorities, from the most significant one to the lesser significant one.

4.2.1 Priority 1: Control Plane Decentralization

For FC operation, CODECO has opted to rely on Open Cluster Management (OCM) and on the RHT OCM upstream project ACM to address the limitations of existing FC management systems. Both tools are based on RHT OpenShift. OpenShift is a very mature technology that has edged over its competing solutions, especially in production environments; this is mostly because OpenShift ensures high availability and uptime. Other OpenShift-related projects have evolved to support Edge scenarios. In particular, Hypershift is a solution that ensures scalability and fast provisioning of k8s clusters in remote/edge workers. MicroShift is a lightweight Kubernetes solution for deploying solely a minimal OpenShift control plane. To meet the requirements of even more constrained environments, such as the micro-edge, there are also evolving solutions, a promising one being Flotta. Flotta manages workloads deployed on small-footprint devices and integrates nicely with Microshift.

OCM follows a hub-and-spoke control plane model and as debated in section 3.3.1.7 for the ACM operation, the application of OCM to multi-cluster environments is clear, being key challenges to address in this context the application semantic abstraction adaptation (CAM), the automating bootstrapping of authentication and control message encryption, and monitoring.

However, the adaptation of CAM is also subject to a debate on up to which point it would be important for the overall CODECO framework to rely on a decentralised plane in particular considering that CODECO targets far Edge to Cloud orchestration. Based on comprehensive comparisons of existing K8s tools, Baldoni et al. advocate the need for a decentralised control

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plane to support the far Edge [54]. Some proposals towards such decentralization start to emerge, as is the case of the work of Larsson et al., who propose a decentralised control plane to support FC orchestration based on a shared database of CRDs which are to be shared amongst all federated clusters, and via a distributed resource scheduling approach. CRDs may, however, not suffice in the context of more variable time-series data, as is the case of networking metrics. The work of Larsson et al. is a starting point for the debate to be addressed in CODECO in the upcoming months (WP4) to decide whether or not the control plane should follow a fully decentralised or hierarchical model.

Assuming a direction towards a decentralised control plane, CODECO will have to address such decentralization across the three orchestrated layers (data, compute, network) and understand the resulting complexity. For instance, at an application layer it is important to address if CODECO is expected to support both stateless and stateful applications. At a networking level (NetMA), it is also important to consider SDN-based decentralised approaches and how these would interact with the control plane [55]. For the data observability, MDM intrinsically can cope with decentralization (e.g., based on a distributed database model to capture and handle linked data and relationships between application and data).

4.2.2 Priority 2: Privacy-preserving Decentralised AI

Approaches to consider supporting a robust and scalable FC operation have been presented in section 3.3.3.6 (PDLC FC). As explained, CODECO aims at going beyond hierarchical FL and is exploring the possibility of considering Swarm Learning, SplitNNs and Gossip Learning to achieve a common knowledge exchange across a federation of clusters.

Relevant in this context, in addition to the operational aspects tied to the adaptation of RL and MARL to the Edge-Cloud continuum, is to consider how to train (and adapt) personalized models to specific environments, thus ensuring scalability in CODECO. In particular, it is important to articulate (also from an operational mechanism) the capability to perform inline training, and not just offline, centralised training, as this is essential when considering the far Edge.

The data monitoring and management architecture (ACM) in CODECO is also a relevant aspect to articulate in this context. Inline training will require continuous data and some form of prior calibration, to provide meaningful results.

It is relevant to notice that currently, CODECO relies on a privacy-preserving centralised AI/ML model to provide the CODECO scheduler (SWM) with information that can support an informed and more stable decision-making for the application scheduling and re-scheduling.

The focus towards PDLC-FC is to discuss and validate the need and relevancy of considering a decentralised partial decision making and learning layer on top of the CODECO FC framework, to assist in the overall adaptation of the system in a way that allows clusters to keep their isolation, while at the same time-sharing sufficient resources to sustain a self-organizing federation of clusters.

4.2.3 Priority 3: FC Semantic Abstraction and Adaptive Networking

As has been debated in sections 3.3.1.7 (ACM) and 3.3.4.7 (NetMA), CODECO FC needs to handle the **application** and the **infrastructure** (federation of clusters, multi-tenant) via flexible and expressive semantic abstractions.

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For the **application**, the starting point is CAM. CODECO will continue on relying on a YAML based approach but address also the need to consider additional interfaces if CRDs are not sufficient to handle the resource exchange across clusters.

For the **infrastructure** (federation), CODECO shall address the federation as a semantic abstraction to assist in better defining aspects such as configuration synchronization, and cluster data to be exposed across the federation, following some initial ideas under development in the community, such as the multi-tenant Virtualcluster abstraction proposed by Zheng et al. [56], or the debate on service relationship orchestration derived from large-scale experimentation with K8s provided by Sebrechts et al. [57]. Methods for data aggregation that target performance profiling will be considered, to reduce the need to expose data, and contribute to data security and privacy (PLDC-CA), considering the need for decentralization [58].

Concerning internetworking and FC connectivity aspects, as has been debated in NetMA, section 3.3.4.7, the focus shall be on a progressive design that can consider tenant involvement, i.e., different administrative domains at an internet AS level. Hence, the basis for the design of the NetMA federated operation is a **multi-cluster, multi-tenant environment**, and two main research questions will guide the work of the NetMA-FC operation:

- How to ensure secure data exchange across multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments, addressing challenges derived from potential frequent mobility and application migration.
- Which information needs to be exchanged across clusters, to allow for an efficient orchestration and migration of applications across Edge-Cloud, while ensuring low latency, and low energy consumption.

The proposed approach described in section 3.3.4.7, which considers a design that mimics the routing approach followed in the internet, addressing intra and inter-AS /intra and inter-cluster operation separately, will be compared from a model level to advocated solutions in the community focusing on decentralised SDN – decentralised K8s/CODECO plane interaction and interoperability, assuming heterogeneous networking technologies, including cellular/wireless technologies [55].

4.2.4 Priority 4: FC Scheduling

Assuming a design that targets, for resilience, robustness, and energy efficiency a far Edge to Cloud decentralised application deployment and orchestration, then it is important to consider up to which point (and what means) can the scheduling process in CODECO be decentralised. As has been explained in section 3.3.5.6 (SWM FC), there are currently directions towards the design of a meta-scheduler, centralised approach, and a hierarchical approach. Furthermore, it is relevant to understand the need and relevancy of a decentralised scheduling approach. From the different proposals, it is relevant to highlight Pigeon which provides decentralised scheduling by dividing worker nodes into fixed resource encapsulations, albeit this may not be suitable to the CODECO compute-network-data approach.

Additional relevant approaches in this context are Tarsil [60] and Sparrow [61]. Tarsil relies on a hybrid shared-state approach. Schedulers work in parallel (per cluster) and rely on a shared state server and specific resource units. Specific application workloads are assigned to a node by a scheduling agent. Each time a decision is performed, the scheduler informs the control plane. While this design suits the current SWM and CODECO design and is in line with the proposed meta-scheduler approach, conflicts may occur due to data synchronization across the cluster. An improved version of Tarsil is available via the work of Ungureanu et al. [59].

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Sparrow⁶² is based on a fully distributed scheduling approach, where again multiple schedulers operate in parallel, but there is no a single global view of the overall federation. Sparrow relies on the power of “*two choices in randomized load-balancing*” and introduces late-binding to handle application scheduling with lower latency. To schedule a workload, Sparrow relies on probes to a randomly selected set of worker nodes. Then, it places the workloads on the least loaded of the probed workers (late-binding).

The approaches mentioned serve as potential example of directions that may be taken in WP4.

5 Global Validation Aspects

5.1 Experimentation Tools

5.1.1 Simulators, Emulators, Testbeds

The CODECO consortium is addressing the validation of different features based on different tools available. This section goes over some tools that can be used, and which are suggested to provide alignment in terms of validation.

Several **emulators and simulators** can be used to test Edge-Cloud components of CODECO, e.g., node containers and networking aspects. For instance, Mininet-WiFi⁶³ (useful to emulate Edge devices), Containernet⁶⁴ (useful for lightweight Edge-Cloud deployments) and OpenConfig-KNE⁶⁵ (a K8s network emulation) can create custom network topologies and add container-based hosts, while experimental tools such as k8s-netsim⁶⁶ (a Mininet based K8s Network Simulator) simulates K8s workers as Mininet hosts (using flannel for connectivity among containers and Skupper for multi-cluster deployments). Furthermore, additional network simulators and emulators can be utilized to investigate independent/isolated network mechanisms, technologies, and standards (e.g., cloud deployments, TSN) such as CORE⁶⁷, EMANE⁶⁸, EstiNet⁶⁹, OMNeT++⁷⁰ and ns-3⁷¹. Regarding the (synthetic) data generation and visualization, some CODECO use cases are already expected to use simulators/emulators e.g., UC2 to produce data from cameras and V2X RSUs, with the CARLA8 and OMNeT++.

Furthermore, CODECO counts with a synthetic data generator, as detailed in section 5.1.2.

Some tools utilized for **benchmarking** in K8s include kubestr⁷² (a set of tools to evaluate the performance of cluster storage options), kube-bench⁷³ (a tool to evaluate the K8s deployment security), k-bench⁷⁴ (a framework for benchmarking the control and data plane aspects of a K8s infrastructure, namely, pod start, networking, I/O metrics), Theodolite⁷⁵ (a framework for

62 <https://github.com/radlab/sparrow>

63 <https://github.com/intrig-unicamp/mininet-wifi>

64 <https://github.com/containernet/containernet>

65 <https://github.com/openconfig/kne>

66 <https://github.com/IBM/k8s-netsim>

67 <https://github.com/coreemu/core>

68 <https://github.com/adjacentlink/emane>

69 <https://www.estinet.com/ns/>

70 <https://github.com/omnetpp/omnetpp>

71 <https://gitlab.com/nsnam/ns-3-dev/>

72 <https://github.com/kastenhq/kubestr>

73 <https://github.com/aquasecurity/kube-bench>

74 <https://github.com/vmware-tanzu/k-bench>

75 <https://github.com/cau-se/theodolite>

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benchmarking the horizontal and vertical scalability of cloud-native K8s applications/microservices).

In addition, **networking tools** such as iPerf, NetPerf, cURL, and wget can be used for various aspects of networking, workload, and performance testing. In the context of K8s, NetPerf and iPerf server/client can be created and deployed on the nodes of a K8s cluster (as Deployment or Daemonset) detecting network properties, such as MTU size and bandwidth, but also measuring performance statistics, such as packet loss, delay, and jitter. cURL and wget can be used to directly access the K8s REST API, monitor the availability and web server responsiveness of applications deployed in K8s as well as monitor the services' health.

Referring to real-time **monitoring/observability**, operators and performance visualization tools are essential to provide insights into the health and performance of clusters, nodes, or individual pods. Such tools include Netdata⁷⁶, Prometheus, Grafana, Datadog⁷⁷ and Pixie⁷⁸ while Thanos and Mimir⁷⁹ can enhance/extend the monitoring and storage capabilities of multi-cluster environments.

Furthermore, a variety of **load testing tools** are available to simulate load conditions, ensuring the performance and scalability of components and applications under stress and distributed load. These tools can help identify bottlenecks, optimize system behavior, and enhance resilience in real-world scenarios. Some examples include JMeter⁸⁰ and Gatling⁸¹ (focusing on performance testing of applications), Grafana K6 (a full-feature tool for DevOps), Kube-burner⁸² (for K8s clusters' scalability stress testing) and Fortio (a CLI tool running queries per second, recording execution times, and calculating percentiles).

Various **open test-beds** can facilitate the deployment and validation of the CODECO technologies and used for the experimentation of multi-cluster solutions such as SLICES/Fed4FIRE [86]⁸³, FABRIC / GENI [87]⁸⁴, and EdgeNet [88]⁸⁵. The federated SLICES and FABRIC testbeds provide dynamic hardware resources reservation and allocation around the globe allowing for multi-cluster deployments and testing at large-scale. They also provide automations in the resource discovery and allocation with control tools (e.g., GUIs, CLI) such as jFed CLI⁸⁶ and geni-lib⁸⁷. In contrast, EdgeNet is a global K8s cluster, accessed through a Web-based interface and a user-specific config file which provides role-based access control. Another novel K8s native experimentation solution is ClusterSlice [38], which is able to convert testbed resources from bare-metal to slices that can be fully operated and provide automated K8s-centered experimentation.

The **CODECO experimentation framework (CODEF)** is a novel experimentation tool that extends existing approaches to provide a comprehensive framework, with the flexibility to cover a diverse range of resources across heterogeneous platforms and infrastructures. This framework provides easy, fast and reproducible deployment of experiments via a common declarative specification, leveraging Bash scripting, Ansible and SSH, while allowing the

76 <https://www.netdata.cloud/>

77 <https://www.datadoghq.com/>

78 <https://github.com/pixie-io/pixie>

79 <https://github.com/grafana/mimir>

80 <https://github.com/apache/jmeter>

81 <https://github.com/gatling/gatling>

82 <https://github.com/kube-burner>

83 <https://www.fed4fire.eu/>

84 <https://www.geni.net/>

85 <https://www.edge-net.org/>

86 <https://doc.ilabt.imec.be/jfed-documentation/>

87 <https://geni-lib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

modification of a wide set of characteristics for experimentation. Furthermore, it covers the entire experimentation process in an automated manner, starting from node allocation (from scratch e.g., deployment and OS) to application installation and acquisition of results. The CODECO experimentation framework is developed within WP5 and further detailed in Section 5.3.

5.1.2 The CODECO Synthetic Data Generator

CODECO counts with a **Synthetic Data Generator (CSDG)** which has been developed as answer to the lack of available cluster data at a K8s, network, data observability level in an early stage of the project.

CSDG mimics the behaviour of the components that monitor data in CODECO (ACM, NetMA, MDM) and provides the reader with the capability to create large-scale synthetic data derived from (smaller scale) monitoring. CSDG is designed to produce realistic benchmark data corresponding to the metrics described in D9/D10 to be tested with the functionalities offered by CODECO components. For instance, the CODECO-PDLC component, which employs an AI-based approach for behaviour estimation, requires enrichment with data to perform all necessary operations and achieve its objectives. For implementation and code, please refer to deliverable D12.

The version of CSDG available in release v2.0 of the CODECO includes the integration of the new official CRDs from all CODECO components (CODECO-ACM, CODECO-NetMA, and CODECO-MDM), ensuring a production-oriented data flow throughout the entire CODECO Framework. The attributes used in the generator follow the syntax provided on the output of NetMA, ACM, and MDM.

5.2 CODECO Validation Approach

This section provides guidelines for validation with CODECO, being particularly directed to the consortium. These guidelines follow wide-used benchmarking directives such as the ACM SIGSOFT Empirical Standard for Benchmarking⁸⁸. A benchmark consists of four essential components, namely: the quality to be benchmarked, the metrics quantifying the quality, the measurements methods, and the system status during measurement time (e.g., workload, usage profile, tasks).

The methodological approach in CODECO considers first the **collection of a set of potential measurements** and the corresponding **evaluation metrics**. Some indicative metrics are the pod readiness time [39], the pod removal time, the number of failed requests, the load balancer's overhead, measures on the distribution of requests, as well as networking-related metrics such as throughput, latency (RTT), packet loss.

Then, **baseline experiments** are performed, wherein nodes are in an "idle" state, i.e., running but not performing any cluster operations. This allows to measure latencies associated with create and delete operations. To measure other latency types, more sophisticated experimental setups are required, involving operations, such as restart, update. For example, to evaluate failure detection, re-start and recovery time system crashes are simulated by terminating containers abruptly, while users keep sending requests to obtain metrics, such as failed requests (e.g., based on chaos engineering tools). Certain operations of secondary importance, like image pulls, may be omitted through warm-up runs which ensure that images are already present on nodes upon experiment initialisation. In any case, delays should be considered between operations (e.g., via hard-coded waiting times) to achieve realistic conditions and allow the resources to settle down. Moreover, for more complex aspects such

⁸⁸ <https://acmsigsoft.github.io/EmpiricalStandards/docs/?standard=Benchmarking>

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as scalability, the resource demand and load capacity metrics have been proposed⁸⁹, and can be evaluated by varying load and resources combinations to assess the system's ability to scale and handle demands, while maintaining satisfactory QoS. Pertinent tools (e.g., Theodolite) are available for this purpose.

In the data plane, **stress scenarios** [40] in which multiple pods/clusters are initiated in parallel to exhaust available resources are considered to assess the system's performance and resource utilization under heavy workloads. To evaluate networking aspects, both intra-node and inter-node communication are considered in related work [41] with respect to both pod(s)-to-pod(s) and pod(s)-to-service(s) communication. Requests are exchanged among nodes (e.g., in an all-to-all or in a one-to-all request mode) to create multiple routes. Such setup is well-suited for testing the CODECO's NetMA performance, even assuming different networking topologies configurations, e.g., including links with same bandwidth vs heterogeneous scenarios [42]. The work of Kulkarni et focuses on the performance comparison of CNI plugins, and evaluates throughput and RTT, but also the communication overhead. Two scenarios are used: intra-node performance to better assess the communication overhead that stems from routing and the interaction with the host network stack, and inter-node communication.

Overall, orchestration frameworks are typically tested with different numbers of nodes and workloads. One of the most widely used tool to generate workload is K-Bench⁹⁰. During benchmarking, we also consider generating workload using EdgeNet-hosted clients based on defined selectors (e.g., geo-location).

Focusing on **security aspects** of Kubernetes environments, guides/benchmarks such as the NSA/CISA Kubernetes Hardening Guide or the CIS Kubernetes Benchmark provide comprehensive set of practical recommendations and guidelines to enhance security and ensure compliance with industry best practices. They aim to secure Kubernetes components from security threats and vulnerabilities, including the API server, scheduler, etcd, controller manager, worker nodes, etc. By integrating tools such as Kubescape, kube-bench and OpenSCAP vulnerability scanning is automated across multiple frameworks. These tools, which are typically integrated into CI/CD pipelines, systematically check the compliance of Kubernetes clusters, highlighting the security status of different components and configurations. They also generate detailed reports that outline compliance levels (PASS or FAIL results) and provide step-by-step recommendations (remediation), facilitating continuous monitoring and proactive security management. In addition to the previous guides/benchmarks, open-source tools such as Trivy, Clair, Falco and Kyverno can be complementary employed to provide runtime security (e.g., real-time threat detection and monitoring) and policy management/enforcement capabilities.

In these lines, **attack resilience** is also an aspect of particular interest. Security will be ensured by the ACM component and built upon the OCM Submariner tool. Attack resilience will be evaluated against some widely known attack vectors (e.g., flooding, black-hole, or reverse attacks), by imitating sophisticated attacker behaviour and assessing their impact on CODECO performance. Advanced attack detection methods will be assessed, including novel supervised and unsupervised anomaly detection techniques [43], with the involvement of the PDLC component.

Finally, **health-testing** can be utilized to assess the stability of the system, for example measuring the execution time of the health check, since the latter tends to grow, when the system gradually becomes underperforming, e.g., due to a high resource utilization. An

89 <https://www.theodolite.rocks/concepts/metrics.html>

90 <https://github.com/vmware-tanzu/k-bench>

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interesting approach is to combine health check tools (e.g., active monitor⁹¹) with checks based on Argo workflows⁹² and utilize anomaly detection methods to predict reliability issues⁹³.

In CODECO, we also aim to contribute to the state-of-the-art, by devising a **concrete methodology that fits the needs of multi-cluster solutions' benchmarking**. To this end, we are currently considering potential extensions of existing tools so that they support multi-clusters. One promising direction is to extend the k8s-bench-suite⁹⁴, i.e., a scripts collection to benchmark K8s cluster performance (e.g., using knb, a lightweight script for network benchmarking on a target Kubernetes cluster), to enable the automated benchmarking in multi-clusters. These tests also include measurements (e.g., throughput and latency) between pods and services deployed in different clusters. For example, the OCM Hub cluster may also act as an experimentation controller for managed clusters. The former can be configured (via yaml manifest files) and then, automatically control the experiments over the managed clusters, appropriately.

The main purpose is to evaluate CODECO with respect to the CODECO KPIs, as defined in the GA. For instance, we plan to monitor the time taken to setup and configure multiple applications on a single cluster across Edge-Cloud, but the time taken to setup and configure federated clusters, as well. Such metrics will be monitored via well-established multi-cluster monitoring tools, such as Thanos. Similarly, the level of automation achieved during single clusters, but also multi-clusters deployment is crucial. The achieved level can be extracted via the built-in information of automation tools (e.g., Ansible).

To evaluate CODECO components, the consortium will rely on suitable metrics, having as starting point the KPIs provided in the GA Annex II (DoA), and which have been further refined for the use-cases in CODECO (WP5). For instance, ACM can be evaluated with respect to system metrics, such as CPU or memory utilization, the energy consumption per node, the number of failures, or volume of failures of a node. SWM can rely on metrics that have been used for the seamless computing work [44] evaluation, e.g., the migration time comprising the time the scheduler takes to detect the change and re-start a new node. NetMA evaluation might rely on de-facto networking metrics or others like number of hops traversed, lifetime (i.e., counts with the node average consumed energy and link consumed energy).

The guidelines provided are aligned in the context of the CODECO Experimentation Framework. This asset of CODECO is the basis for experimentation in WP5 and follows the methodological approach that has been described in this section.

5.3 CODECO Experimentation Environments

The CODECO experimentation environments belong into three categories: i) the use-case testbeds and lab experiments, referring to the provided experimentation facilities from partners, ii) the CODECO deployment and implementation environment, a multi-cluster environment based on public cloud resources and clusters provided from partners, and iii) the CODECO experimentation framework, which also integrates the open-source EdgeNet software and features to provide in a straightforward manner CODECO technologies to external users. A brief description of the three infrastructure types follows.

91 <https://github.com/keikoproj/active-monitor>

92 <https://argoproj.github.io/argo-workflows/>

93 <https://medium.com/keikoproj/aiops-simple-anomaly-detection-in-kubernetes-with-active-monitor-and-tensorflow-24727c1606e5>

94 <https://github.com/InfraBuilder/k8s-bench-suite>

5.3.1 Use-case Testbeds

This subsection primarily focuses on the deployment environments provided by CODECO partners, aiming to utilize CODECO in specific use-case applications and evaluate its performance in these experimental environments. Thus, six (6) use-cases shall be deployed as the basis for experimentation and demonstrations in operational environments across four (4) different European markets/domains: Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing and Smart Buildings. A short description of the different infrastructures follows:

- **P1 - UGOE / City of Göttingen** will provide a smart-city deployment based on an IoT LoRa/LoRaWAN sensing infrastructure. In particular, 6 locations in the periphery of the City of Göttingen have been selected to monitor the traffic flow, deploying clusters i.e., nodes that consist of LiDARs for object sensing (e.g., Livox HAP, RoboSense M1) and packaged edge devices for DL analysis, processing and classification (based on NVIDIA Edge Computing Developer Kits). In addition, a data center (used for data storage, node control and monitoring), wireless communicating devices (located on the roadside to provide connectivity and information support) and network Infrastructure equipment (e.g. 4G nodes) will be in place to meet the UC requirements. P1 will integrate CODECO into different operational environments across the city, such as mobile Edge nodes (i.e., CODECO toolkits in buses and smart Apps).
- **P2 - i2CAT premises** will establish a heterogeneous urban sensing infrastructure next to a university campus and a highway to create a decentralised cloud-edge digital twin which will monitor and forecast the movements of entities and provide warnings of potential p hazardous scenarios. To achieve this, traffic cameras, On Board Units (OBUs) and V2X Roadside Units (RSUs) developed by i2CAT with LTE-V2X and 802.11p compatibility based on Gateworks hardware will be deployed. Edge devices and nodes (e.g., cameras) will detect the position and trajectory of unconnected moving entities and pass information to the infrastructure. Cloud servers will collect relevant data of the mobility environment (e.g., real-time data) and coordinate the operation of edge nodes, smart 5G Customer Premise Equipments (CPEs) will provide 5G coverage and low latency to the UC area, while vehicles and 5G network infrastructure will support the UC. The CODECO Edge-cloud continuum framework will be used on the infrastructure side of the use-case.
- **P3 - TID's lab facilities and ICOM's fs|cdn - commercial future-proof CDN platform** (coordinated by TID, ICOM and UPM) will provide commercial networking equipment and state-of-the-art computing environments for smart, efficient and QoE-enhanced media delivery (e.g., video streaming, gaming, and AR/ER). The setup will include an SDN/NFV testbed, a metro-core network, and a core control plane lab. The infrastructure will utilize MDS Platform/Servers/Devices (e.g., subscribers) for distributing MDS content, along with network equipment (switches and routers) to expose certain network characteristics and metrics, such as bandwidth or topology to content managers and controllers.
- **P4 - UPM premises/testbed** will deploy Edge-based smart energy nodes to assist in the real-time, efficient and reliable LECEMS (Local Energy Community Energy Management System) across various (university) buildings in the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. This deployment will span three campuses and over 30 buildings, each with different energy requirements and equipped with physical energy-related equipment such as sensors (for energy information acquisition), PV Panels, Smart Meters, Shift Demand Managers, Electric Vehicles & Chargers, and computing equipment (e.g., devices, servers). The system will gather real-time energy data (generation, consumption, price, CO2 emissions), analyze and forecast energy-related decisions based on the available and collected data series.
- **P5 - Fortiss IIoT Lab** will provide an experimental environment based on realistic Industrial IoT scenarios, to provide efficient flexible and cost-reductive ways to support fleets while managing the application workload with K8s/CODECO. The setup will feature

at least 10 Edge nodes (mobile or embedded), including multiple devices, such as an IoT gateway (i.e., MQTT broker/RabbitMQ/Mosquitto), field-level Edge (*Automated Guide Vehicles (AGVs)*, i.e., mobile robots equipped with sensors e.g., TurtleBots or static Raspberry Pi embedded devices) and Cloud (*AGVs controller nodes using Intel Next Unit of Computing, NUC*) nodes. The CODECO framework will be installed across the Fortiss IIoT Lab in 3 phases, starting from a single cluster with static and mobile control plane and concluding with a federated deployment.

- **P6 - Crownstone Platform/Application Deployment** will support the smart buildings use-case in a Crownstone ecosystem (devices, platform and application) to allow the deployment of microapps and optimization of node decision-making. The setup will include end-user infrastructure such as Crownstone nodes (smart terminals), hubs (Raspberry Pi) and bridges (USB-sticks), mobile phones and smart building sensors & actuators. In particular, 100 Crownstones are located in an on-premises building, with an average of approximately 15 Crownstones per hub, while a total of 25 sensors are deployed over the building, connecting via microapp to measure humidity, temperature and presence (all Crownstones) using Bluetooth Low Energy (BTLE).

5.3.2 The CODECO Shared Cloud Infrastructure

Via the common Cloud space provided and managed by IBM, a common CODECO-Experimentation and CODECO-testing infrastructure is initially provided in the form of distinct AWS cluster environments: **experimentation**, and **system testing**. The infrastructure requirements, access list, and additional details are kept in the CODECO internal repository (WP5). Furthermore, all partners are being provided with a How-To developed by partner ATH (responsible for WP5 and the overall experimentation aspects in CODECO), in alignment with partner IBM (provider of the infrastructure) and partner ICOM (responsible for system integration). The use of the CODECO shared infrastructure is currently being available for the consortium only, currently via VPN (Tailscale) or whitelisting access.

The design of the current environment took into consideration consultation developed with all partners involved in the consortium, being minimum requirements of technologies summarized in Table 14.

Table 14: Minimum system requirements of technologies utilized by CODECO.

Technology	Minimum System Requirements					Node type
	Node type	OSS	CPU/vCPU	RAM (GB)	Disk (GB)	
OpenShift/O CM/ACM ⁹⁵	Master	Red Hat Enterprise Linux (RHEL) 7.5, or RHEL Atomic Host 7.4.5 or later	4 CPU; 4 vCPU	16	42	Medium
	Worker		1 vCPU	8	32	Medium
	External etcd Ansible controller			0.075 (75 MB)	20	Medium small
MicroShift		Red Hat Enterprise Linux (RHEL) Extended Update Support (EUS) (9.2 or later)	x86_64 or aarch64 CPU architecture 2 CPU cores	2	2	Small
K3s		- RHEL9, Ubuntu, openSUSE Leap, Oracle Linux, Rocky Linux and SLES - Red Hat/CentOS Enterprise	- x86_64 or armhf or arm64/aarch64 or s390x CPU	0.512 GB (512MB)		Small

⁹⁵ <https://docs.openshift.com/container-platform/3.11/install/prerequisites.html>

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Technology	Minimum System Requirements	Node type
	Linux and Raspberry Pi OS with additional setup	architecture - 1 CPU core

The **experimentation infrastructure** is handled by IBM together with partner ATH (WP5 leader), responsible for the overall experimentation aspects in CODECO. For the experimentation environment, it is currently dimensioned for a cluster (based on the milestones of CODECO) and integrates a cluster with three VMs deployed on Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS with 16-core CPU, 64GB RAM and 100GB disks available for initial experimentation.

The **system testing infrastructure** is handled by IBM together with partner ICOM, responsible for the code integration and system integration testing in CODECO.

CODECO Partners are therefore able to run experiments, install and run the latest or mock versions of individual components to be tested along with other components. This methodology is expected to allow for the seamless development and integration of CODECO components, but also ensure the smooth end-to-end communication between the components' APIs.

The current design considers the CODECO operation for a single cluster environment. Starting from M19, under WP5 a plan for evaluation and further design of the multi-cluster environment will be considered. This addresses the use of the shared cloud space in interconnection with clusters provided by some partners (FOR, ATH, ICOM, etc.), and will be further documented in M24 (D24).

5.3.3 CODECO Deployment and Implementation Environment

The CODECO framework is open-source and available to the community **via the Eclipse CODECO research GitLab**⁹⁶. This repository is continuously updated with contributions from different repositories provided by the CODECO partners and worked directly.

In addition to the public repository, **Partner ICOM provides a private GitLab repository for deployment and implementation**, supporting the overall code integration and deployment over time.

Hence, for testing and validation, partners rely on local facilities. However, in CODECO, Partners shall also rely on a **common experimental and integration infrastructure** which considers individual, local clusters provided by partners and a common Cloud space will be managed and maintained by Partner IBM. Details about the shared cloud space are provided in Section 5.2.2. Partners will use the shared Cloud resources to develop and test the CODECO framework, interconnected with local clusters provided by partners, such as the ICOM provided cluster. Moreover, the design of this experimental framework has been developed in WP5, tested on the premises of Partner ATH, and is currently in the process of being deployed in the experimental cloud space. An overview of the current individual clusters which are expected to be interconnected (via EdgeNet or the CODECO shared Cloud K8s environment) being planned is provided in Table 15.

⁹⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

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Table 15: CODECO individual clusters and potential interconnections via a shared Cloud infrastructure.

Partner	Testbed Title	Purpose	Cluster(s)	EdgeNet or shared
FOR	IIoT Lab/Use-case P5	Deployment of realistic industrial IoT scenarios	10 edge nodes (mobile and embedded) – 1 to 5 clusters	Yes
ATOS	Internal testbed	Monitoring architecture	1 cluster for testing, currently K3s	No
ICOM	fs cdn™		1 cluster, 2 nodes	Yes (security restrictions)
ICOM	K8S Cluster	For executing CI/CD pipelines	1 private cluster	No
ATH	ATH premises	Experimentation (performance evaluation) with K8s and CODECO components through the CODECO Experimentation framework	min 2 private clusters	Yes
UGOE	Use-case P1	smart-city deployment, based on IoT LoRa/LoRaWAN infrastructure (stadtwerke-Goettingen)	1-2 clusters	Yes
SIE	Internal testbed	SWM development	1-2 clusters, internal testing	No
I2CAT	Use-case P2	Heterogeneous urban sensing infrastructure, including cloud servers, edge devices, vehicles, 5G network capabilities	1-2 clusters	Yes (requires authorization first)
TID	TID's lab facilities	TID: Commercial networking equipment and state-of-the-art computer environments for media delivery UC3M: UC3M: three K8 clusters, including one of high availability.	1-5 clusters	Yes (requires authorization first)
UPM	UPM premises	energy management over buildings with different requirements (3 campuses, over 30 buildings)	1-3 clusters	Yes
ALM	Crownstone smart buildings solution	smart building solutions, e.g., energy demand and indoor tracking	Crownstone Nodes; Crownstone Bridges; Crownstone Hubs	Needs to be defined first
IBM	Public Cloud Resources	Plans to have internal testing; closed.	Share Cloud, min 3 clusters, expected 10	No

Via the common shared Cloud infrastructure, CODECO Partners will be able to install and run the latest or mock versions of individual components to be tested along with other components. This methodology is expected to allow for the seamless development and integration of CODECO components, but also ensure the smooth end-to-end communication between the components' APIs.

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The shared resources will be allocated among the CODECO partners, to avoid relying on the private resources of each organization due to the associated security threats. For instance, K8s cluster(s) with sufficient and adjustable resources can be allocated, with each partner using the shared resources and reporting on their test activities to ensure the efficient resource usage/allocation.

Finally, the CODECO shared Cloud infrastructure will also be used for the integration of the complete CODECO framework in the context of the use cases to allow for the development, testing, and public demonstrations. These resources will be supplementary to other resources that will be exploited, e.g., the CODECO Experimentation Framework, able to also deploy EdgeNet. EdgeNet was initially chosen as an example of a globally distributed experimental Edge computing platform, suitable for large-scale experiments, where nodes from around the globe can be interconnected and used in several use-cases, e.g. for internet-scale tests [45]; for workload generation [46].

The plan to exploit the capabilities of CODEF is thoroughly explained in the following subsection.

5.3.4 CODEF Purpose and Guidelines

The CODEF functional design is illustrated in Figure 46 highlighting the distinct and extensible abstraction layers that cover the various experimentation stages. These abstraction layers include:

- **Experiment Manager:** coordination of the experimentation processes.
- **Infrastructure Managers:** cluster nodes creation and allocation over heterogeneous test-beds e.g., bare metal, physical nodes, VMs, Cloud test-beds.
- **Resource Managers:** node-level automation abstraction and software deployment (based on Ansible playbook YAMLS).
- **Experiment Controller:** experiments execution according to the defined parameters and metrics.
- **Result processor:** management of results (statistical evaluation, plotting, post-processing).

Figure 46: CODEF functional architecture.

CODEF provides heterogeneous and multi-domain options through its Infrastructure Managers abstraction layer, enabling deployment capabilities across bare metal, physical machines, VirtualBox and Amazon Cloud or cloud infrastructures (e.g., CloudLab). In addition, the multi-cluster capabilities can be enhanced through the integration of different technologies such as Liqo, Karmada or Submariner, solutions discussed in Section 5.1.

CODEF **purpose** is two-fold: to i) allow validation of CODECO in different use-cases; ii) to support large-scale experimentation in alignment with EdgeNet.

Concerning **validation**, by relying on CODEF, several CODECO components can currently be deployed and evaluated within single or multi-cluster domains⁹⁷. Currently, components such as the ACM and the L2S-M solution (part of the NetMA component) are already integrated into CODEF (rf. to D12 on how to install and run).

CODEF has already been used in different experiments, within distinct infrastructures, hardware specs and K8s ecosystems. These include: i) the evaluation of native networking solutions (e.g., CNI plugins) and their features (tunnelling, security and observability options) across diverse K8s distributions in terms of performance and resource utilization [32] ii) the evaluation of Change Point methods, by extending the “typical” AD (e.g., accuracy and false alarm rate) assessment and highlighting their trade-offs e.g., actual response time and resource footprint [35]; iii) the deployment of more complex software solutions like EdgeNet in functional K8s clusters.

The mentioned work shows some interesting results and useful key findings. For instance, initial results showed that the deployment of networking plugins across lightweight K8s distributions does not ensure a better performance regarding resource footprint or throughput which indicates the need for adjustment in Edge environments. In addition, while

⁹⁷ At the stage of development, CODEF has been implementing the CODECO components as soon as available. For the overall CODECO framework, a release of CODEF is expected until M24 (December 2024).

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experimenting with various AD methods of different complexity, cases where the trade-offs in resource utilization, performance and computational cost overcome “traditional” evaluation metrics, leading to scenarios where a complex but more accurate algorithm may perform poorly in limited resources scenarios, while a less accurate but lightweight method may lead to quicker responses.

To assist the overall wide validation of CODECO, CODEF is currently being planned to be available to the consortium within the CODECO shared Cloud space infrastructure (rf. to section 5.3.3).

Concerning **EdgeNet**, the initial aim of CODECO at a proposal stage was to consider a large-scale representative infrastructure such as EdgeNet to support multi-cluster, multi-tenant experimentation. A distinction between the **EdgeNet infrastructure** and the **EdgeNet software** should be highlighted.

The EdgeNet infrastructure is a distributed Edge-Cloud infrastructure which includes different contributed nodes from around the globe implementing the EdgeNet software as a set of K8s extensions based on CRs. Some basic features include⁹⁸:

- Selective Deployment & Node selection: assign labels through scheduler, allow geolocation- based deployments and pick up nodes through a selector.
- Authority (Permission management): through a user-specific kubeconfig file provided by EdgeNet after the registration and a role-based access control (RoleBinding K8s object).
- Teams: create a namespace for the participants to create slices independently.
- Slicing: among nodes to form isolated subclusters (SliceClaim) by defining a selector - creates a namespace with a resource quota in which defined users participate.
- Isolation: experimenters are assigned their own namespace to interact with EdgeNet.

However, the experimentation and functionality of the different features within the EdgeNet testbed is solely/mainly depending on the support and current status of the EdgeNet infrastructure.

Therefore, the consortium has agreed to focus on relying on a customized version of the EdgeNet open-source software provided by partner ATH to offer the deployment option of CODECO-EdgeNet clusters that integrate some of the inherent EdgeNet features. These include the multi-tenancy and multi-provider features. The former provides different cluster management options such as tenant and role requests, slices and sub-namespaces, while the latter allows to contribute nodes (VMs or physical machines) into a unified CODECO-EdgeNet cluster with a simple bootstrap script. Detailed instructions about the installation, examples, demonstrations and proof of concept are provided in the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab repository⁹⁹. and the D12 deliverable.

The possibility of utilizing the under-development federated capabilities of EdgeNet in CODECO (e.g. to validate CODECO components on various performance aspects) is also under discussion. However, this initiative is currently on hold due to the current state of EdgeNet.

98 <https://github.com/EdgeNet-project/edgenet/tree/main/docs>

99 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

6 Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Guidelines

The section describes the guidelines and infrastructure that the CODECO project has put in place to host its open-source code and to manage its interactions with early adopters, along with supporting open-source best practices such as transparency, openness, meritocracy, and vendor neutrality.

As this deliverable is an update of D9, delivered in M6, this section does not show important modifications apart from an update of the actions in terms of Ecosystem development, the current status of the CODECO repository¹⁰⁰ in the Eclipse Research Labs, the licenses and the plan for coming period.

6.1 Open-Source Governance and the Eclipse Development Process

Professional open-source projects are governed according to certain rules, processes, and best practices to manage contributions and development by diverse communities. This is especially important for vendor-neutral open-source projects which are not managed by a single entity. The aim for CODECO open-source assets is to become community-driven, vendor-neutral open-source projects.

The Eclipse Development Process defines the processes and rules, governance structures and definitions, project roles, releases and reviews, and interaction between projects and the community

The very basis for setting up a successful open-source project with proper governance is the project creation. Figure 47 shows the process of project creation at the Eclipse Foundation.

Figure 47: The Eclipse project creation process.

¹⁰⁰ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

It starts with a proposal describing the project, the content of the code, the license used, the project leader and the first committers. The proposal is made available to the community for review for two weeks. At the end of the community review period, the creation review begins with a trademark review. After the creation review, the project is created and provisioning can begin, i.e., moving the code to the Eclipse Foundation infrastructure and ensuring that the committers paperwork is in place (contributor/committer agreements). After the project is provisioned, an Intellectual Property (IP) review is performed to identify potential issues such as missing copyrights, copying code, or incompatible licenses between dependencies or with the license selected by the project. Finally, once the IP review is complete, the initial contribution is released. It can be safely shared with the rest of the world.

The initial contribution when creating a new project consists of a piece of code of various sizes and may belong to a single organization or different organizations. Contributing a single piece of code, for a single organization, is straightforward and takes between 2 weeks and 2 months for the creation and the IP review. Conversely, in case of a large piece of code and/or many contributors from different organizations, which is the case for a research project, this exercise can take a lot of time and effort. In such a context, the Eclipse Foundation has found that this can slow down the project, which is not desirable as the task usually occurs in the last few months of the research project.

Therefore, we have adapted the project creation process to research projects, allowing project partners to get used to open-source best practices and account for the research and development tasks performed during a research project. **Eclipse Research Labs** aims at gradually and continuously preparing research results to becoming proper open-source projects during the research project lifetime.

6.2 Implementing Open-Source Best Practices

6.2.1 The Eclipse CODECO Research Labs

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab) and trainings to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results. In concrete terms, this means enabling:

- **Open Collaboration:** An open infrastructure (GitLab) has been provided for CODECO consortium collaborate in the open early, which is one of the main guidelines for doing open-source successfully in research projects. It also enables good practices of (open-source) software development such as integrating often and soon, automating the process with continuous testing and integration scripts to identify bugs or broken APIs (Application Programming Interface) as early as possible.
- **Transparency:** It encourages the consortium to work openly: realizing that the code is in the middle of hundreds of millions of public repositories and may go unnoticed, expressing the development plan clearly and openly throughout the process and expressing your decisions clearly and transparently, avoiding drowning them in internal emails. It also eases the communication of early project results to external stakeholders.
- **Community Governance:** Contributor Agreements allow to identify and list the contributors to the open-source project(s) from beginning. Signing the Eclipse Contributor Agreement (ECA)¹⁰¹ is a prerequisite for pushing code in one of the CODECO Research

¹⁰¹ <https://www.eclipse.org/legal/ECA.php>

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Labs repositories. Further information on why an ECA is required and what it is for can be found in the ECA FAQ102.

- **Open-Source Licenses:** It is important to select appropriate licenses for the CODECO outputs, depending on the intended means of exploitation. In the “default cases” this will be EPL-2.0, Apache-2.0 or MIT. As all CODECO results should be commercially exploitable, GPL and similar strong copyleft licenses will be avoided.
- **IPR Review:** IPR reviews help to analyse shared code as early and often as possible to identify potential intellectual property issues, such as missing copyright headers in source files, metadata files in repositories or third-party dependencies with incompatible licenses (alternative compatible libraries can be used).

The Eclipse Research Labs GitLab is hosted by OVH and is in France; it is important for the Eclipse Foundation, located in Europe, and for a European research project to be hosted and managed in Europe, following the European laws on privacy and data protection.

Implementing these best practices will allow the project partners to work in a professional open-source environment - based on proven Eclipse Foundation practices – and ease the transition from research results into proper Eclipse Foundation open-source projects. Furthermore, this approach gives the consortium the room to experiment and define the scope of the resulting open-source projects. This approach is depicted in Figure 47 and is usually realized in three phases:

- **Phase 1: Identification of code to open-source (M1 – M12).** The CODECO consortium selects the parts of the CODECO architecture that are going to be open-source. These parts are immediately moved to the Eclipse Research Labs. Additional open-source components can be moved to Research Labs, while any CODECO component may be created directly in the Eclipse Research Labs if it is intended to be open-source.
- **Phase 2: Open collaboration development (M7 – M36).** During this phase research and development takes place and we ensure the implementation of the open-source best practices and governance principles (transparency, openness, IPR-analyses, contributor agreements).
- **Phase 3: Eclipse project creation (M24 – beyond project).** When the consortium decides to release a component (or a set thereof) as vendor-neutral open-source project, the process of moving the project to become a “real” Eclipse Foundation project can be kicked off (as described in section 6.1). Thanks to the Research Labs approach, the necessary open-source good practices are already in place, so this step will in most cases be very smooth.

102 <https://www.eclipse.org/legal/ecafaq.php>

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Figure 48: Eclipse Research Labs Phases.

The indicated timings of the phases are a rough timeframe. Usually, the phases are overlapping, due to the quite agile nature of research projects and the diversity of parties involved.

Figure 49 shows an indicative timeline, based on the main CODECO outputs related to open source.

Figure 49: CODECO open-source timeline.

In M2, the Eclipse CODECO Research Labs were provisioned, by M6 27 developers signed the Contributor Agreement and joined the CODECO GitLab, while by the date of writing (M18) 48 developers are members of CODECO repository. Initial repositories were created according to the CODECO main components, see Figure 49.

Figure 50: The CODECO Eclipse GitLab repositories at M6.

Once the Research Labs Gitlab was made available and enabled, the partners moved their initial code to it, integrating with their own partner's repositories and setting up the CI/CD process, coordinated by WP3, T3.6 (ICOM). After the intense software development done in the consortium, the final CODECO repository is now available.

Since most of the development partners identified their open-source contributions early during the first year, Y1, they started uploading their open-source code to the CODECO repository at Eclipse Research Labs, kick-starting the Open Collaboration as planned. The remaining and last partners agreeing to open-source their results in the project did it by M12, joining the rest of the consortium. Therefore, the CODECO Toolkit was identified as completely open source, resulting in a big milestone for the project.

By the time of writing, M18, the project partners are developing openly and collaboratively (under **Phase 2**). Most of the components are being developed transparently in the open, following open-source best practices. As a result, all the CODECO sub-repositories have code and have identified the open-source license they would like to apply to their code.

Following a code-first approach, once code is pushed, license compliance and third-party IPR checks start. According to the initial CODECO plan, collaborative development in the open was starting in M6, aiming at having an initial snapshot of the CODECO open-source toolkit in M9 and the first intermediate release at M18. It is expected to start the potential creation of Eclipse Projects from Research Labs components around M24.

As by M12 there was good code in the CODECO repository, the first IPR work began. Figure 51 shows the files which are required and recommended in each sub-repository.

Legal Documentation

Required files:

- License files in all repository roots
- README
- CONTRIBUTING (or equivalent)

Recommended files:

- NOTICES or equivalent (you can use the [Legal Documentation generator](#) available under committer tools)
- CODE_OF_CONDUCT
- SECURITY

See examples for [Security file](#) and [Code of Conduct](#).

Figure 51: Documentation necessary in an open-source repository.

An initial IPR check in the available CODECO GitLab repository revealed some dependencies with third-party libraries, and libraries licensed under restrictive licenses. More information about the IPR checks and the work related to the open-source and non-open-source licenses will be made available in D25 (M24), along with the Community Engagement activities done around the open-source results.

It should be noted that besides creating new CODECO open-source assets, partners will also contribute upstream to existing open-source projects and communities. These efforts and the related community building activities are addressed in WP7, task 7.1, and will be documented in D25 as well.

6.2.2 CODECO OSS Licenses

At the time of writing, the project has reached an agreement and stability in terms of licenses. All the components have a license in the repository, and most of them are licensed under Apache 2.0 license, a permissive license favourable to open source the project results. Just one sub-component is licensed under MIT license (its owner has agreed to move the license to Apache 2.0), while the owner of another component has agreed to license it under Apache 2.0 as well.

Figure 52 shows the CODECO architecture, where each component is labelled with its corresponding license.

Figure 52: CODECO components and the license applied to each module.

As all the components are licensed under the same license, the CODECO project will have only one license, Apache 2.0, increasing the possibilities of adoption of our project by external developers for several reasons:

- Apache 2.0 is a well-known open-source permissive license, and developers tend to adopt code under this license as they are aware that it is legally legitimate to reuse this code.
- One license applied to the project as a whole implies that developers only need to study once the possible consequences of adoption of that code, resulting quick and convenient.

6.2.3 Training

To facilitate the open-source work to the partners and to help understand the open-source best practices, two training sessions were provided to the consortium during the first 6 months of the project life:

- Open-Source Ecosystem, in February 2023, two-hours online workshop.
- Open-Source Licensing and Compliance, June 2023, two-hours online workshop.

During the following 12 months of the project, two more trainings were provided to continue improving the open-source experience in the project and for the partners in charge of CODECO development:

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- Open-Source IPR review, Copyright, Licenses and Metadata, in November 2023. One-hour training in person during the CODECO plenary meeting.
- Intellectual Property and Licences in the Context of European Projects¹⁰³, in April 2024. One-hour online workshop by Wayne Beaton, Director of Open-Source Projects at Eclipse Foundation, as part of the EUCloudEdgeIoT¹⁰⁴ initiative.

7 Summary and Next Steps

The CODECO Deliverable D10 provides an overview on the work developed over the first eighteen months of the project in WP2. D10 corresponds to an update of D9 and integrates work that has been developed in tasks 2.2 (*Technological Boundaries and Global Validation Design Aspects*), tasks 2.3 (*Open-source CODECO Ecosystem Design*), and task 2.4 (*CODECO architectural design*).

D10 provides first an architectural perspective of the CODECO framework and its components across the Edge-Cloud continuum.

The architectural design provided is the basis for the CODECO architecture, envisioning operation within a single-cluster environment. This design can be applied to multi-cluster environments, based on a centralised control plane.

However, such design does not suffice in the face of challenges such as mobility, or far Edge environments. Hence, the deliverable provides in section 4 a discussion on challenges and priorities that need to be tackled to provide a flexible and secure Edge-Cloud orchestration. Main topics to address are debated, and priorities are listed.

In addition to the architectural design, D10 explains global validation approaches, including infrastructures (individual labs from partners, and a shared Cloud infrastructure) being used in CODECO. D10 covers as well CODEF, which is a relevant CODECO asset for supporting robust validation based on CODECO mechanisms.

The work presented in D10 will continue in WP4. The guidelines for validation are relevant to the work under development in WP5. Furthermore, the OSS Ecosystem guidelines are essential in the context of WP7. WP7 shall further develop the CODECO ecosystem, by considering the proposed methodology and timeline detailed in section 6.

The architectural design of CODECO is, however, not complete. During WP4, CODECO will update the architectural design taking into consideration the approaches followed for its FC operation. The final updates to the CODECO architecture, concerning its operation in federated, multi-tenant environments, will be provided in D14 together with the final code of CODECO (WP4, M36).

¹⁰³ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/event/intellectual-property-and-licences-in-the-context-of-european-projects>

¹⁰⁴ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

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Annex I – CODECO Cross-Layer Metrics

This annex provides a global perspective of the minimum sub-set of metrics for:

- The definition of a CODECO Application Model (QoS, QoE preferences from user DEV concerning the application to be deployed across far Edge-Cloud), as
- The minimum subset of metrics currently expected to be collected by different components (NetMA, MDM, ACM).

Some of the metrics here described are not yet integrated into the architectural concept of CODECO and are expected to be discussed during the second phase of the project. They are nonetheless described here for the sake of future research guidelines. These metrics are highlighted in red.

Table 16: CODECO Application Model Attributes, spec, and status.

ID (attribute)	Description	How it is handled
Spec		
Userid	Identification of the user DEV setting up an application.	Available in K8s, but should be provided by other CODECO components by ACM
Usergroup	Identification of the group of user DEV	Available in K8s, but should be provided by other CODECO components by ACM
QoS	Preferred QoS level. A scale 1-5 is provided to the user and converted to a desired QoS model, e.g., Diffserv codepoints.	New, to be discussed in the second phase of CODECO (M19-M36)
failureTolerance	Desired tolerance to infrastructure failures. The user selects a %	To be provided by CODECO. Failure_tolerance is currently computed in PDLC (sub-component PDLC-CA) as an aggregate metric that considers parameters from the computational infrastructure and from the networking infrastructure (NetMA)
energyExpenditure	Maximum desired level of energy expenditure for the overall K8s infrastructure serving an application group.	Energy expenditure of the infrastructure is provided by PDLC (PDLC_CA) based on node expenditure (ACM, Prometheus) and link/path expenditure
securityClass	Desired level of security based on a scale of 1-5	To be provided by CODECO, ACM.
complianceLevel	expected level of compliance, based on a scale of 1-5	Provided by MDM
Input_data_size	Expected volume of input data for the application. 0 implies no input data. Expressed in the same units as the mem.	Provided by MDM
Output_data_size	Expected volume of output data for the application. 0 implies no output data. Expressed in the same units as the mem.	Provided by MDM
Status		
avgAppCpu	Aggregation of the CPU usage of all the services in the app (in vCPU	Provided by ACM

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ID (attribute)	Description	How it is handled
	units)	Provided by ACM
avgAppMemory	Aggregation of the memory usage of all the services in the app	
numPods	The number of the pods instantiated for the application	
avgServiceCpu	Average CPU usage per micro-service pod	
avgServiceMemory	Average memory usage per micro service pod	
clusterName	Cluster name (unique, assigned by K8s)	
nodeName	Node name (unique, assigned by K8s)	
podName	Pod name (unique, assigned by K8s)	
serviceName	Service name, user assigned in the app model, non-unique (can have multiple instances of the same service)	
avgNodeCpu	Avg CPU consumption of the application on this node (aggregation of service CPU over the node)	
avgNodeEnergy	Avg energy consumption of the node	
avgNodeFailure	node failures averaged over a specific time window (Exponential moving average)	
avgNodeMemory	Avg memory consumption of the application on this node (aggregation of service memory over the node)	
nodeName	Node name (unique, assigned by K8s)	

Table 17: CODECO metrics being collected by MDM.

ID (attribute)	Description	Type	CODECO components relying on the metrics
nodeName	identifier of the node in K8s	string	All
freshness	Measuring the healthiness of a node, to whether it is able to ensure that new or updated data of its existing workload is processed in a timely fashion and that the dataset grows in stable specified size.	string	PDLC
compliance	Data Compliance refers to the desired adherence to regulations and policies derived from geographical zones regulation, etc	string	PDLC
portability	How effective the application workload performs in the current node in comparison to a former node.	string	N/A

Table 18: CODECO metrics being collected by NetMA.

ID (attribute)	Description	Type	CODECO components relying on the metrics
nodeName	Identifier of the node in K8s	string	All
name (inside link)	Identifier of the link of a node	string	All
NSM: netma-nsm-mon (underlay metrics at a node level)			
uLinkFailure	Number of failures of a link	integer	PDLC
uPacketLoss	<u>Amount of packet losses in a connection.</u>	float	PDLC
uNodeNetFailure	Sum of elink_failure and link_failure	integer	PDLC
uNodeBandWidth	Egress bandwidth for a node - sum of bw for all Egress links on that node	string	PDLC
uNodeDegree	In a network, the degree of a node is defined as the sum of all edges connected to it (later, ingress and egress links)		PDLC
uLatencyNanos	Latency (EMA) for all egress links of a worker node	string	PDLC
uLinkenergy	The average expenditure of energy over a time window (EMA) for a specific link	string	PDLC
NSM (netma-nsm-npp) and Secure Connectivity			
oNodeBandWidth	Ingress bandwidth for a node - sum of bw for all ingress links on that node	string	SWM
oNodeDegree	Sum of all Channels for a source node	integer	
oLatencyNanos/	average latency derived from elink latency; can be based on RTT	string	SWM, PDLC
uPathLength	Number of hops traversed; Average Shortest Path Length	integer	SWM, PDLC

Annex II – CODECO Application Model

```
apiVersion: codeco.he-codeco.eu/v1alpha1
kind: CodecoApp
metadata:
  generation: 1
  name: codecoappinstance3
  namespace: he-codeco-acm
  resourceVersion: "1456"
  uid: 5c948d7e-43d6-425b-b0b2-76402b606e07
spec:
  appEnergyLimit: "20"
  appFailureTolerance: ""
  appName: acm-swm-app
  codecoapp-msspec:
    - nwbandwidth: "1.2"
      nwlatency: "3"
  podspec:
    containers:
      - image: quay.io/skupper/hello-world-backend:latest
        name: skupper-backend
      ports:
        - containerPort: 8080
          name: skupper-backend
          protocol: TCP
    resources:
      limits:
        cpu: "2"
        memory: 4Gi
  serviceChannels:
    - advancedChannelSettings:
        bandwidth: "5"
        frameSize: "100"
        maxDelay: "1"
        sendInterval: "10"
      chanelName: frontend
      otherService:
        appName: acm-swm-app
        port: 9090
        serviceName: front-end
      serviceName: backend
    - nwbandwidth: "1.2"
      nwlatency: "3"
```


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```
podspec:
  containers:
  - image: quay.io/dekelly/frontend-app:v0.0.2
    name: front-end
    ports:
    - containerPort: 8080
      protocol: TCP
  serviceChannels:
  - advancedChannelSettings:
    bandwidth: "5"
    frameSize: "100"
    maxDelay: "1"
    sendInterval: "10"
    chanelName: backend
    otherService:
      appName: acm-swm-app
      port: 8080
      serviceName: backend
    serviceName: front-end
  complianceClass: High
  qosClass: Gold
  securityClass: Good
```

Figure 53: Example for the CAM, simple application.

